

Zero PM

Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances

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**Report on EU-level policy zero-pollution ambitions:
analysis of actions, needs, and challenges for meeting
ambitions**

Work Package 3 – Policy analysis, development, and
assessment

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Summary

This report is deliverable 3.1: Report on EU-level policy zero-pollution ambitions: analysis of actions, needs, and challenges for meeting ambitions, in the H2020 ZeroPM project. It is part of Work Package 3 ‘Policy analysis, development, and assessment’, which aims to stimulate and support policy changes to more effectively tackle PMT/vPvM substances. The report presents the results from the first task of WP3 (task 3.1), which aimed to review the EU’s overarching policy ambitions, objectives, and targets for the sustainable use of chemicals in order to understand the context in which ZeroPM is working and the objectives it should contribute to.

The deliverable provides an overview of the relevant policy scope that will be covered in WP3 in terms of substances, sectors and uses, and policies (section 2 of the deliverable), as was outlined in Milestone 4 of ZeroPM. In section 3, the deliverable provides information on targets and measures contained in Green Deal strategies that are relevant for preventing the emission of PMT/vPvM substances to the environment and thus exposure to these substances. It also maps the links between these targets and measures to work that will be carried out in the different ZeroPM work packages. The detailed review of Green Deal strategies, carried out in preparation of this deliverable is available in Appendix A to O.

The work carried out in task 3.1 aimed to set the scene for upcoming work in WP3. As part of task 3.2, WP3 will carry out a more detailed analysis of opportunities and gaps in the existing policy and legal framework for preventing PMT/vPvM substances from entering the environment. WP3 will then develop policy options for preventing emissions from PMT/vPvM substances and explore their effectiveness, feasibility and impacts on different actors (task 3.3 and 3.4).

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1 Introduction

1.1 Context and objectives of the deliverable

ZeroPM, which stands for Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances, is a 5 year long, European research project funded under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation program. ZeroPM will interlink and synergize three strategies to protect the environment and human health from persistent and mobile (PM) substances: **Prevent**, **Prioritize** and **Remove**. To do this, ZeroPM will develop an evidence-based multilevel framework. The framework will guide policy, technological and market incentives to minimize use, emissions and pollution of entire groups of PM substances.

The work package ‘Policy analysis, development, and assessment’ (WP3) aims to contribute to the strengthening, improvement, and enforcement of the EU chemicals policy framework in order to more effectively regulate persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) and very persistent and very mobile (vPvM) substances as well as incentivise and create an enabling environment for the uptake of alternative, sustainable chemicals. The first task in this work package aims to review the EU’s overarching policy ambitions, objectives, and targets for the sustainable use of chemicals in order to understand the context in which ZeroPM is working and the objectives it should contribute to. As part of this task, recent EU strategies and action plans published in the context of the Green Deal, were reviewed to determine which targets and measures contained in these strategies are relevant for preventing the emission of PMT/vPvM substances to the environment and thus exposure to these substances. The relevant targets and measures were then mapped to link them to the work that will be carried out in the different ZeroPM work packages. The results of this review are provided in this deliverable – Deliverable 3.1: Report on EU-level policy zero-pollution ambitions: analysis of actions, needs, and challenges for meeting ambitions.

1.2 Methodology

Documents reviewed for this deliverable include strategies and action plans published in the context of the European Green Deal, as well as a small number of other strategies adopted prior to the European Green Deal such as the Plastics Strategy. Annexes and documents accompanying all Commission strategies listed in Table were also reviewed.

Table 1 List of strategies reviewed

▼ Biodiversity Strategy (COM(2020) 380 final)
▼ Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (COM(2020) 667 final)
▼ Circular Economy Action Plan (COM(2020) 98 final)
▼ European Green Deal (COM/2019/640 final)
▼ Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan (COM(2021) 44 final)
▼ Farm to Fork Strategy (COM(2020) 381 final)
▼ Industrial Strategy for Europe (COM(2020) 102 final and COM(2021) 350 final)
▼ Pharmaceutical Strategy (COM(2020) 761 final)
▼ Renovation Wave for Europe (COM(2020) 662 final)
▼ Soil Strategy for 2030 (COM(2021) 699 final)
▼ Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy (COM(2018) 28 final)

- ▼ Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy (COM(2021) 240 final)
- ▼ Sustainable and Circular Textiles Strategy (COM(2022) 141 final)
- ▼ Zero Pollution Action Plan (COM/2021/400 final) and SWD ‘Towards a monitoring and outlook framework for the zero pollution ambition’ (SWD(2021) 141 final)

In order to collate information for all of the strategies, a template was developed and completed for all documents listed above. The template allowed relevant actions for ZeroPM to be identified. The content of the template is described in Table and shown in Appendix A.

Table 2 Sections of the template

Title and reference of document
▼ Brief description & relevance for ZeroPM
▼ Links to relevant documents
▼ Objectives (general objectives and specific objectives)
▼ Actions listed in document. Distributed according to the following categories: “Prevent & Reduce”, “Prioritize”, “Remediation” (and “Other”) and sub-categories (research and development; policy realignment; tightening and reformation of relevant legislation; raising awareness (towards consumers and non-consumers); stakeholder cooperation; financing)
▼ Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback (only filled in when synopsis report available)
▼ Challenges (only filled when explicitly mentioned in the text of the strategy)
▼ Timeline (adoption and expected review of strategy)
▼ Relevant policies and legislation mentioned in the documents
▼ Links to other ZeroPM Work Packages (links between policies and actions listed in strategies and the work carried out under the different work packages of ZeroPM)

All of the completed templates are provided in the appendices to this deliverable (Appendices B to O).

2 Policy scope for Work Package 3

The work carried out for this deliverable supported the completion of the first milestone under WP3 (Milestone 4), whereby lists of substance groups, uses and sectors for policy analysis and identification of policy action were identified. This list defines the scope of WP3 and will serve as a reference for the various tasks undertaken in this work package.

2.1 Substances

The list of substance groups and individual substances within these groups for the first phase of ZeroPM was agreed upon during the project kick-off phase. This list serves as a reference for WP3 and is presented in Table 3. It is noted that each WP in ZeroPM may consider more or just a subsection of the substance list in Table 3. For instance, WP5 will consider all substances belonging to a group, WP2 and WP4 will focus on some uses of a subset of the substance list, and WP6 and WP7 will both include some substances on the list, but will also expand this to include others belong to the same group. WP3 will primarily consider policies affecting substance groups – e.g. the

regulation of PFAS as a group – although policies affecting single substances may be considered when relevant.

Table 3: Persistent and mobile substance groups for the first phase of ZeroPM

PREVENT	PRIORITIZE		REMOVE	
Substances and Uses	PMT/vPvM substances and structure group ^A	Hazards Indicated	Technical Challenges	
PFAS <i>Uses:</i> fluoropolymer processing aids, emulsifiers, flame retardants, ski waxes, lubricants others	TFMSA, PFEtS, PFPrS, PFBS, PFPeS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS, TFA, PFPrA, PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, 6:2 FTS, GenX, FAP, Bisfluramide, PFECHS, ADONA	 small PFAS, n=0	- PFBS and GenX recently categorized as SVHC under REACH - many known and unknown PFAS with unknown hazards	Removal requires expensive treatment like reverse osmosis or next generation technologies.
Triazines <i>Uses:</i> melamine resins (laminates), flame retardants, wood resins, agricultural chemicals (e.g. plant protection products and fertilisers), biocides	Melamine, Cyanuric Acid, Ametryn, Ammeline, 6-phenyl-1,3,5-triazine-2,4-diyldiamine, Ammelide, 2,4,6-trichloro-1,3,5-triazine, 4-[(4,6-Dichloro-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl)amino]benzene-1-sulfonic acid, Trithiocyanuric acid, Atrazine	 s-Triazines	- Triazines interact to form nephrotoxic complexes. - Melamine STOTRE2 classification - found in banned herbicides, like atrazine	Small triazines are permeable to most water remediation technology (e.g. activated carbon filtration).
Triazoles <i>Uses:</i> anticorrosive agents, fungicides, agricultural chemicals, UV-filters	Benzotriazole, 1H-1,2,4-Triazole, 4-Methyl-1H-benzotriazole, 5-Methyl-1H-benzotriazole	 1,2,3- & 1,2,4-Triazole	- Chronic effect concentrations (aquatic species) reported in low µg/L - alternatives available with unknown hazards	Water and sludge treatment methods are ineffective.

More chemical information can be found here <https://zenodo.org/record/5854252#.YroQZRXMl2w>

2.2 Sectors and uses

Industrial and agricultural activities and consumer products, which may be sources of PMT/vPvM substance pollution, are numerous and cover many sectors. Uses of the largest group of persistent and mobile substances, PFAS, have been mapped by Glüge et al. (2020), where more than 200 uses of PFAS under 64 use categories (which are further divided into 21 ‘industry branches’ and 43 ‘other use categories’) listed in Table , were identified. As PFAS are the largest group of PMT/vPvM substances, and they are used in a wide range of products and industrial processes, the inventory presented provides a good indication of which product and/or sectoral policies are relevant to address PMT/vPvM substances.

Table 4 PFAS use categories. Source: Glüge et al. (2020)

Industrial branches

▼ Aerospace	▼ Mining
▼ Biotechnology	▼ Nuclear industry
▼ Building and construction	▼ Oil & gas industry
▼ Chemical industry	▼ Pharmaceutical industry
▼ Electroless plating	▼ Photographic industry
▼ Electroplating	▼ Production of plastic and rubber
▼ Electronic industry	▼ Semiconductor industry
▼ Energy sector	▼ Textile production
▼ Food production industry	▼ Watchmaking industry
▼ Machinery and equipment	▼ Wood industry
▼ Manufacture of metal products	

Other use categories

▼ Aerosol propellants	▼ Medical utensils
▼ Air conditioning	▼ Metallic and ceramic surfaces
▼ Antifoaming agent	▼ Music instruments
▼ Ammunition	▼ Optical devices
▼ Apparel Particle physics	▼ Paper and packaging
▼ Automotive	▼ Personal care products
▼ Cleaning compositions	▼ Pesticides
▼ Coatings, paints and varnishes	▼ Pharmaceuticals
▼ Conservation of books and manuscripts	▼ Pipes, pumps, fittings and liners
▼ Cook- and baking ware	▼ Plastic, rubber and resins
▼ Dispersions	▼ Preservatives
▼ Electronic devices	▼ Printing
▼ Fingerprint development	▼ Refrigerant systems
▼ Fire-fighting foam	▼ Sealants and adhesives
▼ Flame retardants	▼ Soldering
▼ Floor covering including carpets and floor polish	▼ Soil remediation
▼ Glass	▼ Sport article
▼ Household applications	▼ Stone, concrete and tile
▼ Laboratory supplies, equipment and instrumentation	▼ Textile and upholstery
▼ Leather	▼ Tracing and tagging
▼ Lubricants and greases	▼ Water and effluent treatment
	▼ Wire and cable insulation, gaskets and hoses

2.3 Policies

Given the vast array of uses and sectors that are relevant for persistent and mobile substances, ZeroPM believes that it is important that the legal framework takes a global approach to addressing persistent and mobile substances, covering all types of pollution sources, as well as human exposure pathways.

Emissions of persistent and mobile substances to the environment come from a wide range of sources, both point and diffuse, and through multiple pathways across the complete life cycle of the substance, covering manufacture, use, disposal and recycling. The emissions can fall into the following:

- ▼ Industrial plants manufacturing and/or using chemicals that discharge chemicals into the air, soil and surface and groundwater.
- ▼ Waste management infrastructure including landfills releasing chemicals into soils and water, incineration plants discharging chemicals into the air which then settle on land and in water, wastewater treatment plants discharging chemicals that are not removed during treatment and which then contaminate drinking water supplies.
- ▼ Biosolids produced by wastewater treatment plants that are contaminated themselves and then applied to agricultural fields resulting in contamination of soil and subsequently to crops grown on the soil.
- ▼ Contamination from the application of pesticides in agriculture areas.
- ▼ Diffuse pollution from use, disposal and recycling of products containing chemicals.

The main sources of human exposure to chemicals include drinking water, food and consumer products. Figure , from the European Environmental Agency, shows the routes through which persistent and mobile substances – in this case focusing on PFAS – can move in the environment.

Figure 1 Typical PFAS exposure pathways. Taken from EEA (2019)

Based on the exposure sources and pathways shown in Figure , the relevant legal framework to address PMT/vPvM substances (summarized in Figure 2) can be considered to span across a wide range of policies and legislation, including those:

- ▼ banning or restricting the manufacturing, placing on the market and use of substances and substances in products
- ▼ requiring industrial facilities or other sectoral activities to take preventive measures against pollution
- ▼ setting concentration limits in environmental compartments or food
- ▼ requiring the monitoring of certain substances in environmental compartments
- ▼ establishing rules for the collection, treatment, reuse, recycling, decontamination and disposal of certain types of waste
- ▼ establishing the polluter pays principle to prevent and remedy environmental damage

Figure 2 Policy scope to address PMT/vPvM substances

Mirroring Figure presenting exposure pathways and sources, Figure 3 shows the relevant policy areas for addressing PMT/vPvM substances.

- (1) Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) Regulation; Classification, Labelling, and Packaging (CLP) Regulation; Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) Regulation; Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR);
- (2) Industrial Emissions Directive (IED); European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR);
- (3) Waste Framework Directive (WFD), Restriction of Hazardous Substances (RoHS) Directive; Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (PPWD); Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD);
- (4) Water Framework Directive (WFD); Environment Quality Standards Directive (EQSD), Groundwater Directive (GWD); Drinking Water Directive (DWD); Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD); Ambient Air Quality Directive (AAQD), National Emission Ceilings Directive (NECD); Plant Protection Product Regulation (PPPR); Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive (SUPD).

Figure 3 Relevant policy areas to address PMT/vPvM substances. Figure based on EEA (2019) and adapted for ZeroPM.

3 Overview of EU strategies

This section presents the review of the Green Deal strategies, which was carried out to identify those strategies of relevance for ZeroPM and thus those that should be followed in WP3. The review was also carried out to identify targets and measures relevant for the work carried out in ZeroPM.

The goals of ZeroPM reflect the current changing political landscape of the European Union. The Green Deal, which was presented by the European Commission in 2019, aims to achieve carbon neutrality and zero pollution by 2050. To achieve its goal, the

Green Deal provides a holistic policy framework to transform the economy towards increased sustainability and address environmental degradation. Addressing pollution from chemicals is fundamental to achieving both ambitions as it will support the establishment and development of sustainable value chains and will prevent and remediate environmental degradation.

Key priorities from the Green Deal to address chemical pollution are the Zero Pollution Ambition for a toxic free environment, preserving and restoring ecosystems and biodiversity, as well as mobilising industry for a clean and circular economy (Figure).

Figure 4 Elements of the European Green Deal. Source: COM(2019) 640 final, p.3

3.1 Objectives and targets related to chemicals pollution

The three key priorities to address chemicals pollution shown in Figure are detailed and translated into objectives, including in a quantitative form in set targets (e.g. quantified reduction of chemicals use or emission by a set deadline), in subsequent policy documents. The Zero Pollution Action Plan sets the general ambition to achieve zero pollution by 2050, when ‘*air, water and soil pollution is reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems and that respect the boundaries our planet can cope with*’ (COM(2021) 400 final, p.3). This general target is complemented by the Soil Strategy and the Biodiversity Strategy, which set the ambition that soils and ecosystems are restored and adequately protected by 2050. An intermediary target set for 2030 is to have achieved significant progress regarding soil remediation and biodiversity recovery. To contribute to the Zero Pollution Ambition, strategies aiming at achieving sustainable and clean value chains and the phase out of hazardous substances from these value chains, set an earlier target to be achieved by 2030. In particular, the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability towards a toxic free environment sets a target for reaching clean chemicals value chains, aiming that, by

2030, ‘chemicals are produced and used in a way that maximises their contribution to society, including achieving the green and digital transition, while avoiding harm to the planet and to current and future generations’ (COM(2020) 667 final, p.3).

The Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability is the main and most focused Green Deal strategy addressing chemicals pollution and contributing to the achievement of the Zero Pollution Ambition. The Strategy is organised around two main objectives, shifting production towards safe and sustainable by design chemicals and addressing environmental and health concerns of chemicals, including by strengthening the legal framework to achieve zero chemical pollution in the environment. The Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability directly addresses persistent and mobile substances, and in particular a subgroup of them, PFAS. The actions of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability relevant for ZeroPM are described in section 3.3.

In addition, chemicals pollution is addressed more generally in other Green Deal strategies as a type of pollution to prevent. The Biodiversity Strategy identifies pollution as a key driver of biodiversity loss and indicates that the following pressures must be reduced: ‘the release of nutrients, chemical pesticides, pharmaceuticals, hazardous chemicals, urban and industrial wastewater, and other waste including litter and plastics’ (COM(2020) 380 final, p.13). Preventing soil pollution is one of the four objectives around which the Soil strategy is built and the strategy identifies chemicals, pesticides, fertilisers and pharmaceuticals as priorities for action (COM(2021) 699 final, p.16). The Farm-to Fork Strategy, the Biodiversity Strategy and the Soil Strategy contain targets for the reduction of pesticide use. Of particular importance is the target to reduce the use of the most hazardous pesticides by 50% by 2030 (COM(2020) 381 final, p.6). The Sustainable Blue Economy strategy highlights the importance of clean oceans and identifies chemical pesticides, nutrients and microplastic as main sources of pollution to be tackled (COM(2021) 240 final, p.6).

Strategies aiming at achieving sustainable and clean value chains generally address chemicals pollution through the objective of phasing out hazardous substances from products and industrial processes. The Circular Economy Action Plan aims to address the presence of hazardous chemicals in products through the development of a sustainable policy framework and by aiming to prevent and remove hazardous and persistent substances from contaminating secondary-raw-material-cycles (COM(2020) 98 final, p.13). The Circular Economy Action Plan largely picks up on the objectives of the Plastics Strategy, adopted in 2018, and before the Green Deal, to phase out substances that hamper recycling processes. The Industrial Strategy sets the objective of creating green and digital transition pathways for 14 ‘industrial ecosystems’, identified as priorities for the EU Recovery plan and investments projects. These 14 ‘industrial ecosystems’ include sectors that are large users of chemicals, such as aerospace and defence, construction, digital, electronics, energy intensive industries, renewable energies, mobility – transport – and automotive, and textile. Transition pathways, which involve a co-creation process with stakeholders, should lead to specific voluntary pledges such as commitments on circularity and circular business models. It remains unclear whether these transition pathways will also include specific actions on chemicals use. The Sustainable Textile Strategy defines the overarching goal for 2030 that ‘textile

products placed on the EU market are [...] free of hazardous substances' (COM(2022) 141 final, p.2). Although not its core objective, the Pharmaceutical Strategy aims to reduce the impact of pharmaceutical production and use on the environment, through the development of environmentally sustainable pharmaceuticals and the improvement of environmental risk assessment of chemicals, and to improve the disposal of medicines – in particular residues, that may have endocrine-disrupting potential or increase the risk of antimicrobial resistance.

The main objective of the Renovation Wave strategy is to increase the energy efficiency and reduce the climate impact of buildings. The strategy lists the integration of '*high health and environmental standards*' including '*ensuring high air quality, good water management, [...] or the removal of and protection against harmful substances such as asbestos and radon*' (COM(2020) 662 final, p.13) as one of the 'key principles for building renovation'. However, it does not further address the presence of hazardous substances, such as PFAS (or other persistent and mobile substances), in construction products and does not establish a link with the actions under the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. With the delayed adoption of the Sustainable Built Environment Strategy, the Renovation Wave strategy currently is the only Green Deal strategy addressing the construction sector. Although planned in the Circular Economy Action Plan, the Sustainable Built Environment Strategy might not be adopted on the grounds that many of the planned actions have been frontloaded in the Renovation Wave strategy and the EU Recovery Plan. If this was to be the case, the Renovation Wave strategy could remain the only Green Deal strategy addressing the construction sector and its lack of measures addressing chemicals in construction, together with the absence of reference to the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, may constitute a policy gap.

3.2 The Zero Pollution Hierarchy

To achieve the objectives and targets set out in the documents detailed above, the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and the Zero Pollution Action Plan are built around the Zero Pollution Hierarchy. The hierarchy assumes that EU environmental policies should be based on the precautionary principle and preventative action, preventing pollution at the source as a priority, and only in cases when this is not fully possible, minimising and controlling pollution and finally remediating environmental damage. The Zero Pollution Hierarchy is represented as a reverse pyramid showing the three types of actions 'prevent', 'minimise and control' and 'eliminate and remediate', indicating the ambition of reversing the current approach to pollution by focusing on prevention (Figure).

Union policy on the environment shall be based on the **precautionary principle** and on the principles that **preventive action** should be taken, that environmental damage should as a priority be **rectified at source** and on the **polluter pays principle**.

Figure 5 The Zero Pollution Hierarchy. Source: Zero Pollution Action Plan (COM(2021) 400 final, p.4)

The Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability uses a similar hierarchy tailored to chemicals management called the Toxic Free Hierarchy. The hierarchy prioritises the development of safe and sustainable chemicals, clean production and recycling processes and the phase out of substances of concern for non-essential uses. Minimise and control efforts are directed towards risk management measures achieved through the promotion of modern and smart production processes and safe and sustainable uses and business models. The least favourable solution in the hierarchy is the elimination of substances of concern in waste and secondary raw materials and the promotion of clean recycling solutions (Figure).

Figure 6 The Toxic free Hierarchy. Source: Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (COM(2020) 667 final, p.4)

Although not directly referring to the Zero Pollution Hierarchy, some of the other strategies take a similar approach and address the different components of the hierarchy with a focus on prevention. The Biodiversity Strategy combines prevention (preventing pollution harmful for biodiversity) and remediation (remediating polluted sites and restoring ecosystems). The Soil Strategy recognizes that ‘contamination should be prevented at source as a priority’ (COM(2021) 699 final, p;16) but also sets the objective of having achieved significant progress in the remediation of contaminated sites by 2030. Other sectoral strategies are mostly focused on prevention and the development of sustainable sectoral value chains (e.g. Farm to Fork Strategy, Circular Economy Action Plan, Industrial Strategy, Sustainable Textile Strategy).

3.3 Main actions relevant for ZeroPM

The Green Deal strategies announce several regulatory and non-regulatory initiatives that will be followed closely by the ZeroPM project as part of WP3, to identify potential gaps and ensure a harmonized strategy for PMT/vPvM substances consistent with the Zero Pollution ambition. These initiatives are presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Regulatory and non-regulatory initiatives that will be followed by ZeroPM

To follow these regulatory and non-regulatory initiatives, and identify appropriate moments to provide input on these initiatives (through calls for evidence and consultation processes), a regulatory watch has been set up in WP3. A Gantt chart showing when the various initiatives mentioned below are expected is available in Appendix P.

Phasing out of PFAS and PMT/vPvM substances

The Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability plans for the creation of new hazard classes and criteria in the CLP Regulation, including those for PMT/vPvM substances. This would be complemented by the amendment of Article 57 of the REACH Regulation to add these substances to the list of substances of very high concern (SVHC) (COM(2020) 667 final, p.10). These amendments are expected this year in the upcoming Commission

proposals for the two regulations. Following the introduction of these criteria, the phase out and substitution of harmful PMT/vPvM substances will be promoted through the authorisation and restriction processes under REACH and through the generic approach (outlined below) in product legislation. Further, the broad PFAS restriction currently under development will seek to restrict all non-essential uses of PFAS and where necessary replace PFAS with less harmful alternatives.

The Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability supports a gradual movement away from assessing and regulating chemicals substance-by-substance to regulating them in groups. This will be supported by the implementation of the generic approach to risk management, which, according to the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, should become the default approach. The generic approach to risk management implies that risk management measures are automatically triggered based on the hazardous properties of a substance and generic exposure considerations. This approach is already implemented in several pieces of legislation for carcinogenic, mutagenic and reproductive toxicants (CMR), which are banned by default, sometimes with exceptions allowed, in consumer products such as cosmetics or toys. To support group assessments, the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability plans that the generic approach will be extended to '*chemicals that cause cancers, gene mutations, affect the reproductive or the endocrine system, or are persistent and bioaccumulative*' (COM(2020) 667 final, p.10). This will be implemented through the revisions of REACH, and sectoral product legislation, such as the Cosmetic Regulation, the Toy Safety Directive, and the Food Contact Material legislation, which are all planned to happen in 2022. In parallel, an impact assessment should be launched to determine whether and how the generic approach can be extended to other chemicals present in consumer products (including those '*affecting the immune, neurological or respiratory systems and chemicals toxic to a specific organ*') and which product legislation should be concerned (COM(2020) 667 final, p.10). Based on the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, the generic approach will not be exclusively applied in case of human health risks but should also cover some environmental risks (i.e. persistent and bioaccumulative substances), which leaves the possibility that the generic approach could be extended to PMT/vPvM substances, following the creation of the new hazard class.

Before the generic approach to risk management is fully in place, the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability plans for the prioritisation of substances falling under the generic approach (see above) for group restrictions. The Strategy also proposes to address PFAS as a group, under REACH and under other relevant legislation including water, sustainable products, food, industrial emissions, and waste (COM(2020) 667 final, p.14). Two restrictions under REACH are already being prepared – one regarding PFAS in firefighting foams for which a restriction dossier is under public consultation and the other regarding the manufacture, placing on the market and uses of PFAS, for which the restriction dossier is expected early 2023. It is also anticipated that PFAS will be addressed as a group through the revisions of the Environmental Quality Standards Directive, the Groundwater Directive, the Industrial Emissions Directive and the Food Contaminants Regulation which will take place in 2022, as well as the revision of the Sewage Sludge Directive planned for 2023. As PFAS are a strong focus of ZeroPM, the

REACH restrictions and the revisions of these pieces of legislation are being closely followed.

The implementation of the generic approach to risk management as the default approach for most hazardous chemicals and the introduction of group restrictions are to be complemented by a consistent approach to derogations or exceptions across legislation, through the definition of criteria for essential uses. These criteria will ensure that *'most harmful chemicals'* (which should at least cover substances of very high concerns (SVHCs)) are only allowed if *'their use is necessary for health, safety or is critical for the functioning of society and if there are no alternatives that are acceptable from the standpoint of environment and health'* (COM(2020) 667 final, p.10). The process for developing these criteria is closely followed by WP2 Alternatives Assessment of ZeroPM. A complete overview of the linkages between initiatives listed in the various Green Deal strategies and the Work Packages of ZeroPM can be found in the appendices B to O.

Actions listed in the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability relate to industrial chemicals, regulated by EU chemicals legislation. As mentioned in section 2, legislation related to biocides and pesticides are also relevant to ZeroPM's work as some biocides and pesticides are also persistent and mobile substances. As previously mentioned, the Farm-to Fork Strategy, the Biodiversity Strategy and the Soil Strategy contain targets to reduce the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% and the use of the most hazardous pesticides by 50% by 2030. *'Most hazardous pesticides'* referred to in the Green Deal strategies include those identified as CMR 1A and 1B, endocrine disruptors, and candidates for substitution when using the definition of Article 24 of Regulation (EU) 1107/2009 (COM(2020) 381 final, p.6). This target is relevant for ZeroPM as it includes a number of triazole fungicides, approved at EU level, as candidates for substitution (containing 1H-1,2,4-Triazole), and of which ZeroPM will focus on (see Table 3).

Substitution of hazardous substances in products

The Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, the Zero Pollution Action Plan and the Circular Economy Action Plan place a strong focus on developing the circular economy through *'toxic free material cycles'* and clean recycling. This is an important driver in the Green Deal strategies for the substitution of hazardous substances in products and their removal in recycled materials. The Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability plans for the development of EU safe and sustainable-by-design criteria for chemicals and materials, which will provide guidance for assessing the safety, sustainability and circularity of products and processes in an integrated way and through their lifecycle, from design stages to end of life and reuse or recycling (COM(2020) 667 final, p.15). The stakeholder consultation process accompanying the development of the criteria started in 2021 and the criteria are expected to be developed in the course of 2022. The safe and sustainable by design criteria are an important driver for substitution and as such are relevant to the work carried out in WP2 Alternatives Assessment and WP4 Market Transition of ZeroPM.

The other relevant initiative announced in the Circular Economy Action Plan is the sustainable product initiative and in particular the proposal for a new Ecodesign for

Sustainable Products Regulation. The recently adopted Commission proposal (COM(2022) 142 final) introduces a possibility for the European Commission to adopt delegated acts establishing ecodesign requirements for one specific or several product groups. Ecodesign requirements can relate to a wide range of product aspects including the durability, reliability, reusability, reparability, energy use, recycled content, and among these aspects to the presence of substances of concern. If adopted, these provisions will allow the European Commission to adopt requirements for restriction of substances present in products or used in their manufacturing processes for reasons other than chemical or food safety (to avoid duplication with existing chemicals and food safety legislation) and requirements on the tracking and communication of sustainability information, including on the presence of substances of concern in products throughout their life cycle. The new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation could also be a driver for the substitution of persistent and mobile substances in products.

Risk assessment

The Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability aims to simplify and harmonise the regulatory framework for the safety assessment of chemicals across legislation, through the implementation of the ‘one substance, one assessment’ (1S1A) initiative. The initiative will introduce more coordinated mechanisms – including a better distribution of chemicals’ risk assessments between agencies, a dedicated expert group, harmonized methodologies, and common data portals (COM(2020) 667 final, p.16). In addition, the ‘one substance, one assessment’ initiative will provide an opportunity to *‘increase and harmonize the consideration of soil quality and biodiversity in EU risk assessments for chemicals, food and feed additives, pesticides, and fertilizers’* (COM(2021) 699 final, p.17), according to the Soil Strategy. The new approach to risk assessment is relevant for work carried out in WP5 Substance Grouping and WP6 Risk Assessment in ZeroPM.

Monitoring

The Zero Pollution Action Plan places a strong focus on monitoring, with the proposal to adopt a Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook Framework, as part of the 8th Environment Action Program (EAP) monitoring. The framework will monitor overall pollution levels and impacts and allow tracking of progress towards achieving the objectives of the Green Deal in Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook Reports from 2024 (COM(2021) 400 final, p.19). According to the Action Plan, the monitoring framework will also *‘help translating ‘early warnings’ into recommendations on pollutants of concern’*. Although not clearly indicated in the Zero Pollution Action Plan, the zero pollution monitoring framework may feed into the early warning system, announced in the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, which will be developed by the Horizon Europe project Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC). ZeroPM WP7 Technical Solutions will collect monitoring data and the move towards the early warning system will support the work carried out in WP5 Substance Grouping.

Remediation of contaminated sites

In comparison to the action points related to prevention, there are relatively few measures related to the remediation of contaminated sites in the reviewed strategies.

This is in line with the toxic free hierarchy and its emphasis. The measures that are contained in the strategies are mainly related to soil decontamination and are outlined in the Soil Strategy and the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. According to the Soil Strategy, the upcoming Soil Health Law will include provisions requiring Member States and the Commission to identify contaminated sites, set up an inventory and register of those sites and remediate the sites that pose a significant risk to human health and the environment by 2050. This will be supported by the development by 2024 of an EU priority list for contaminants of major and/or emerging concern posing significant risks for European soil quality (COM(2021) 699 final, p.19). Other initiatives identified in Green Deal strategies relate to financial support for research and development of decontamination solutions in terrestrial and aquatic environments, in particular to remediate PFAS contamination.

4 Concluding remarks

The work carried out in task 3.1 aimed to set the scene for upcoming work in WP3. In particular, task 3.1 helped to define the scope of WP3 in terms of substances, uses or sectors (completing Milestone 4 of ZeroPM), as well as in terms of policies and legislation to analyse. As part of task 3.2, WP3 will carry out a more detailed analysis of opportunities and gaps in the existing policy and legal framework for preventing PMT/vPvM substances from entering the environment. WP3 will then develop policy options for preventing emissions from PMT/vPvM substances and explore their effectiveness, feasibility and impacts on different actors (task 3.3 and 3.4).

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Appendices A to O: Templates for information gathering on strategic papers

Appendix A: Data gathering template (left blank)

Name(s) of the initiative/policy		Official Title of the policy-document Alternative names/abbreviations COM(XXXX) XXX final (complemented by SWD(XXXX) XXX final and XYZ)		
Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM				
Type of act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal • Others 		
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)			
	Specific Objectives			
				Relevant To ZeroPM:
				Relation to other WPs:
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development			
	Policy-realignment			
	Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation			
	Raising awareness (consumers)			

	Raising awareness (non-consumers)			
	Stakeholder cooperation			
	Financing			
	Other			
Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)				
Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)				
Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)				
Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback				
Challenges				
Proposed timeline				
Links				
Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document				
Links to other ZeroPM-WPs		WP2: WP4: WP5: WP6: WP7: WP8:		
Notes				

* = actions that do not fall exclusively but mostly into its designated category/subcategory

= actions whose categorization might change or for which categorization is still underpinned by uncertainty. Hence, categorization should be handled tentative

Table for further analysis of actions/measures with relevance to ZeroPM:

Actions, Sub-actions and Relevance to ZeroPM		Subcategories:								Prioritize	Remediate
		Research & Development	Policy-realignment	Tightening and re-formation of relevant legislation	Raising awareness (consumers)	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Stakeholder co-operation	Financing	Other		
Actions/Measures for "prevent and reduce" & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	< Action/Measure > <u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u>										
	< Action/Measure > <u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u>										

Used criteria for sub-categorization:

1. Research and Development:

- Data-monitoring
- Generation and collection of scientific knowledge for future assessments and reviews

2. Policy-realignment:

- Evaluation, review and assessment of necessary changes for existing policies
- Setting new targets, goals, roadmaps, strategic papers, etc.
- Integration, unifying, aligning of policies with each other (like an integration of directive X in action plan Y, etc.)

3. Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation:

- Bans
- Efforts of reducing/minimizing/limiting (like limit emission-output of potentially harmful substances)
- Establishment of new requirements, guidelines, etc.

- Improving implementation/enforceability
- 4. Raising Awareness (consumers):**
 - Informing consumers
- 5. Raising Awareness (non-consumers):**
 - Promotion and facilitation of practices, new technologies, etc.
 - Information of stakeholders, agencies, the public and other relevant players
- 6. Stakeholder cooperation:**
 - Cooperation-processes
 - Unifying-attempts at a local, national European-wide and international level
- 7. Financing:**
 - Funding
 - Procurement
- 8. Other:**
 - Actions that do not fit into the other subcategories

Appendix B: Biodiversity Strategy

Name(s) of the initiative/policy		EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030. Bringing nature back into our lives Biodiversity Strategy COM(2020) 380 final
Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM		<p>The Biodiversity Strategy was adopted in May 2020, as a component of the Green Deal. It establishes strong links to the Zero Pollution Action Plan, the Farm-to-Fork Strategy and the Soil Strategy. The overall aim of the Strategy is to put biodiversity on the path to recovery by 2030 and is organised around the following commitments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing a wider EU network of protected areas • Launching an EU nature restoration plan • Taking measures to enable the necessary transformative change (governance framework, enforcement, investments etc.) • Taking measures to tackle the global biodiversity challenge <p>The Strategy is also EU's contribution to the upcoming international negotiations on the global post-2020 biodiversity framework.</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM: The Biodiversity Strategy is strongly linked to the Zero Pollution Action Plan and the Farm to Fork Strategy with regards to the reduction of pesticides and fertilisers' use and the remediation of contaminated soil sites. The Biodiversity Strategy identifies pollution as a key driver of biodiversity loss and indicates that the following pressures must be reduced: the release of nutrients, chemical pesticides, pharmaceuticals, hazardous chemicals, urban and industrial wastewater, and other waste including litter and plastics. It takes an approach that combines prevention (reducing pollution) and remediation (remediating polluted sites and restoring ecosystems).</p>
Type of act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal • Others
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)	The Biodiversity Strategy aims to 'ensure that Europe's biodiversity will be on the path to recovery by 2030, in line with the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and with the objectives of the Paris Agreement on Climate Change'.
	Specific Objectives	<p>Improving and widening our network of protected areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legally protect a minimum of 30% of the EU's land area and 30% of the EU's sea area and integrate ecological corridors, as part of a true Trans-European Nature Network. • Strictly protect at least a third of the EU's protected areas, including all remaining EU primary and old-growth forests. • Effectively manage all protected areas, defining clear conservation objectives and measures, and monitoring them appropriately. <p>Developing an ambitious EU Nature Restoration Plan:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening the EU legal framework for nature restoration. Legally binding EU nature restoration targets to be proposed in 2021, subject to an impact assessment. Targets: 'by 2030, significant areas of degraded and carbon-rich ecosystems are restored'; 'habitats and species show no deterioration in conservation trends and status'; and 'at least 30% reach favourable conservation status or at least show a positive trend'.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support and incentivise the transition to fully sustainable agricultural practices. Targets: ‘the decline in pollinators is reversed’; ‘the risk and use of chemical pesticides is reduced by 50% and the use of more hazardous pesticides is reduced by 50%’; ‘at least 10% of agricultural area is under high-diversity landscape features’; ‘at least 25% of agricultural land is under organic farming management, and the uptake of agro-ecological practices is significantly increased’. • Addressing land take and restoring soil ecosystems. Targets from the Soil Strategy and the ZPAP. • Increasing the quantity of forests and improving their health and resilience. Target: ‘three billion new trees are planted in the EU, in full respect of ecological principles’. • Promote sustainable bioenergy • Restoring the good environmental status of marine ecosystems. Targets: ‘the negative impacts on sensitive species and habitats, including on the seabed through fishing and extraction activities, are substantially reduced to achieve good environmental status’; ‘the by-catch of species is eliminated or reduced to a level that allows species recovery and conservation’. • Restoring freshwater ecosystems. Target: ‘at least 25,000 km of free-flowing rivers are restored’. • Greening urban and peri-urban areas. Targets: ‘cities with at least 20,000 inhabitants have an ambitious Urban Greening Plan’ and ‘no chemical pesticides are used in sensitive areas such as EU urban green areas’. • Reducing pollution. Targets: ‘the losses of nutrients from fertilisers are reduced by 50%, resulting in the reduction of the use of fertilisers by at least 20%’ and ‘significant progress has been made in the remediation of contaminated soil sites’ • Addressing invasive alien species. Target: there is a 50% reduction in the number of Red List species threatened by invasive alien species. <p>Introducing measures to enable the necessary transformative change</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stepping up implementation and enforcement of EU environmental legislation • Developing an integrated and whole-of-society approach through business partnerships, strengthening the biodiversity proofing framework, the ‘user pays’ and ‘polluter pays’ principles, green public procurement, supporting the establishment of an international natural capital accounting initiative, developing knowledge, education and skills. <p>Raising the level of ambition and commitment worldwide and promote EU ambitions through external action:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agree an ambitious new global framework for post-2020 at the 15th Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity, including global goals for biodiversity for 2050, and global 2030 targets in line with EU commitments in the Biodiversity Strategy. • Support an ambitious legally binding agreement on marine biological diversity of areas beyond national jurisdiction (BBNJ) by the end of 2020. • Support EU biodiversity ambitions through trade policy, international cooperation and neighbourhood policy. <p><u>Relevance to Zero PM</u> The Biodiversity Strategy is strongly linked to the Zero Pollution Action Plan and the Farm to Fork Strategy with regards to the reduction of pesticides and fertilisers’ use and the remediation of contaminated soil sites. The Biodiversity Strategy identifies pollution as a key driver of biodiversity loss and indicates that the following pressures must be reduced: the ‘release of nutrients, chemical pesticides, pharmaceuticals, hazardous chemicals, urban and industrial wastewater, and other waste including litter and plastics’.</p>		
<p><i>(Only actions with a link to pollution reduction have been included below)</i></p>		<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1731 1187 1832 1279"> Relevant To ZeroPM: </td> <td data-bbox="1832 1187 1921 1279"> Relation to other WPs: </td> </tr> </table>	Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:			

Actions/Measures for "prevent and reduce" & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development	Develop a set of indicators for the progressive reduction of pollution and establish baselines to help monitor progress.	X	WP7
	Policy-realignment	Review and possible revision of the EU Pollinators initiative by 2020		
		Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan by 2022	X	WP7
		Review and possible revision of the Environmental Crime Directive by 2021		
	Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation	Proposal for EU nature restoration targets by 2021		
		Revision of the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive and enhance Integrated Pest Management provisions by 2022	X	WP7
		Measures to ensure that Member States' CAP Strategic Plans set explicit national values for relevant targets of the Biodiversity and Farm to Fork Strategies, supported, inter alia, by CAP instruments and implementation of the Habitats Directive		
		Delegated act under the Taxonomy Regulation to establish a common classification of economic activities that substantially contribute to the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems by 2021		
	Raising awareness (consumers / citizens)	N/A		
	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	N/A		
Stakeholder cooperation	N/A			
Financing	N/A			
Other	N/A			
Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback	N/A			
Challenges	No challenges related to pollution reduction are clearly outlined in the Strategy.			
Proposed timeline	Strategy adopted in 2020 with targets Planned review : not stated in Strategy.			
Links	https://ec.europa.eu/environment/strategy/biodiversity-strategy-2030_en			
Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document	Common Agricultural Policy Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive			
Links to other ZeroPM-WPs	WP7			

Notes	The biodiversity Strategy is strongly related to the Soil Strategy and the Farm to Fork Strategy with regards to soil contamination and agricultural practices. The development of the Nutrient Management Action Plan may be of interest.
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Table for further analysis of actions/measures with relevance to ZeroPM:

Actions, Sub-actions and Relevance to ZeroPM		Subcategories:							Prioritize	Remediate
		Research & Development	Policy-realignment	Tightening and re-formation of relevant legislation	Raising awareness (consumers)	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Stakeholder co-operation	Financing		
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Develop a set of indicators for the progressive reduction of pollution and establish baselines to help monitor progress. <u>Relevance for ZeroPM:</u> linked to Zero Pollution Action Plan. This could be relevant in particular in relation to pesticides (the 50% reduction target will be monitored).	X	X							
	Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan by 2022 <u>Relevance for ZeroPM:</u> The integrated nutrient management action plan will identify policy gaps for a more coherent and integrated approach to reducing pollution throughout the nutrient cycles. It will cover all environmental media (air, water, marine and soil) and all relevant sources of pollution (e.g. agriculture, industry, urban, waste, energy, transport). It will develop a framework for action needed at all levels (EU, national, regional) to achieve the targets of the biodiversity and farm to fork strategies to reduce nutrient losses by at least 50%. Limited relevance for ZeroPM: mainly linked to use of biosolids in agriculture, and possible chemicals contamination that could prevent their use. Biosolids can be contaminated with PMT/vPvM substances from wastewater.		X							
	Revision of the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive and enhance Integrated Pest Management provisions by 2022 <u>Relevance for ZeroPM;</u> the revision of the SUPD should contribute to the 50% reduction target for pesticide use. The revision should aim to reduce the use and risk of pesticides containing more hazardous active substances; increase the uptake of less hazardous and non-chemical alternatives for pest control.				X					

Appendix C: Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability

Name(s) of the initiative/policy		Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. Towards a Toxic-Free Environment Chemicals Strategy COM(2020) 667 final (complemented by SWD(2020) 225 final; SWD(2020) 247 final; SWD(2020) 248 final; SWD(2020) 249 final; SWD(2020) 250 final; SWD(2020) 251 final)
Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM		<p>The Chemicals Strategy was adopted in October 2020 as part of the Green Deal’s zero pollution ambition. The Strategy sets an overall ambition to reach a toxic free environment by 2030. The Strategy is complementary to the CEAP, as it places strong focus on clean material cycles, to the Industrial Strategy, as it strongly emphasises innovation and moving towards a green and digital industrial transition. It also establishes links with the Pharmaceutical Strategy.</p> <p>The Chemicals Strategy is organised around five building blocks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation for safe and sustainable EU chemicals • Stronger EU legal framework to address pressing environmental and health concerns • Simplification and consolidation of the legal framework • Knowledge base on chemicals and science policy interface • Action at international level <p>The implementation of the Strategy is being monitored by the Commission and is presented in an online tracking table.</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM</p> <p>The Chemicals Strategy is based on the ‘toxic-free hierarchy’, modelled on the ‘zero pollution hierarchy’ (prevent, minimise and control, and eliminate and remediate) a defines EU actions corresponding to the three stages of the hierarchy. ZeroPM is firmly rooted in this strategy. All work is aligned to support it</p>
Type of act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal • Others
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)	The Chemicals Strategy aims to achieve by 2030 ‘a toxic-free environment, where chemicals are produced and used in a way that maximises their contribution to society including achieving the green and digital transition, while avoiding harm to the planet and to current and future generations’ and to make the EU industry ‘globally competitive player in the production and use of safe and sustainable chemicals’. The two pillars of the Strategy are the protection of health and the environment and encouraging innovation.
	Specific Objectives	<p><i>Encouraging innovation for the production of safe and sustainable chemicals</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shift to a safe and sustainable-by-design approach, promote the development of safe and sustainable chemicals and materials, • Support industrial innovation, climate neutral and clean production processes and technologies • Achieve non-toxic material cycles to ensure secondary materials and products are safe and support waste decontamination solutions <p><i>Addressing environmental and health concerns</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen the legal framework to protect consumers, vulnerable groups and workers from the most harmful chemicals

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce chemicals emissions into the environment • Make substance assessment processes simpler and more transparent through the ‘one substance, one assessment’ principle • Improve the availability of chemical data, the knowledge base on properties and uses and promote innovative testing and risk assessment methods • Facilitate sharing, reuse and interoperability of chemical data • Improve enforcement of EU chemicals legislation, compliance and market surveillance • Strengthen international standards • Promote safety and sustainability standards outside the EU 		
			Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development	Develop methodologies for chemical risk assessment that take into account the whole life cycle of substances, materials and products	X	WP6
		Support initiatives and funding in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and development in advanced materials for applications in the energy, construction, mobility, health, agriculture and electronics sectors to deliver the green and digital transition. • Research, development and deployment of low-carbon and low environmental impact chemical and material production processes. • Research and development of innovative business models such as performance-based business model to ensure a more efficient use of chemicals and other resources and the minimization of wastes and emissions. • Re-skilling and up-skilling the workforce involved in the production and use of chemicals towards the green and digital transition. • Development and deployment of infrastructure allowing to switch to the use, transport and storage of electricity from renewable / carbon-neutral energy sources for the production of chemicals. • Increase the current deployment rate of available technologies for manufacturing purposes such as internet of things, big data, artificial intelligence, automation, smart sensors and robotics. 		
		Accelerate the development and uptake of methods to generate information on endocrine disruptors through screening and testing of substance		
		Improve the assessments of the mixtures used in the manufacture of tobacco and related products by using where possible existing EU agencies		
		Establishment of an open platform on chemical safety data and tools for accessing relevant academic data	X	WP5
		Establishment of a EU repository of human and environmental health-based limit values		
		Explore the use of digital tools to support market surveillance and customs authorities as well as to improve the compliance of products containing chemicals sold online to European consumers		
		Establish and update a research and innovation agenda for chemicals, driven by a EU-level Coordination Group, that would also promote the regulatory uptake of research findings	X	All
		Foster multidisciplinary research and digital innovations for advanced tools, methods and models, and data analysis capacities to also move away from animal testing	X	WP6

		Establish an EU Chemical Early Warning and Action System	X	WP5
		Promote the development of common standards and innovative risk assessment tools internationally, notably with the OECD, and promote their use under international frameworks, inter alia to shift further away from animal testing	X	WP6
	Policy-realignment	Mapping safe and sustainable-by-design skills mismatches and competence gaps, and make recommendations	X	WP2
		Develop EU safe and sustainable-by-design criteria for chemicals	X	WP2 WP4
		Establish Key Performance Indicators to measure the industrial transition towards the production of safe and sustainable chemicals	X	WP2 WP4
		Roadmap to prioritise carcinogenic, mutagenic and reprotoxic substances (CMRs), endocrine disruptors, persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT and very persistent and very bioaccumulative (vPvB) substances, immunotoxicants, neurotoxicants, substances toxic to specific organs and respiratory sensitisers for (group) restrictions under REACH	X	WP2 WP4
		Define criteria for essential uses, taking into account the definition of the Montreal Protocol, to ensure that the most harmful chemicals are only allowed if their use is necessary for health, safety or is critical for the functioning of society and if there are no alternatives that are acceptable from the standpoint of environment and health. These criteria will guide the application of essential uses in all relevant EU legislation for both generic and specific risk assessments	X	WP2 WP4
		Address the impact on the environment of the production and use of pharmaceuticals in the upcoming pharmaceuticals strategy for Europe		
		Establishment of a 'One substance, one assessment' process to coordinate the hazard/risk assessment on chemicals across chemical legislation, through the use of a single Public Authorities Coordination Tool, an expert group and a Commission coordination mechanism	X	WP6
		Horizontal proposal for reallocation of EU technical and scientific work on chemicals to the EU agencies (including work of the SCHEER and SCCS)		
		Develop a framework of indicators to monitor the drivers and impacts of chemical pollution and to measure the effectiveness of chemicals legislation		
	Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation	Make amendments to the EU legislation on industrial emissions to promote the use of safer chemicals by EU industry (revision of the IED)	X	WP7
		Introduce legal requirements to minimise the presence of substances of concern in products, including PFAS, through the initiative on sustainable products, giving priority to those product categories that affect vulnerable populations as well as those with the highest potential for circularity, such as textiles, packaging including food packaging, furniture, electronics and ICT, construction and buildings	X	WP2 WP4
		Ensure availability of information on chemical content and safe use, by introducing information requirements in the context of the Sustainable Product Policy Initiative and tracking the presence of substances of concern through the life cycle of materials and products	X	WP2 WP4
Ensure that authorisations and derogations from restrictions for recycled materials under REACH are exceptional and justified				
Proposals to extend the generic approach to risk management to ensure that consumer products (including, among other things, food contact materials, toys, childcare articles, cosmetics, detergents, furniture and textiles) do not contain chemicals that cause cancers, gene mutations, affect the reproductive or the endocrine system, or are persistent and bioaccumulative and toxic; assess through an impact assessment the modalities and timing to extend the same approach to further chemicals including those		X	WP2 WP4	

	affecting the immune, neurological or respiratory systems and chemicals toxic to a specific organ		
	Introduce mandatory legal requirements under the General Product Safety Directive and restrictions in REACH to enhance the safety of children from hazardous chemicals in childcare articles and other products for children (other than toys)	X	WP2 WP4
	Proposal to amend REACH Article 68(2) to include professional users		
	In the process of the upcoming Strategic Framework for Health and Safety at work, define further priorities for addressing workers' exposure to hazardous substances, including by identifying most harmful substances for which the Commission will propose to set occupational limit following the established consultation process in the area of health and safety at work		
	In consultation with social partners, strengthen protection of workers, notably by proposing lowering existing occupational limit values for lead and asbestos as well as establishing a binding limit value for di-isocyanates		
	Propose to establish legally binding hazard identification of endocrine disruptors, based on the definition of the WHO, building on criteria already developed for pesticides and biocides, and apply it across all legislation		
	Ensure that endocrine disruptors are banned in consumer products as soon as they are identified, allowing their use only where it is proven to be essential for society;		
	Strengthen workers' protection by introducing endocrine disruptors as a category of substances of very high concern under REACH		
	Ensure that sufficient and appropriate information is made available to authorities to allow the identification of endocrine disruptors by reviewing and strengthening information requirements across legislation		
	Assess how best and introduce (a) mixture assessment factor(s) in Annex I of REACH	X	WP6
	Introduce or reinforce provisions to take account of the combination effects of chemicals in water, food contact materials, food additives, toys, detergents, cosmetics	X	WP6 WP7
	Proposal to amend the CLP Regulation to introduce new hazard classes on endocrine disruptors, PBTs/vPvBs and persistent and mobile substances, and apply them across all legislation	X	All
	Proposal to amend REACH Article 57 to add endocrine disruptors, persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) and very persistent and very mobile (vPvM) substances to the list of substances of very high concern	X	All
	Ensure that the information made available to authorities on substances allows comprehensive environmental risk assessments by strengthening requirements across legislation	X	WP6
	Reinforce the regulation of chemical contaminants in food to ensure a high level of human health protection		
	Proposal to restrict PFAS as a group under REACH for all non-essential uses including in consumer products	X	WP2 WP4 WP5

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	<p>Address PFAS with a group approach, under relevant legislation on water, sustainable products, food, industrial emissions, and waste:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review of the annexes of the Environmental Quality Standards Directive and of the Groundwater Directive to add PFAS where possible as a group Address the presence of PFAS in food by introducing limits in the legislation on food contaminants Proposal to revise the legislation on industrial emissions and the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register to address emissions and reporting of PFAS from industrial plants Proposal to address the emissions of PFAS from the waste stage including through the revision of the legislation on sewage sludge 	X	WP5 WP6 WP7
	Proposals under the Stockholm Convention and the Basel Convention to address PFAS concerns at a global scale	X	WP2 WP4 WP5
	Make a proposal to strengthen the governance of the European Chemicals Agency and increase the sustainability of its financing model (founding regulation)		
	Proposal to revise the REACH authorisation and restriction processes	X	WP2 WP6
	Proposal to amend CLP Regulation to give the Commission the mandate to initiate harmonised classification		
	Review the definition of nanomaterial and ensure its coherent application across legislation using legally binding mechanisms		
	Horizontal proposal to remove legislative obstacles for re-use of data, to streamline the data flow across legislation and to extend the open data and transparency principles from the EU food safety sector to other pieces of chemical legislation		
	Proposals to allow EU and national authorities to commission testing and monitoring of substances as part of the regulatory framework	X	WP7
	Amend REACH to ensure compliance checks on all registrations of substances under REACH and to allow for the revocation of registration numbers		
	Proposal to amend REACH to introduce a European Audit Capacity		
	Proposal to extend OLAF's scope of action to investigations on the circulation of illicit chemical products in the EU		
	Proposals for implementing acts under the Market Surveillance Regulation to set uniform conditions and frequency of checks for certain products		
	Proposals to revise requirements for registration in REACH to ensure: the identification of substances with critical hazard properties, including effects on the nervous and immune systems, the move towards grouping approaches, the registration of a sub-set of polymers, information on the overall environmental footprint of chemicals, the obligation of chemical safety reports for substances between 1-10 tonnes	X	WP5 WP6
	Strive for the adoption of global strategic objectives and targets for the sound management of chemicals and waste beyond 2020 to reflect life cycle approaches for chemicals, in line with the post-2020 global biodiversity targets		
	Proposal at the UN GHS level to introduce, adapt or clarify criteria/hazard classes in line with the CLP Regulation		

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		Ensure that hazardous chemicals banned in the European Union are not produced for export including by amending relevant legislation if and as needed		
	Raising awareness (consumers)			
	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Step up EU's international advocacy to meet the 2030 Agenda's goals and targets for the sound management of chemicals, in particular by having a leading role and promoting the implementation of existing international instruments as well as EU standards globally		
		Initiatives with international organisations and industry to promote the use of the UN GHS internationally	X	WP4
		Promote the sound management of chemicals through international cooperation and partnerships, in bilateral, regional and multilateral fora, including through cooperation with Africa, as well as cooperation with neighbours and other partners to support their capacity to assess and manage chemicals in a sound manner		
		Promote due diligence in the sustainable production and use of chemicals in the future initiative on sustainable corporate governance		
	Stakeholder cooperation	Set up a high level roundtable with the purpose of promoting efficiency and effectiveness of chemicals legislation, boosting development and uptake of innovative safe and sustainable chemicals, and monitoring the impact of the Strategy's actions.	X	WP2 WP4
		Establish an EU-wide safe and sustainable-by design support network	X	WP2 WP4
		Identify key value chains and dependencies where chemicals are important building blocks and engage with stakeholders to increase the EU's strategic foresight on chemicals	X	WP4
		Promote interregional collaboration along sustainable chemicals value chains, through smart specialisation, to accelerate the development of joint investment projects	X	WP4
		Ensure a harmonised EU-wide response and coordinated exchange of information on enforcement of chemical legislation, by strengthening the use of relevant Commission IT platforms		
	Financing	Financial support for the development, commercialisation, deployment and uptake of safe and sustainable-by-design substances, materials and products	X	WP4
		Support investments in sustainable innovations that can decontaminate waste streams, increase safe recycling and reduce the export of waste, in particular plastics and textiles		
		Access to risk finance, in particular for SMEs and start-ups		
		Promote the EU's resilience of supply and sustainability of chemicals used in essential applications for society through EU funding and investment mechanisms.		
		Provide research and innovation funding for safe innovations to substitute PFAS under Horizon Europe	X	WP2 WP4
		Encourage the Member States to use the Recovery and Resilience Facility to invest in the reinforcement of market surveillance infrastructures and digitalisation		
		Fund EU-wide human and environmental (bio)monitoring		
	Support, in particular through funding, to build the capacity of third countries to assess and manage chemicals			
	Other			

Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Roadmap to prioritise carcinogenic, mutagenic and reprotoxic substances (CMRs), endocrine disruptors, persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT and very persistent and very bioaccumulative (vPvB) substances, immunotoxicants, neurotoxicants, substances toxic to specific organs and respiratory sensitisers for (group) restrictions under REACH	X	WP2 WP4
	Define criteria for essential uses, taking into account the definition of the Montreal Protocol, to ensure that the most harmful chemicals are only allowed if their use is necessary for health, safety or is critical for the functioning of society and if there are no alternatives that are acceptable from the standpoint of environment and health. These criteria will guide the application of essential uses in all relevant EU legislation for both generic and specific risk assessments	X	WP2 WP4
	Proposal to amend REACH Article 57 to add endocrine disruptors, persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) and very persistent and very mobile (vPvM) substances to the list of substances of very high concern	X	All
Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Support research and development for decontamination solutions in terrestrial and aquatic environments	X	WP7
	EU-wide approach and financial support for innovative solutions to remediate contamination with PFAS	X	WP7
Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A		
Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback	<p>Feedback to the Roadmap:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public authorities: necessity to speed up the phasing out of substances of concern, including groups of substances, by introducing restrictions that would only exempt essential uses. Public authorities in particular backed an EU action plan for addressing PFAS, for which only essential uses should be allowed. Broad majority of stakeholders from all groups supported action on chemicals affecting the environment, in particular regarding PFAS. However different groups of stakeholders showed different views regarding the scope of the actions and the need for grouping approaches. Most public authorities backed the introduction of new hazard classes to the SVHC definition, including persistent and mobile substances. NGOs supported regulating very persistent chemicals, including but not limited to PFAS, in all relevant chemical legislation. They backed a ban of all non-essential uses of persistent chemicals and chemicals that accumulate in the environment and the phase out all chemicals that are persistent, mobile and toxic. Academia also stated that highly persistent organic chemicals, in particular when also bioaccumulative or mobile, must be limited as much as possible. This group backed restricting uses of PFAS to essential uses. Businesses emphasised that persistent chemicals should be regulated if a risk is identified. Many stated that potential mobility is not suitable to inform on exposure. 		
Challenges	N/A		
Proposed timeline	The Strategy adopted in 2020 does not set a timeline for revision.		
Links	https://ec.europa.eu/environment/strategy/chemicals-strategy_en		
Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document	REACH CLP Cosmetics Regulation Toys Safety Directive Detergents Regulation General Product Safety Directive Environmental Quality Standards Directive Groundwater Directive		

	<p>Sewage sludge Directive Waste legislation Industrial Emissions Directive European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register Health and Safety at work legislation Food contact materials Regulation Food additives Regulation UN GHS Stockholm Convention Basel Convention</p>
<p>Links to other ZeroPM-WPs</p>	<p>All Work packages: the Chemicals Strategy plans to introduce a new hazard class in the CLP Regulation on PMTs and to amend REACH Article 57 to add PMTs to the list of SVHCs.</p> <p>WP2: The Chemicals Strategy places a strong focus on the transition to a safe and sustainable-by-design approach and aims to develop EU safe and sustainable-by-design criteria for chemicals. In terms of risk management, the Strategy aims to make the generic approach the default approach for most harmful chemicals, in particular for consumer products, while still allowing for the uses that are proven essential for society. To implement that, the Commission has launched an initiative to define criteria for essential uses. It aims to apply this approach to PFAS, banning them as group, allowing their use only where they are essential for society. This is ongoing through restriction processes under REACH.</p> <p>WP4: The generalisation of the generic approach to most harmful chemicals and the restriction roadmap aim to accelerate market transition to safer chemicals. The definition of EU safe and sustainable-by-design criteria for chemicals and essential use criteria are relevant for the work package. In addition, the Strategy refers to instruments to support market transition such as funding for the development of safe and sustainable-by-design substances, materials and products, and innovations to substitute PFAS under Horizon Europe.</p> <p>WP5: The Chemicals Strategy supports gradually moving away from assessing and regulating chemicals substance-by-substance to regulating them by groups, in particular through the generalisation of the generic approach and the revision of registration data requirements. It will also be supported by the 'one substance, one assessment' initiative. In particular it includes measures to regulate PFAS as a group under relevant legislation on water, sustainable products, food, industrial emissions, and waste. The revision of the registration data requirements in the ongoing REACH revision is important as it should introduce tighter requirements allowing the identification of substances with critical hazard properties and requirements for a sub-set of polymers (currently not covered by REACH). The Strategy also plans for the creation of an early warning system and the establishment of an open platform on chemical safety data and tools for accessing relevant academic data, to which ZeroPM could contribute.</p> <p>WP6: The Chemicals Strategy aims to promote research and innovation in chemical risk assessment to reduce dependency on animal testing, improve the quality, efficiency and speed of chemical hazard and risk assessments, take into account the whole life cycle of substances, materials and products, and take better account of the effect of chemical mixtures. The Strategy also aims to simplify the regulatory framework for hazard and risk assessment and management of chemicals, through the 'one substance, one assessment'. This will include synchronising hazard identification/classification and risk assessment across chemicals legislation.</p> <p>WP7: The Strategy aims to address PFAS with a group approach under relevant environmental legislation on water, industrial emissions, and waste through the revisions of IED, EPRT-R, GWD and EQSD, and sewage sludge directive. It also aims to develop an EU wide approach as well as funding for remediating contamination from PFAS. It lists as an objective to address the combination effects of chemicals in water.</p>
<p>Notes</p>	

Table for further analysis of actions/measures with relevance to ZeroPM:

Actions, Sub-actions and Relevance to ZeroPM		Subcategories:							Prioritize	Remediate	
		Research & Development	Policy-realignment	Tightening and re-formation of relevant legislation	Raising awareness (consumers)	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Stakeholder co-operation	Financing			Other
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Develop methodologies for chemical risk assessment that take into account the whole life cycle of substances, materials and products (2022) <u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Linked to the Strategic Research and Innovation Plan for Chemicals and Materials mentioned below. Possibility for ZeroPM to contribute to its implementation.	X									
	Establishment of an open platform on chemical safety data and tools for accessing relevant academic data (2023) <u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Possibility for ZeroPM to contribute to these platforms and tools.	X									
	Establish and update a research and innovation agenda for chemicals, driven by a EU-level Coordination Group, that would also promote the regulatory uptake of research findings (2022) The Strategic Research and Innovation Plan for Chemicals and Materials addressing research and innovation needs across the lifecycle of chemicals and materials is still mentioned as upcoming on the Commission’s website . <u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Possibility for ZeroPM to contribute to the implementation of this research agenda.	X					X				
	Foster multidisciplinary research and digital innovations for advanced tools, methods and models, and data analysis capacities to also move away from animal testing <u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Possibility for ZeroPM to contribute through WP6.	X									
	Establish an EU Chemical Early Warning and Action System <u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Relevance for WP7 regarding monitoring of emerging	X					X				

	<p>substances in water and WP5 who will look at feeding an early warning system. The development of the early warning system will be done by the Horizon Europe project Partnership for the assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC).</p>									
	<p>Promote the development of common standards and innovative risk assessment tools internationally, notably with the OECD, and promote their use under international frameworks, inter alia to shift further away from animal testing.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Possibility for ZeroPM to contribute through WP6 where NAMs are being used.</p>	X	X							
	<p>Develop EU safe and sustainable-by-design criteria for chemicals (by 2022)</p> <p>Action being implemented in part through Horizon Europe call (HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-08); preliminary studies carried out by Commission. Stakeholder workshops held by DG RTD in 2021 and 2022 to discuss concept and first developments.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Relevance for WP 2 and 4 as criteria should foster the uptake of safer alternatives and market transition.</p>		X			X				
	<p>Establish Key Performance Indicators to measure the industrial transition towards the production of safe and sustainable chemicals. Action marked for 2021 – no update / action found.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> May be of interest for WP4 via dialogue ongoing.</p>		X							
	<p>Roadmap to prioritise carcinogenic, mutagenic and reprotoxic substances (CMRs), endocrine disruptors, persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT and very persistent and very bioaccumulative (vPvB) substances, immunotoxicants, neurotoxicants, substances toxic to specific organs and respiratory sensitisers for (group) restrictions under REACH (2021)</p> <p>Roadmap published on 25 April 2022.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> the Rolling List contains all substances that are in the pipeline for restriction procedure (those already listed in the Registry of Intention, those that are planned and for which preparatory work has started and those that are being discussed as potential risk management option).</p>		X					X		
	<p>Define criteria for essential uses, taking into account the definition of the Montreal</p>		X							

	<p>Protocol, to ensure that the most harmful chemicals are only allowed if their use is necessary for health, safety or is critical for the functioning of society and if there are no alternatives that are acceptable from the standpoint of environment and health. These criteria will guide the application of essential uses in all relevant EU legislation for both generic and specific risk assessments (2021-2022)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Relevance for WP 2 and 4 working on essential uses and with chemical manufacturers and end users.</p>									
	<p>Establishment of a ‘One substance, one assessment’ process to coordinate the hazard/risk assessment on chemicals across chemical legislation, through the use of a single Public Authorities Coordination Tool, an expert group and a Commission coordination mechanism.</p> <p>Will be implemented through three legal proposals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The reattribution of tasks on chemicals to EU Agencies (2022), • Transparency and reuse of data allowing EU and national authorities to commission testing (2023), and • ECHA’s founding regulation (2023), to improve the predictability and stability of ECHA’s financing <p>And through the the development of a common open data portal on chemicals (2023) and a repository of health-based limit values (2022).</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> will consolidate risk assessment procedures across chemicals legislation and support group assessments, so aligned with WP5 and WP6.</p>		X							
	<p>Make amendments to the EU legislation on industrial emissions to promote the use of safer chemicals by EU industry (revision of the IED).</p> <p>Revision ongoing. COM Proposal for a Directive adopted in April 2022.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> The proposal intends to clarify the rules that apply to the indirect release of polluting substances into water through urban wastewater treatment plants, including PFAS, microplastics and pharmaceuticals. The review of the BREF should take into account the identification of substances of concern under EU water legislation (ground and surface water watchlists, and other substances posing a significant risk to or via the aquatic environment).</p>			X						
	<p>Introduce legal requirements to minimise the presence of substances of concern in products, including PFAS, through the initiative on sustainable products, giving priority to those product categories that affect vulnerable populations as well as</p>			X						

	<p>those with the highest potential for circularity, such as textiles, packaging including food packaging, furniture, electronics and ICT, construction and buildings</p> <p>Revision ongoing. COM Proposal for a Directive adopted in April 2022.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM</u>: as ZeroPM aims to reduce PFAS use in consumer products.</p>									
	<p>Ensure availability of information on chemical content and safe use, by introducing information requirements in the context of the Sustainable Product Policy Initiative and tracking the presence of substances of concern through the life cycle of materials and products</p> <p>Revision ongoing. COM Proposal for a Directive adopted in April 2022.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM</u>: improved tracing of PFAS in products, waste and recycled materials.</p>			X						
	<p>Proposals to extend the generic approach to risk management to ensure that consumer products (including, among other things, food contact materials, toys, childcare articles, cosmetics, detergents, furniture and textiles) do not contain chemicals that cause cancers, gene mutations, affect the reproductive or the endocrine system, or are persistent and bioaccumulative and toxic; assess through an impact assessment the modalities and timing to extend the same approach to further chemicals including those affecting the immune, neurological or respiratory systems and chemicals toxic to a specific organ (2022)</p> <p>Action implemented through the revisions of REACH, Cosmetics Regulation, Toy Safety Directive, Food Contact Materials Regulation, and other such as Detergents Regulation.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM</u>: the extension of the generic approach contributes to moving towards regulating substances by group. It is also linked to the concept of essential uses. The Strategy indicates the possibility to extend the generic approach beyond CMRs and PBTs – potentially to PMTs/vPvM.</p>			X						
	<p>Introduce mandatory legal requirements under the General Product Safety Directive and restrictions in REACH to enhance the safety of children from hazardous chemicals in childcare articles and other products for children (other than toys)</p> <p>General Product Safety Directive: 2021; REACH (Comitology) 2022.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM</u>: May cover PMT/vPvM substances such as PFAS.</p>			X						

Assess how best and introduce (a) mixture assessment factor(s) in Annex I of REACH (2022) <u>Relevance to ZeroPM</u> : integration of chemical mixtures assessment into risk assessment – relevance for WP6.			X							
Introduce or reinforce provisions to take account of the combination effects of chemicals in water, food contact materials, food additives, toys, detergents, cosmetics (2022) <u>Relevance to ZeroPM</u> : integration of combined effects – relevant for WP6.			X							
Proposal to amend the CLP Regulation to introduce new hazard classes on endocrine disruptors, PBTs/vPvBs and persistent and mobile substances, and apply them across all legislation (2022) <u>Relevance to ZeroPM</u> : Introduction of PMT hazard class in CLP			X							
Proposal to amend REACH Article 57 to add endocrine disruptors, persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) and very persistent and very mobile (vPvM) substances to the list of substances of very high concern (2022) <u>Relevance to ZeroPM</u> : Listing of PMT in SVHC criteria.			X						X	
Ensure that the information made available to authorities on substances allows comprehensive environmental risk assessments by strengthening requirements across legislation <u>Relevance to ZeroPM</u> : strengthening information requirements across legislation for risk assessment – relevance for WP6.			X							
Proposal to restrict PFAS as a group under REACH for all non-essential uses including in consumer products. Restriction dossier expected in January 2023. <u>Relevance to ZeroPM</u> : application of group approach to regulating PFAS; reduction of PFAS use in consumer products.			X							
Address PFAS with a group approach, under relevant legislation on water, sustainable products, food, industrial emissions, and waste: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review of the annexes of the Environmental Quality Standards Directive and of the Groundwater Directive to add PFAS where possible as a group (2022) Address the presence of PFAS in food by introducing limits in the 			X							

	<p>legislation on food contaminants (2022)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proposal to revise the legislation on industrial emissions and the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register to address emissions and reporting of PFAS from industrial plants (2022) Proposal to address the emissions of PFAS from the waste stage including through the revision of the legislation on sewage sludge (2023) <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> application of group approach to regulating PFAS; addressing PFAS environmental pollution – relevance for WP7.</p>											
	<p>Proposals under the Stockholm Convention and the Basel Convention to address PFAS concerns at a global scale</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> reduction of PFAS use at a global scale</p>			X								
	<p>Proposals to revise requirements for registration in REACH to ensure: the identification of substances with critical hazard properties, including effects on the nervous and immune systems, the move towards grouping approaches, the registration of a sub-set of polymers, information on the overall environmental footprint of chemicals, the obligation of chemical safety reports for substances between 1-10 tonnes (2022)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> better identification of substances with critical hazard properties; facilitate grouping approaches; collection of registration data for polymers.</p>			X								
	<p>Establish an EU-wide safe and sustainable-by design support network</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> possibility for Zero PM to participate.</p>					X	X					
	<p>Financial support for the development, commercialisation, deployment and uptake of safe and sustainable-by-design substances, materials and products</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> support for industrial alternatives – relevance for WP4</p>	X						X				
	<p>Provide research and innovation funding for safe innovations to substitute PFAS under Horizon Europe</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> links between WP2 / WP4 with other Horizon Europe projects.</p>	X						X				

Appendix D: Circular Economy Action Plan

Name(s) of the initiative/policy		A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe Circular Economy Action Plan COM(2020) 98 final
Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM		<p>The (new) Circular Economy Action Plan describes an EU-initiative under the European Green Deal that presents an agenda to push onwards ambitions of creating and refining a functioning circular economy model for a “<i>cleaner and more competitive Europe</i>”. The plan tries to streamline the EU regulatory framework in coherence with other Green Deal initiatives like e.g. the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, Farm to Fork or Renovation Wave. For achieving this, all relevant actors at all levels (from local to international) like industrial organizations, consumers and citizens will be addressed. Regarding the content of the action plan, products and services, business models and consumption patterns in terms of waste generation, product value chains, the development of a secondary material market as well as new (digital) technologies and circularity in general (like recycling, reusability or reparability) are being tackled with emphasis on key sectors like plastics, textiles, electronics and more.</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM: Relevance for ZeroPM is related to concerning chemicals in the process of building circularity and in the selection of key sectors that often entail persistent and mobile substances.</p>
Type of act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal • Others
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)	<p>The main objective of the Circular Economy Action Plan is – as its name suggests – to develop further, refine and strengthen the concept and implementation of a circular and therefore sustainable economy.</p> <p>This includes the idea of a transition that decouples economic growth from resource use and that ensures the long-term competitiveness of the EU. Also, leaving no one behind, which means a socioeconomically fair change and to further along climate neutrality is intended. Along these lines the action plan means to give the planet back more than what is taken.</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM: The Circular Economy Action Plan relates in numerous ways to the ZeroPM-project. It refers on multiple occasions to the presence of substances of concern or hazardous chemicals in products and aims to address them accordingly. This holds true especially for substances, that persist through the channels of circularity and contaminate recycled raw secondary materials. The action plan puts emphasis to relevant sectors that are often of interest for ZeroPM like electronics, ICT, textiles, furniture, intermediary products, plastics and chemicals as a whole.</p>
	Specific Objectives	<p>Seven specific Objectives can be directly derived from the subitems of the Circular Economy Action Plan. These include the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A sustainable product policy framework shall be achieved. In essence, a sustainable and circular business model is planned to be the new norm. This new norm will orient itself by “<i>sustainability principals and other appropriate ways</i>” that are expected to lead the way in future policies and legislative developments. This new framework will apply to products as well as services. Targets in this context are – among

		<p>others – improved product durability, reusability, reparability, an increase in energy efficiency and recycled content, a decrease in the carbon and environmental footprint, the insurance of performance and safety standards, but also the addressment of the presence of hazardous chemicals in products. In addition, this objective covers a general facilitation of greater industrial circularity together with an enhancement of consumers in form of providing better, more transparent information about sustainability of products and by new material rights for consumers.</p> <p>2. Key product value chains are intended to be better managed. The action plan sets out the objective to identify and address barriers that hinder the expansion of markets for circular products in selected sectors. Relevant sectors are first and foremost electronics, ICT, batteries, vehicles, packaging, plastics, textiles, food, water, nutrients as well as construction and buildings. A general decrease of the presence of microplastics in the environment, a decrease in food waste and securement of sustainability of renewable bio-based resources will be accompanying these objectives. Some more specific targets in that regard entail:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To ensure that all packaging on the EU market is reusable or recyclable in an economically viable way by 2030 • Provide guidance to achieve high levels of separate collection of textile waste, which Member States have to ensure by 2025 <p>3. “Less waste, more value” describes the objective of the action plan to decouple waste generation from economic growth by better managing EU waste streams. This is meant to be achieved by a) preventing and or reducing waste generation where possible in the first place, b) increasing the recycling of waste, c) modernizing and regularly updating EU waste laws, d) enhancing circularity by preventing and removing hazardous and persistent substances from the secondary-raw-material-cycle as well as e) helping those secondary raw materials to compete with primary raw materials by creating a well-functioning EU market for them. In addition to that the EU plans to take more responsibility for its waste stream by f) restricting its export of waste – especially of waste that could be treated in the EU or that is considered harmful to environment and or health – to third countries. A specific target in this regard is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Halve the amount of residual (non-recycled) municipal waste by 2030 • Double circular material use rate in the coming decade <p>4. Making circularity work for people, regions and cities by harnessing “the potential of EU financing instruments and funds” to invest in the green transition to a circular economy model and use said transition to create new jobs related to it.</p> <p>5. Use Crosscutting actions to enhance synergy between greenhouse gas emission reductions and circularity and use the circular economy in that regard to achieve climate neutrality. Also steer financing towards supporting the circular economy and sustainable production and consumption patterns. To complement this, it is planned to further stimulate research, innovation and digitalization.</p> <p>6. Another Objective is to offer leading efforts at global level to support a global shift to a circular economy that supports the implementation of the 2030 SDGs as well.</p> <p>7. Reinforcing EU monitoring progress to generate adequate data.</p>		
		<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1729 1176 1827 1246">Relevant To ZeroPM:</td> <td data-bbox="1827 1176 1924 1246">Relation to other WPs:</td> </tr> </table>	Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:			

Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development	2021: Methodologies to track and minimize the presence of substances of concern in recycled materials and articles made thereof	X	WP2/5/7	
		2021: Harmonised information systems for the presence of substances of concern	X	WP2/4/5	
		2023: Improving measurement, modelling and policy tools to capture synergies between the circular economy and climate change mitigation and adaptation at EU and national level			
		2021: Updating the Circular Economy Monitoring Framework to reflect new policy priorities and develop further indicators on resource use, including consumption and material footprints	X		
	Policy-realignment	2021: Legislative proposal for a sustainable product policy initiative	X	WP4	
		2021: Legislative and non-legislative measures establishing a new “right to repair”			
		As of 2021: Review of the Industrial Emissions Directive, including the integration of circular economy practices in upcoming Best Available Techniques (BAT) reference documents	X	WP7	
		2020/2021: Circular Electronics Initiative, common charger solution, and reward systems to return old devices			
		2021: Review of the Directive on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment and guidance to clarify its links with REACH and Ecodesign requirements	X	WP2	
		2020: Proposal for a new regulatory framework for batteries	X	WP2	
		2021: Review of the rules on end-of-life vehicles	X	WP5	
		2022: Review of the rules on proper treatment of waste oils	X	WP5	
		2021: Review to reinforce the essential requirements for packaging and reduce (over)packaging and packaging waste	X	WP2/4/5	
		2021: Policy framework for bio-based plastics and biodegradable or compostable plastics	X	WP2	
		2021: EU Strategy for Textiles	X	WP2/4	
		2021: Strategy for a Sustainable Built Environment			
		2021: Initiative to substitute single-use packaging, tableware and cutlery by reusable products in food services			
		2022: Waste reduction targets for specific streams and other measures on waste prevention #			
		2022: EU-wide harmonized model for separate collection of waste and labelling to facilitate separate collection			
		2021: Scoping the development of further EU-wide end-of-waste and by-product criteria			
		2021: Revision of the rules on waste shipments	X	WP5	
		As of 2020: Supporting the circular economy transition through the Skills Agenda, the forthcoming Action Plan for Social Economy, the Pact for Skills and the European Social Fund Plus			
		2023: Regulatory framework for the certification of carbon removals			
		2021: Reflecting circular economy objectives in the revision of the guidelines on state aid in the field of environmental and energy			
		Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation	2020: Legislative proposal on substantiating green claims		
			2021/2022: Mandatory requirements on recycled plastic content and plastic waste reduction measures for key products such as packaging, construction materials and vehicles	X	WP2/4
	2021: Restriction of intentionally added microplastics and measures on unintentional release of microplastics				

	Raising awareness (consumers)	2020: Legislative proposal empowering consumers in the green transition		
	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	2022: Launch of an industry-led industrial symbiosis reporting and certification system		
	Stakeholder cooperation	2020/2021: Mainstreaming circular economy objectives in the context of the rules on non-financial reporting, and initiatives on sustainable corporate governance and on environmental accounting		
		As of 2020: Leading efforts towards reaching a global agreement on plastics	X	WP5
		As of 2021: Proposing a Global Circular Economy Alliance and initiating discussions on an international agreement on the management of natural resources		
	Financing	As of 2020: Mainstreaming circular economy objectives in free trade agreements, in other bilateral, regional and multilateral processes and agreements, and in EU external policy funding instruments		
		As of 2021: Mandatory Green Public Procurement (GPP) criteria and targets in sectoral legislation and phasing-in mandatory reporting on GPP	X	WP4
Other	As of 2020: Supporting the circular economy transition through Cohesion policy funds, the Just Transition Mechanism and urban initiatives			
Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback	Feedback was given in form of a 4 weeks long feedback period that ended on 20 th January 2020. A total of 374 replies were given. These are available under: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12095-Circular-economy-new-action-plan-to-increase-recycling-and-reuse-of-products-in-the-EU_en (accessed 22.06.2022)			
Challenges	<p>A challenge of establishing the market for secondary raw materials: In the single market, many products break down too quickly or cannot be easily reused, repaired or recycled. Using secondary raw materials instead of prime raw materials is not only a possible solution for this and other issues but also essential for setting up the circular economy. To achieve this, secondary raw materials need to be able to compete with prime raw materials related to performance, availability, costs and safety. Yet a number of issues arise. For example – and relevant for ZeroPM – there is an issue related to the safety of these materials, since they can be contaminated by (banned) substances that persist in recycled feedstock. Because of this, concerns relating to persistent and mobile substances exist.</p> <p>A challenge of managing waste streams: Generated waste in the EU is despite efforts still not going down according to the Circular Economic Action Plan. Nevertheless, a decoupling of waste generation from economic growth is strived for. This will be a demanding task at all levels and along the whole value chain. With regards to this, half of the EU member states are at a risk of non-compliance in terms of the target of recycling 50% of municipal waste. On top of that, there are legal and illegal waste exports to non-EU-countries that not only represent a sort of resource loss in cases, which contain waste that could have been recycled in the EU, but also harbour negative environmental and or health impacts to those countries, they are shipped to.</p>			

	<p>A global challenge: According to the action plan, global consumption of materials is expected to double in the next forty years. Still the European Commission states, that a global transition to a circular economy is mandatory for the EU to succeed and achieve its goals. This holds especially true in terms of plastics and in regard to free trade agreements.</p> <p>A social challenge: A systemic, deep and transformative transition to a circular economy can be disruptive for society at times, according to the Circular Economy Action Plan. A fair transition is therefore needed, that will involve cooperation of stakeholders at all levels.</p> <p>A challenge posed by certain sectors of key value chains: Electrical and electronic equipment, batteries, packaging, plastics, textiles, construction and building as well as the food value chain are all sectors that pose issues on their own in terms of low recycling-rates, high waste-generation, sustainability, ethical sourcing of raw materials, carbon footprint, ubiquitous use or raw material consumption while still essential to society in some ways. This multitude of issues of these key value chains needs to be tackled in the future to ensure a functioning transition to a circular economy.</p>
<p>Proposed timeline</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adoption of the first pre-Green-Deal-version of the Circular Economy Action Plan: December 2015 (replaced by the new Circular Economy Action Plan referred to in this template) • Adoption of the Circular Economy Action Plan by the European Commission: March 11th 2020 • Planned review: not stated in the strategy document.
<p>Links</p>	<p>Overview by the European Commission: https://ec.europa.eu/environment/strategy/circular-economy-action-plan_en (accessed 22.06.2022)</p> <p>Circular Economy Action Plan; COM(2020) 98 final: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2020:98:FIN (accessed 22.06.2022)</p>
<p>Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document</p>	<p>Strategy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - COM(2018) 28 final (EU Strategy for Plastics in the Circular Economy) - COM(2018) 673 final (Bioeconomy Action Plan) - COM(2019) 640 final (The European Green Deal) - COM(2020) 21 final (Green Deal Investment Plan) - COM(2020) 380 final (EU Biodiversity Strategy) - COM(2020) 381 final (Farm to Fork Strategy) - COM(2020) 662 final (Renovation Wave) - COM(2020) 667 final (Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability) - COM(2022) 141 final (EU Strategy for Textiles) <p>Legislative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Directive 86/278/EEC (Sewage Sludge Directive) - Directive 91/271/EEC (Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive) - Directive 94/62/EC (on packaging and packaging waste) - Directive 98/83/EC (Drinking Water Directive) - Directive 2000/53/EC (on end-of life vehicles) - Directive 2006/66/EC (Batteries Directive; this is planned to be replaced by a new regulatory framework for batteries in the near future) - Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 (on shipments of waste)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 (REACH) - Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 (CLP) - Directive 2008/98/EC (on waste and repealing certain Directives) - Directive 2009/125/EC (Ecodesign Directive) - Directive 2010/75/EU (Industrial Emissions Directive) - Directive 2011/65/EU (on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment) - Directive (EU) 2019/904 (on Single Use Plastic Products) - Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 (on Persistent Organic Pollutants) - Regulation (EU) 2020/741 (Water Reuse Regulation) - Regulation (EU) 2021/695 (Horizon Europe) <p>Conventions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stockholm Convention <p>Other:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU Environmental Technology Verification scheme - (2022/C/80/01) Guidelines on State aid for environmental protection and energy
<p style="text-align: center;">Links to other ZeroPM-WPs</p>	<p>WP2 (Alternative Assessment): Links to WP2 relate to the assessment of alternative, safer chemicals could be found in the development of methodologies to track and minimize the presence of substances in recycled content (e.g. by life cycle considerations). The same holds true for the planned harmonized information system on “substances of very high concern and other relevant substances”. The assessment of alternatives could play a role too with regards to the review of reinforcing essential requirements for packaging along with the action on mandatory requirements on recycled plastic content, since this affects food contact materials and other key products which often contain persistent and mobile substances like construction materials and vehicles. Also, the review of the Industrial Emissions Directive and more specific the here mentioned inclusion of circular economy practices in form of upcoming Best Available Techniques (BAT) and the upcoming EU Strategy for Textiles might be touching on WP2s methods to provide safer alternatives to questionable substances and their use.</p> <p>WP4 (Market Transition): The legislative proposal for a sustainable product policy initiative, the harmonized information system for the presence of substances of concern, reviews as well as revisions and introductions of legislations that concern themselves with circular economic practices, objectives, requirements and guidelines on state aid and many other actions of the Circular Economic Action Plan that highlight a willingness for strong cooperation with the industry might be of interest for WP4 and its task to assist a market transition away from persistent and mobile substances and its close collaboration with the chemical industry.</p> <p>WP5 (Substance grouping): WP5 will profit or be interested in the development of methodologies to track and minimize the presence of substances in recycled content as well as the introduction of a harmonized information system for the presence of substances of concern. On a similar note, WP5s new strategies of grouping (persistent and mobile) substances might prove fruitful in the context of reviews or revisions of existing legislatives and or upcoming proposals mentioned in the Circular Economy Action Plan like the Industrial Emissions Directive (in terms of integrating circular economy practices into Best Available Techniques BAT), a new regulatory framework for batteries, rules on end-of-life vehicles, rules on waste oil treatment or rules on requirements for packaging and packaging waste.</p>

	<p>WP6 (Risk Assessment): Since the Circular Economy Action Plan speaks of closing the gaps on scientific knowledge related to risks and occurrences of microplastics in the environment, drinking water and food with regards to establishing restrictions on intentionally added microplastics and on measures on unintentional releases of microplastics, a potential linkage to WP6 work of risk assessment might exist – depending on the role additives play.</p> <p>WP7 (Technical Solutions): As mentioned for WP2 and WP5, the Circular Economy Action Plan expressed an interest in developing methodologies to track and minimize the presence of substances of concern in recycled content. Although primary dealing with drinking water, waste water and sludge there might be points of interest for Technical Solutions regarding the minimizing of substances of concern in recycled content.</p>
Notes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A total of 35 Actions are to be found in the Annex of the Circular Economy Action Plan. • A first Circular Economy Action Plan was adopted by the European Commission in December 2015. With the emergence of the European Green Deal, a new Version, the “New Circular Economy Action Plan”, which this template covers and refers as the “Circular Economy Action Plan”, was released in 2020. • For the action “legislative proposal for a sustainable product policy initiative” it is mentioned, that future regulation-approaches as well as broader policy developments (like strategy-documents) will try to follow “<i>sustainability principles</i>”. One of these principles states to improve – among others – the addressment of the presence of hazardous chemicals in products, which might very well relate to persistent and mobile substances as well. These principles should be kept a keen eye on, since they might be a potential pathway to achieve ZeroPMs goals by influencing future EU-policy.

Table for further analysis of actions/measures with relevance to ZeroPM:

Actions, Sub-actions and Relevance to ZeroPM		Subcategories:							Prioritize	Remediate
		Research & Development	Policy-realignment	Tightening and re-formation of relevant legislation	Raising awareness (consumers)	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Stakeholder co-operation	Financing		
<p>Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)</p>	<p>2021: Legislative proposal for a sustainable product policy initiative</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> This action is of interest for ZeroPM, since it tries at its core to widen the already in place Ecodesign Directive beyond only energy-related products to “the broadest possible range of products” and ensure circularity in this context. This includes setting “<i>sustainability principles</i>” for regulating. One of these principles contains the improvement of “<i>product durability, reusability, upgradability and reparability, addressing the presence of hazardous chemicals in products...</i>”. The last part – the</p>		X	x						

	<p>addressing of hazardous chemicals in products – could relate to persistent and mobile substances as well. On top of this, electronics, ICT (information and communication technologies), textures, furniture and high intermediary products like steel, cement and chemicals themselves will be prioritized.</p>									
	<p>As of 2021: Mandatory Green Public Procurement (GPP) criteria and targets in sectoral legislation and phasing-in mandatory reporting on GPP</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> This action most likely will not be very relevant for ZeroPM. However, in the case that persistent and mobile substances play a role in the GPP-criteria, a certain degree of relevance might exist, depending on interpretation. Also, there is an intent for guiding, training and disseminating good practices for public buyers as well as monitoring in form of compulsory reporting for public buyers, which might be of some relevance also, if persistent and mobile substances are included.</p>			x	x		x			
	<p>As of 2021: Review of the Industrial Emissions Directive, including the integration of circular economy practices in upcoming Best Available Techniques (BAT) reference documents</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> As the main instrument of the EU for regulating pollutant emissions from industrial installations this action, and therefore the Industrial Emissions Directive itself too, will be of high relevance.</p>		x							
	<p>2021: Review of the Directive on the restriction of the use of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment and guidance to clarify its links with REACH and Ecodesign requirements</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Since hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment might – depending on the definition – very well translate to persistent and mobile substances this will be of relevance for ZeroPM.</p>		x							
	<p>2020: Proposal for a new regulatory framework for batteries</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> This might be of relevance depending on what kind of substances can be found within batteries targeted by the new framework. If persistent and mobile</p>		x							

	<p>substances are included, relevance for ZeroPM is given.</p>									
	<p>2021: Review of the rules on end-of-life vehicles</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This might be of relevance depending on what kind of substances can be found within ELVs (end-of-life-vehicles). If persistent and mobile substances are included, relevance for ZeroPM is given.</p>		X							
	<p>2022: Review of the rules on proper treatment of waste oils</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This might be of relevance depending on what kind of substances can be found within waste oils. If persistent and mobile substances are included, relevance for ZeroPM is given.</p>		X							
	<p>2021: Review to reinforce the essential requirements for packaging and reduce (over)packaging and packaging waste</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This is in some parts relevant to ZeroPM. Since packaging and especially food packaging contains quite often persistent and mobile substances for water- and oil-repellent attributes, an overall reduction of (over)packaging and packaging waste aligns with ZeroPMs goals in form of indirect effects. In addition, considerations in terms of reducing the complexity of packaging materials like the number of used materials and polymers as well as the planned establishment of rules for the safe recycling into food contact materials of plastic materials other than PET might – depending on additives – also be of relevance for ZeroPM.</p>		X	x	x					
	<p>2021/2022: Mandatory requirements on recycled plastic content and plastic waste reduction measures for key products such as packaging, construction materials and vehicles</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This might be of relevance depending on what kind of substances (additives) can be found within the covered plastics. If persistent and mobile substances are included, ZeroPM will have an interest.</p>			X						
	<p>2021: Restriction of intentionally added microplastics and measures on unintentional release of microplastics</p>	x		X						x

	<p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This might be of relevance depending on what kind of substances (additives) can be found within plastics. If persistent and mobile substances are included, ZeroPM will have an interest.</p> <p>This action addresses the presence of microplastics by restricting intentionally added microplastics, developing measures (regulatory and more) on the unintentional release of microplastics, capture of said emissions, as well as measuring (in a harmonized way) their release and closing a scientific knowledge gap in terms of risks and occurrences of microplastics in the environment, drinking water and food. The last part could be of interest for WP6.</p>									
	<p>2021: Policy framework for bio-based plastics and biodegradable or compostable plastics</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This might be of relevance depending on what kind of substances (additives) can be found within plastics. If persistent and mobile substances are included, ZeroPM will have an interest. Further, this might be of interest for WP2 in terms of searching for alternatives.</p>		X							
	<p>2021: EU Strategy for Textiles</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>Since PFAS, which are often persistent and mobile substances, can be found in textiles, the new EU Strategy for Textiles will be of concern for ZeroPM. This is true especially, since the Circular Economy Action Plan explicitly mentions to tackle the “presence of hazardous chemicals” which could cover persistent and mobile substances as well.</p>		X	x	x	x	x			
	<p>2021: Methodologies to track and minimize the presence of substances of concern in recycled materials and articles made thereof</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>Since this action deals with “substances that pose problems to health or the environment” and the Circular Economy Action Plan explicitly mentions “substances identified as being of very high concern and other relevant substances, in particular those with chronic effects” this measure might include persistent and</p>	X						x	x	

	mobile substances as well. The removal of contaminants from waste is incorporated into the action as well.									
	<p>2021: Harmonised information systems for the presence of substances of concern</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>Since this action deals with “substances that pose problems to health or the environment” and the Circular Economy Action Plan explicitly mentions “substances identified as being of very high concern and other relevant substances, in particular those with chronic effects” this measure might include persistent and mobile substances as well. On top of that, the action plan proposes cooperation with the industry for the establishment of the harmonized information system and the amendment of the annexes of the Regulation on Persistent Organic Pollutants in line with scientific and technical findings. Also, the classification and management of hazardous waste shall be improved.</p>	X	x			x		x		
	<p>2021: Revision of the rules on waste shipments</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>While the Regulation on shipments of waste in its current form would only be of slight relevance for the matter of persistent and mobile substances, the upcoming revision announced to include restrictions in terms of exports of waste that have harmful environmental and health impacts in third countries. Said revision therefore might include pollutants like persistent and mobile substances and should be considered.</p>		X							
	<p>2021: Reflecting circular economy objectives in the revision of the guidelines on state aid in the field of environmental and energy</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>The State Aid Guidelines of 2014-2020 already did include pollution by hazardous substances to some degree regarding conditions for state aid. The revision is to be expected to deepen this content in face of the Zero Pollution Ambition of the EU. Because of this persistent and mobile substances might be addressed in some form too.</p>		X							
	<p>As of 2020: Leading efforts towards reaching a global agreement on plastics</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This might be of relevance depending on what kind of substances (additives) can</p>					X				

	be found within plastics. If persistent and mobile substances are included, ZeroPM should have an interest in efforts leading to a potential international agreement.										
	<p>2021: Updating the Circular Economy Monitoring Framework to reflect new policy priorities and develop further indicators on resource use, including consumption and material footprints</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This action will be of relevance for ZeroPM, since it is planned to incorporate new indicators that are also interlinked with the Zero Pollution Ambition. New indicators are expected to cover not only resource use, but consumption and material footprints too. This could very well contain information about persistent and mobile substances too.</p>	X									
	Relevant actions/measure of the Circular Economic Action Plan: 18 out of 35										

Appendix E: EU Beating Cancer Plan

Name(s) of the initiative/policy		Europe's Beating Cancer Plan COM(2021) 44 final (complemented by SWD(2021) 13 final)
Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM		<p>Europe's Beating Cancer Plan describes an EU-initiative that sets out a framework for lessening the burden that cancer puts on patients, families and health systems as a whole. For this cause, the plan addresses inequalities across the EU, tackles new technological possibilities like the use of AI, personalized medicine or a better use of electronical health data, strives for advancements in research and innovation and presents measures that are structured around four key-areas: prevention, early detection, diagnosis and treatment as well as quality of life of cancer patients and survivors to tackle the entire disease pathway. While doing so, the action plan contains a multi-stakeholder approach that spans across multiple policy areas (among others agriculture and environment, to highlight two areas of interest for ZeroPM) under the catchphrase of "Health in All Policies".</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM: Europe's Beating Cancer Plan does mention environmental pollution, chemical contamination and the resulting risks for human health with regards to cancer prevention – but only in a comparable short section of the text. While doing so, the action plan refers for the most part to the European Green Deal, the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability or the Zero Pollution Action Plan. With that in mind, there are some single actions that might be of moderate relevance for ZeroPM, but all things considered, Europe's Beating Cancer Plan is only of low relevance in terms of political actions against persistent and mobile substances.</p>
Type of act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal • Others
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)	<p>The dominating objective of Europe's Beating Cancer plan is the renewal of Europe's commitment to cancer prevention, treatment and care that recognizes contemporary challenges, opportunities and developments by tackling the entire disease pathway along the four key action areas of prevention, early detection, diagnosis and treatment as well as quality of life of cancer patients and survivors.</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM: The only (specific) objective that correlates with ZeroPMs activities would be the reduction of environmental pollution in close interaction with the European Green Deal and the Zero Pollution Action Plan as well as the reduction of exposure to hazardous substances as part of the cancer prevention goals of Europe's Beating Cancer Plan.</p>
	Specific Objectives	<p>Seven specific Objectives can be directly derived from the subitems of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy. These include the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop a modern approach to cancer with the help of new technologies, research and innovation at the service of patient-centered cancer prevention and care <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drive change through knowledge and research • Use new technologies and scientific progress to better address cancer along the entire disease pathway. This includes better use of health data, digitalization, sharing knowledge, AI and personalized medicine in reference to prevention and care

		<p>2. Safe lives through sustainable cancer prevention</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve health literacy on cancer risks and determinants • Achieve a tobacco-free Europe • Reduce harmful alcohol consumption • Improve health promotion through access to healthy diets and physical activity • Reduce <u>environmental pollution</u> (the Beating Cancer Plan states to “interact closely with the Green Deal and its Zero Pollution Action Plan to step up action on contaminants in surface, ground and drinking water, soil and air”) • Reduce exposure to <u>hazardous substances</u> and radiation • Prevent cancers caused by infections <p>3. Improve early detection of cancer</p> <p>4. Ensure high standards in cancer care</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliver higher-quality care • Ensure a high-quality health workforce • Ensure access to essential medicines and innovation • Build on the promise of personalized medicine for cancer prevention, diagnosis and treatment <p>5. Improve the quality of life for cancer patients, survivors and carers</p> <p>6. Reduce cancer inequalities across the EU</p> <p>7. Put childhood cancer under the spotlight</p> <p>In addition to these seven focal points Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan also deals with funding, international collaboration and coordination as well as with implementation and governance to align policies across the European Commission and other EU institutions in reference to the above-mentioned goals and objectives.</p>		
<i>(Only actions of Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan that are related to ZeroPMs activities have been included below)</i>			Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development	2021-2025: Launch Horizon Europe Partnership on Assessment of Risks from Chemicals to strengthen EU capacities for chemical risk assessment.	X	WP6
	Policy-realignment	N/A		
	Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation	2021-2025: Reduce workers’ exposure to carcinogenic substances through the amendments of the Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive.	X	WP6

	Raising awareness (consumers)	N/A		
	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	N/A		
	Stakeholder cooperation	N/A		
	Financing	N/A		
	Other	N/A		
Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		N/A		
Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		N/A		
Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		N/A		
Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback		<p>Feedback was given in form of a 4 weeks long feedback period that ended on 3th March 2020. A total of 384 replies were given. These are available under: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12154-Europe%E2%80%99s-Beating-Cancer-Plan/feedback_de?p_id=6335574 (accessed 21.06.2022)</p> <p>Feedback was also given in form of a 12 weeks long consultation period that ended on 21st May 2020. A total of 2069 replies were given. These are available under: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12154-Europe-s-Beating-Cancer-Plan/public-consultation_en (accessed 21.06.2022)</p> <p>Also, accompanying the stakeholder consultation, a Staff Working Paper – SWD(2021) 13 final – in form of a synopsis report has been published: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52021SC0013 (accessed 21.06.2022)</p>		
Challenges		<p>Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan states a multitude of challenges in terms of cancer care, prevention, research and more. Tough the only challenge that is of particular relevance for ZeroPM is the following:</p> <p>A challenge of environmental pollution in terms of cancer prevention: Air pollution as well as (chemical) contaminants pose various risks for not only the environment but also for human health (e.g. in form of carcinogens). This is especially true in cases of substances penetrating surface, ground and drinking water, but also in regards to soil. With this, exposure to hazardous substances – with focus on the workplace – is one of the challenges stated in the action plan.</p>		
Proposed timeline		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adoption of Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan by the European Commission: February 03th 2021 Planned review: End of 2024 		
Links		<p>Roadmap: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12154-Europe%E2%80%99s-Beating-Cancer-Plan_en (accessed 22.06.2022)</p>		

	<p>Document of Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=COM:2021:44:FIN (accessed 22.06.2022)</p> <p>Staff Working Document – Stakeholder Consultation – Synopsis Report; SWD (2021) 13 final: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52021SC0013 (accessed 22.06.2022)</p>
Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document	<p>Strategy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - COM(2019) 640 final (The European Green Deal) - COM(2020) 381 final (Farm to Fork Strategy) - COM(2020) 456 final (Next Generation EU) - COM(2020) 667 final (Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability) - COM(2020) 761 final (Pharmaceutical Strategy) - COM(2021) 323 final (Occupational Safety and Health Strategic Framework 2021-2027) - COM(2021) 400 final (Zero Pollution Action Plan) <p>Legislative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Directive 98/83/EC (Drinking Water Directive) - Directive 2000/60/EC (Water Framework Directive) - Directive 2004/37/EC (Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive) - Directive 2010/75/EU (Industrial Emissions Directive) - Regulation (EU) 2021/695 (Horizon Europe)
Links to other ZeroPM-WPs	<p>WP6:</p> <p>The only WP that might be linked to Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan would be WP6 in terms of assessment of the risks from chemicals with regards to carcinogenic attributes of substances. In this context, the launch of the Horizon Europe Partnership on Assessment of Risks from Chemicals might pose a gateway to get more attention to persistent and mobile substances. While doing so, WP6 findings might be used to give feedback and reduce workers exposure to carcinogenic substances through the planned amendments of the Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive.</p>
Notes	<p>This document is not directly part of the European Green Deal. It can be contributed to “Promoting Our European Way of Life” though – one of the other 5 goals under President of the European Commission Von der Leyen.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A total of 42 actions are to be found in Annex I of the Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan • Of these 42 actions 10 describe flagship initiatives, 32 describe supporting actions • Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan is one of the four pillars of the European Health Union – COM(2020) 724 final – that emerged as a response to the COVID-19 pandemic

Table for further analysis of actions/measures with relevance to ZeroPM:

Actions, Sub-actions and Relevance to ZeroPM		Subcategories:							Prioritize	Remediate		
		Research & Development	Policy-realignment	Tightening and re-formation of relevant legislation	Raising awareness (consumers)	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Stakeholder co-operation	Financing			Other	
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	2021-2025: Launch Horizon Europe Partnership on Assessment of Risks from Chemicals to strengthen EU capacities for chemical risk assessment <u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> The European Partnership on Assessment of Risks from Chemicals deals with research, knowledge sharing and chemical risk assessments. With that, persistent and mobile substances would fall into the analytical scope. Therefore, this action is of relevance.	X					X			X		
	2021-2025: Reduce workers’ exposure to carcinogenic substances through the amendments of the Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive. <u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Carcinogenic substances cover in part PMT-substances and with that persistent and mobile substances as well.			X								
	Relevant actions/measure of the Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan: 2 out of 42											

Appendix F: Farm to Fork Strategy

Name(s) of the initiative/policy		A Farm to Fork Strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system Farm to Fork Strategy COM(2020) 381 final (+Annex)
Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM		The Farm to Fork Strategy was adopted in May 2020, in the wake of the Green Deal, with the general aim to achieve the transition to sustainable food systems in the EU. The Strategy takes a global approach and addresses the whole food supply chain – from agriculture and food production to food processing, wholesale, retail, hospitality and food services, and food consumption and diets. As part of the Strategy, a legislative framework for sustainable food systems should be developed. For agriculture, it establishes common targets with the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the Soil Strategy regarding pesticide and fertiliser use, which links it to the zero-pollution ambition. Relevance to ZeroPM: The Farm-to-Fork Strategy addresses agricultural pollution and sets targets for the reduction of pesticide and fertiliser use by 2030. It also addresses the use of hazardous substances in food packaging and refers to the revision of the FMC legislation.
Type of act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal • Others
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)	The general objective of the Farm to Fork Strategy is to achieve the transition to sustainable food systems in the EU, in order to contribute to the overall objective of the Green Deal to reach climate neutrality. The Strategy should: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure sustainable food production – i.e. that EU food systems (covering the whole food chain from food production, to transport, distribution, marketing and consumption) have ‘a neutral or positive environmental impact’, protect natural resources and ecosystems, help mitigating climate change and adapting to its impact, reduce dependency on pesticides and antimicrobials, reduce excess fertilisation, increase organic farming, improve animal welfare, and reverse biodiversity loss • Ensure food security and access to ‘sufficient, nutritious, sustainable food’ for everyone • Promote sustainable food consumption and facilitating the shift to healthy, sustainable diets • Promote sustainable food industry (including processing, wholesale, retail, hospitality and food services) practices • Reduce food waste • Reduce food fraud • Ensure the ‘affordability of food, while generating fairer economic returns in the supply chain’ • Promote global transition to sustainable food systems
	Specific Objectives	Sustainable food production covers the following objectives and targets relevant to ZeroPM: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% and the use of more hazardous pesticides by 50% by 2030 • Promote greater use of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and safer alternative control methods such as crop rotation and mechanical weeding, as well as agricultural practices that reduce the use of pesticides • Facilitate the placing on the market of pesticides containing biological active substances and reinforce the environmental risk assessment of pesticides

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve the collection of statistical data on pesticides use • Reduce nutrient losses by at least 50% and the use of fertilisers by at least 20% by 2030 • Increase the sustainability of the livestock sector to reduce nutrient pollution, promote sustainable agricultural practices that reduce nutrient pollution and the application of precise fertilisation techniques • Reduce overall EU sales of antimicrobials for farmed animals and in aquaculture by 50% by 2030 • Reach at least 25% of the EU's agricultural land under organic farming by 2030 <p>Sustainable food industry practices covers the following objectives and targets relevant to ZeroPM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revise the food contact materials legislation with a view to improve food safety and public health, in particular by reducing the use of hazardous chemicals • Promote innovative and sustainable packaging solutions using environmentally-friendly, re-usable and recyclable materials and the substitution of single-use food packaging and cutlery by re-usable products <p>Sustainable food consumption covers the following objectives and targets relevant to ZeroPM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmonisation of voluntary green claims • Development of a sustainable labelling framework covering nutritional, climate, environmental and social aspects of food products <p><i>Relevance to ZeroPM: to be determined as which environmental aspects will be covered by the sustainable labelling framework is not specified in the Strategy.</i></p> <p>Promote global transition to sustainable food systems covers the following objectives and targets relevant to ZeroPM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lead the work on international sustainability standards and environmental footprint calculation methods in multilateral fora <p>Support research, innovation, technology and investments enabling the transition towards sustainable food systems covers the following objectives and targets relevant to ZeroPM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setting up a mission in the area of soil health and food to develop solutions for restoring soil health and functions (<i>unsure whether this may include pollution remediation</i>) • Setting up a dedicated partnership on agro-ecology living laboratories aiming to contribute to reducing the use of pesticides, fertilisers and antimicrobials <p>Support the development of advisory services, data and knowledge-sharing, and skills covers the following objectives and targets relevant to ZeroPM: Promote effective Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), involving all food chain actors (<i>may include pesticide reduction and IPM alternatives</i>)</p>	
(only actions from the Action Plan with some relevance to ZeroPM have been included below)		Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
Actions/Measures for "prevent and reduce" & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development	N/A	
		N/A	
	Policy-realignment	N/A	
		Proposal for a legislative framework for sustainable food systems by 2023	

	Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation	Proposal for a revision of the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive to significantly reduce use and risk and dependency on pesticides and enhance Integrated Pest Management by Q1 2022	X	WP7
		Revision of the relevant implementing Regulations under the Plant Protection Products framework to facilitate placing on the market of plant protection products containing biological active substances by Q4 2021		
		Proposal for a revision of the pesticides statistics Regulation to overcome data gaps and reinforce evidence-based policy making by 2023		
		Proposal for a revision of the feed additives Regulation to reduce the environmental impact of livestock farming by Q4 2021		
		Proposal for a revision of EU legislation on Food Contact Materials to improve food safety, ensure citizens' health and reduce the environmental footprint of the sector by Q4 2022	X	WP2 / WP4
		Proposal for a sustainable food labelling framework to empower consumers to make sustainable food choices by 2024		
	Raising awareness (consumers / citizens)	N/A		
	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	N/A		
		N/A		
	Stakeholder cooperation	N/A		
	Financing	N/A		
		N/A		
Other	N/A			
Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback	N/A			
Challenges	No challenges are clearly outlined in the Strategy			
Proposed timeline	The farm to Fork Strategy was adopted in 2020 and will be reviewed mid-2023 to assess whether the EU is on track to reach the 2030 targets or whether further action is needed.			
Links	https://ec.europa.eu/food/horizontal-topics/farm-fork-strategy_en			
Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document	Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 Circular Economy Action Plan Common Agricultural Policy			

Links to other ZeroPM-WPs	<p>WP2 / WP4 – the revision of the food contact material legislation may be of interest with regards to substitution, development of PFAS free packaging etc.</p> <p>WP6 The Strategy mentions the strengthening of environmental risk assessment of pesticides. It is unclear where this is addressed in the Action Plan (may be through the one substance one assessment initiative).</p> <p>WP7 – the Strategy relates to the prevention of soil and water pollution – the Farm to Fork Strategy however does not address remediation (covered by the Soil Strategy).</p>
Notes	

Table for further analysis of actions/measures with relevance to ZeroPM:

Actions, Sub-actions and Relevance to ZeroPM		Subcategories:							Prioritize	Remediate
		Research & Development	Policy-realignment	Tightening and re-formation of relevant legislation	Raising awareness (consumers)	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Stakeholder co-operation	Financing		
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	<p>Proposal for a revision of the Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive to significantly reduce use and risk and dependency on pesticides and enhance Integrated Pest Management by Q1 2022</p> <p><u>Relevance for ZeroPM:</u> the revision of the SUPD should contribute to the 50% reduction target for pesticide use. The revision should aim to reduce the use and risk of pesticides containing more hazardous active substances; increase the uptake of less hazardous and non-chemical alternatives for pest control.</p>			X						
	<p>Proposal for a revision of EU legislation on Food Contact Materials to improve food safety, ensure citizens’ health and reduce the environmental footprint of the sector by Q4 2022</p> <p><u>Relevance for ZeroPM:</u> FMC legislation very important to follow given the presence of PMT/vPvM substances (in particular PFAS) in food packaging. the FMC legislation is one of the pieces of legislation for which the introduction of the generic approach to the assessment and management of chemicals should be considered (link with Chemicals Strategy). Link with the development of the essential use criteria – the inception IA clearly refers to the need to define the essential uses of substances in FCMS, taking into account the necessity of the final FCM together with replacement possibilities.</p>			X						

Appendix G: Industrial Strategy

<p>Name(s) of the initiative/policy</p>	<p>A New Industrial Strategy for Europe Updating the 2020 New Industrial Strategy: Building a stronger Single Market for Europe’s recovery Industrial Strategy / 2021 Update to the Industrial Strategy COM(2020) 102 final and COM(2021) 350 final Including accompanying SDW: Strategic dependencies and capacities (SWD(2021) 352 final), and EU strategic dependencies and capacities: second stage of in-depth reviews (SWD(2022) 41 final). Reference made to the Communication on critical Raw Materials Resilience: Charting a Path towards greater Security and Sustainability (COM(2020) 474 final).</p>
<p>Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM</p>	<p>The Industrial Strategy was first adopted in March 2020. Following the Covid-19 crisis, an update to the Strategy was adopted in May 2021. Both documents are described in this template.</p> <p>The primary objectives of the Industrial Strategy were to foster industrial transformation, in particular towards a more digital and green economy, make EU industry more competitive globally, and enhance Europe’s open strategic autonomy. The Strategy establishes links with the objectives of the Green Deal to reach climate neutrality and ‘creating new markets for climate neutral and circular products’, the Circular Economy Action Plan and the Chemicals strategy for sustainability as main strategies enabling industrial transformation. It sets the basis of an industrial ecosystems approach based on the identification of value chains needing specific sectoral approach.</p> <p>The 2021 Update to the Industrial Strategy does not replace or amend the Industrial Strategy but provides for a targeted update, which main rationale is to take stock of the lessons learnt from the pandemic, establish crisis response mechanisms and make the single market more efficient. It expands on the objective to reduce and prevent strategic dependencies in six strategic areas (i.e. raw materials – including rare earths, magnesium and chemicals – , batteries, active pharmaceutical ingredients, clean hydrogen, semiconductors, cloud and edge technologies) and accelerating the twin transition (i.e. digital and green transition). It builds on the ecosystems approach and sets the objective of creating green and digital transition pathways for the 14 relevant ecosystems, starting with tourism and energy intensive industries. The 14 sensitive industrial ecosystems for the recovery include sectors that are large users of chemicals, including PFAS, e.g. electronics, digital technologies, textile, aerospace and defence, mobility, transport and automotive, energy intensive industries, renewable energy and construction. These are detailed in the Staff Working Document on ‘Strategic dependencies and Capacities’ accompanying the 2021 Update to the Industrial Strategy (SWD(2021) 352 final), which presented a first stage of in-depth reviews for six strategic areas, complemented in February 2022 by a second in-depth review, including raw materials and chemicals (SWD(2022) 41 final).</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM: The strategy places some focus on the production of sustainable and circular products. The Strategy also includes chemicals in the six strategic areas in which EU’s industrial and strategic autonomy should be developed. The development of sustainable alternatives and market substitution are envisaged as ways to ensure EU’s autonomy, as well as developing EU’s production capacity and recycling.</p>
<p>Type of act</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Others 		
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)	<p>By 2030:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Foster industrial transformation towards a competitive, digitalised and green industry (enabling to reach the Green Deal objective of climate neutrality) Reinforcing Europe's industrial and strategic autonomy 		
	Specific Objectives	<p>'A New Industrial Strategy for Europe' contains the following objectives relevant to Zero PM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reaching climate neutrality: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> decarbonising energy intensive industries creating new markets for climate neutral and circular products, such as steel, cement and basic chemicals and clean technologies developing sustainable and smart mobility industries Building a more circular economy Reinforcing Europe's industrial and strategic autonomy – covering critical raw materials Developing targeted support for relevant industrial ecosystems <p>2021 Update to the Industrial Strategy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifying strategic dependencies in strategic areas and building a toolbox to reduce and prevent strategic dependencies Create green and digital transition pathways for relevant industrial ecosystems and reinforce the synergies between the sustainable and digital transitions. <p>EU strategic dependencies and capacities: second stage of in-depth reviews:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Address EU dependencies regarding critical raw materials diversify and pool risks as regards critical raw materials. The first in-depth review identified dependencies for 61 products related to raw/processed materials and chemicals (e.g. beryllium, cobalt, antimony, lithium, aluminium, tungstates, chromium, nickel, molybdenum, manganese, ferro-alloys, steel, and various chemicals products). The second in-depth review identified six chemicals as requiring particular attention (iodine, fluorine, red phosphorus, lithium oxide and hydroxide, molybdenum dioxide and tungstates) because EU production capacity for these chemicals is relatively limited, EU imports rely on one or two importing countries, the EU is also highly dependent for access to the raw materials that are at the basis of their production and these chemicals are at high risks of disruption as global demand is likely to increase. Build up resilient raw material value chains in the EU. This is underpinned by the Communication on Critical Raw Materials Resilience: Charting a Path towards greater Security and Sustainability, which announced the creation of a European Raw Materials Alliance and aims to develop raw materials recycling and diversify sourcing of key raw materials. 		
(only relevant actions for ZeroPM have been included below)			Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
Actions/Measures for "prevent and reduce" & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development	Promoting research and innovation through Horizon Europe (cluster 4 Digital, Industry and Space) on more sustainable alternatives to critical raw materials and chemicals – including better waste processing (recycling), innovative materials and increased substitution	X	WP2, WP4
		Mapping of potential secondary sources of critical raw materials in the EU		
		Promotion of relevant expertise and skills related to critical raw materials		

		Use of earth observation programmes for critical raw materials		
	Policy-realignment	Thorough screening and analysis of industrial needs and identification of ecosystems needing a tailor-made approach		
		Periodic review of strategic dependencies and monitoring of risks associated with strategic dependencies	X	WP6
		Development of EU principles on sustainable raw materials	X	WP4
	Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation	N/A		
	Raising awareness (consumers / citizens)	N/A		
	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	N/A		
	Stakeholder cooperation	Setting up of the Industrial Forum to support the implementation of the Strategy	X	WP4
		Launch of industrial alliances for relevant industrial ecosystems, e.g. European Raw Materials Alliance		
		Co-creation of green and digital transition pathways for relevant ecosystems, starting with tourism and energy intensive industries		
	Financing	Funding mechanism to build up resilient raw material value chains in the EU		
Other	Strategic partnership on raw material with third countries (Canada, Ukraine, African countries)			
Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback	N/A			
Challenges	No relevant challenges clearly outlined in the Strategy.			
Proposed timeline	The Strategy adopted in 2020 was updated a first time in 2021. The document does not specify a timeline for revision. The Strategy proposes a vision for 2030 ; actions proposed in the Strategy have however short timeframe (2021 /2022).			
Links	https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-industrial-strategy_en			
Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document	Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Circular Economy Action Plan Sustainable product policy framework EU Strategy for Textiles Circular Electronics Initiative			

	'Renovation Wave' Initiative and Strategy on the built environment
Links to other ZeroPM-WPs	WP4 – the process of identifying strategic dependencies and developing actions to prevent them may be a driver for substitution.
Notes	

Table for further analysis of actions/measures with relevance to ZeroPM:

Actions, Sub-actions and Relevance to ZeroPM		Subcategories:							Prioritize	Remediate
		Research & Development	Policy-realignment	Tightening and re-formation of relevant legislation	Raising awareness (consumers)	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Stakeholder co-operation	Financing		
Actions/Measures for "prevent and reduce" & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Promoting research and innovation through Horizon Europe (cluster 4 Digital, Industry and Space) on more sustainable alternatives to critical raw materials and chemicals – including better waste processing (recycling), innovative materials and increased substitution <u>Relevance for ZeroPM:</u> Limited relevance. Potential driver for substitution of certain chemicals substances.	X						X		
	Periodic review of strategic dependencies and monitoring of risks associated with strategic dependencies <u>Relevance for ZeroPM:</u> Limited relevance. Monitor potential links with chemicals policy.		X							
	Development of EU principles on sustainable raw materials <u>Relevance for ZeroPM:</u> Limited relevance. Monitor potential links with chemicals policy.		X							
	Setting up of the Industrial Forum to support the implementation of the Strategy <u>Relevance for ZeroPM:</u> Limited relevance. Monitor potential links with chemicals policy.					X	X			
	Launch of industrial alliances for relevant industrial ecosystems, e.g. European Raw Materials Alliance <u>Relevance for ZeroPM:</u> Limited relevance. Monitor potential links with chemicals policy.					X	X			
	Co-creation of green and digital transition pathways for relevant ecosystems, starting with tourism and energy intensive industries.					X	X			

	Relevance for ZeroPM: Limited relevance. May be worth checking whether any initiatives are linked to chemicals, in particular in the industrial ecosystems that are large consumers of chemicals.										
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Appendix H: Pharmaceutical Strategy

Name(s) of the initiative/policy		Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe Pharmaceutical Strategy COM(2020) 761 final
Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM		<p>The Pharmaceutical Strategy was adopted in November 2020 as one of the components of the European Health Union, outlined in President von der Leyen’s 2020 State of the Union speech. The rationale of the Pharmaceutical Strategy is strongly linked to the Covid-19 pandemic, which has shown, as stated in the Strategy, vulnerabilities linked to ‘data availability, the supply of medicines or the availability of manufacturing capacities to adapt and support the production of medicines’. The primary objectives of the Pharmaceutical strategy are to ensure patients’ access to high-quality, safe, innovative and affordable medicines; support the competitiveness and innovation of the EU’s pharmaceutical industry; and reinforcing Europe’s autonomy and capacity to respond to crisis. The Strategy also establishes a link with the Green Deal and in particular with the Zero Pollution Action Plan’s objective of reaching a toxic-free environment through the reduction of the impact of pharmaceutical substances on the environment and the contribution of the pharmaceutical industry to EU’s climate neutrality.</p> <p>The Strategy is organised along four broad objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fulfilling unmet medical needs and ensuring accessibility and affordability of medicines • Supporting a competitive and innovative European pharmaceutical industry • Enhancing resilience - diversified and secure supply chains; environmentally sustainable pharmaceuticals; crisis preparedness and response mechanisms • Ensuring a strong EU voice globally <p>Relevance to ZeroPM:</p> <p>The Pharmaceutical Strategy places some focus on reducing the environmental impacts of pharmaceutical production and use, by taking action throughout the lifecycle of pharmaceuticals to reduce resource use, emissions and levels of pharmaceutical residues in the environment. It proposes in particular to revise the pharmaceutical legislation to strengthen the environmental risk assessment of pharmaceuticals. The Strategy takes a global approach to sustainability of pharmaceuticals, calling for actions at all steps of the lifecycle of pharmaceutical products. Actions proposed are mostly focused on prevention.</p>
Type of act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal • Others
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)	<p>The Pharmaceutical Strategy is organised around four general objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fulfilling unmet medical needs and ensuring accessibility and affordability of medicines • Supporting a competitive and innovative European pharmaceutical industry • Enhancing resilience - diversified and secure supply chains; environmentally sustainable pharmaceuticals; crisis preparedness and response mechanisms • Ensuring a strong EU voice globally

	Specific Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fulfilling unmet medical needs and ensuring accessibility and affordability of medicines <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Direct investments in research and development and innovation towards unmet medical needs – under this objective the Strategy addresses antimicrobial resistance and the need to introduce measures to restrict and optimise the use of antimicrobial medicines • Enhancing resilience <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ High quality, safe and environmentally sustainable medicines – under this objective, the Strategy addresses the need to reduce production, use and disposal of medicines, in particular as some ‘residues may have endocrine-disrupting potential and others may increase the risk of antimicrobial resistance’. It sets the specific objectives to minimise exposure to harmful residues, reduce pharmaceutical waste and improve waste management, promote innovation for ‘environmentally sustainable and climate-neutral pharmaceuticals and manufacturing’, using best available techniques, improve environmental risk assessment of pharmaceuticals and raise awareness of environmental risks at international level. Under this objective, the Strategy also aims to support Member State cooperation and capacity on inspections, promote good manufacturing practices, and analyse the regulatory impact of emerging new manufacturing methods, which may create challenges in terms of controls and inspections. 		
(Only actions linked to environmentally sustainable medicines and AMR have been included below)			Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development	Pilot innovative approaches to EU R&D and public procurement for antimicrobials and their alternatives aiming to provide pull incentives for novel antimicrobials by 2022		
		Promote investment and coordinate research, development, manufacturing, deployment and use for novel antibiotics as part of the new EU Health Emergency Response Authority, prior to the start of the authority’s operations preparatory action on AMR by 2021		
		Consider in the review of the pharmaceutical legislation to introduce measures to restrict and optimise the use of antimicrobial medicines. Explore new types of incentives for innovative antimicrobials by 2022		
	Policy-realignment	Review the framework on good manufacturing practice and encourage inspections of good manufacturing and distribution practice to improve compliance by 2022		
	Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation	Propose to revise the manufacturing and supply provisions in the pharmaceutical legislation to improve the transparency and reinforce oversight of the supply chain and clarify responsibilities to ensure overall environmental sustainability, safeguard the quality of medicines and ensure preparedness for new manufacturing technologies by 2022		
		Propose to revise the pharmaceutical legislation to strengthen the environmental risk assessment requirements and conditions of use for medicines, and take stock of the results of research under the innovative medicines initiative	X	WP6
	Raising awareness (consumers / citizens and non-consumers)	Propose non-legislative measures and optimise the use of existing regulatory tools to combat antimicrobial resistance, including harmonisation of product information, draft evidence-based guidance on existing and new diagnostics; promote the prudent use of antibiotics and communication to healthcare professionals and patients		
	Stakeholder cooperation	Work with the Member States to enhance their capacity to participate in international inspection and audit programme		
Engage with international partners through cooperation to ensure the quality and environmental sustainability of the active pharmaceutical ingredients imported from non-EU countries				

		Assess with Member States and EMA the feasibility of improving information in existing databases or linked repositories with regard to manufacturing sites, their use for products authorised in the EU and inspection status		
		Engage with Member States and stakeholders in developing best practices for decarbonising value chains		
	Financing	N/A		
	Other	Continue the implementation of the actions under the strategic approach to pharmaceuticals in the environment, including the environmentally safe disposal of medicines and reducing pack size and packaging		
Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		N/A		
Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		N/A		
Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		N/A		
Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback		SWD(2020) 286 final contains the synopsis report of consultations carried out during the adoption process of the Pharmaceutical Strategy (i.e. feedback on the Roadmap, online public consultation, stakeholder workshop and ad-hoc contributions). Limited feedback from stakeholders was gathered on sustainability aspects during the various consultation activities. In the feedback provided to the Roadmap, environmental concerns and technologies to replace animal testing in medicines testing were mentioned by healthcare respondents and citizens. In the online public consultation, actions most supported by respondents to limit the environmental impact of medicines were stricter disposal rules for unused medicines (42%) and cleaner manufacturing processes (35%), and stakeholders suggested other actions such as improvement of schemes for unused medicines, reutilisation of solvents and chemicals. Regarding AMR, over half of the respondents considered that a more prudent use of antimicrobials would be the action with the biggest impact and backed increased support for research on new antimicrobials or their alternatives.		
Challenges		No challenges related to sustainable medicines are clearly outlined in the Strategy.		
Proposed timeline		The Strategy was adopted in 2020. All measures proposed in the Strategy have short timeframe and should be completed by 2025 (2022 for measures linked to sustainable pharmaceuticals and AMR). There are no longer term targets (2030 or 2050). The Strategy states that the Commission will regularly report on the progress made but does not set a timeline for revision.		
Links		https://ec.europa.eu/health/medicinal-products/pharmaceutical-strategy-europe_en		
Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document		Directive 2001/83/EC on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use Regulation (EC) No 726/2004 laying down Union procedures for the authorisation and supervision of medicinal products for human use and establishing a European Medicines Agency		
Links to other ZeroPM-WPs		WP6 – the Strategy proposes to revise the pharmaceutical legislation to strengthen the environmental risk assessment of pharmaceuticals.		
Notes				

Table for further analysis of actions/measures with relevance to ZeroPM:

Actions, Sub-actions and Relevance to ZeroPM		Subcategories:							Prioritize	Remediate
		Research & Development	Policy-realignment	Tightening and re-formation of relevant legislation	Raising awareness (consumers)	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Stakeholder co-operation	Financing		
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Propose to revise the pharmaceutical legislation to strengthen the environmental risk assessment requirements and conditions of use for medicines, and take stock of the results of research under the innovative medicines initiative <u>Relevance for ZeroPM:</u> potential for better assessment of persistence, mobility and toxicity in risk assessment of pharmaceuticals.			X						

Appendix I: Renovation Wave for Europe

Name(s) of the initiative/policy		A Renovation Wave for Europe - greening our buildings, creating jobs, improving lives Renovation Wave COM(2020) 662 final (complemented by SWD(2020) 550 final)
Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM		<p>The Renovation Wave Communication was adopted in October 2020. Its main objective is to increase the energy efficiency and reduce the climate impact of buildings in view of contributing to the 55% emission reduction target by 2030 and climate neutrality objective by 2050 set the Green Deal and Climate Target Plan. It also aims to foster growth and jobs in the construction sector and to tackle energy poverty, and is in this respect strongly linked to the Recovery Plan, which supports renovation of buildings. It identifies the following priority areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addressing energy poverty and worst-performing buildings • Public buildings and social infrastructure • Decarbonising heating and cooling <p>The Circular Economy Action Plan and the Industrial Strategy included the adoption of a sustainable built environment strategy, which, according to the CEAP, was supposed to ,ensure coherence across the relevant policy areas such as climate, energy and resource efficiency, management of construction and demolition waste, accessibility, digitalisation and skills'. This strategy has not been adopted so far (and may not be adopted at all¹), partially because, according to the Commission, many of the actions planned in this strategy have been frontloaded in the Renovation Wave Communication and the Recovery Plan². Although the Renovation Wave Communication does not fully include the elements that were planned to be covered by the sustainable built environment strategy, it is at the moment the only strategy deriving from the Green Deal that addresses the construction sector.</p> <p>Relevance for ZeroPM: Although the Renovation Wave Communication lists as one of the 'key principles for building renovation' the integration of 'high health and environmental standards' including 'ensuring high air quality, good water management, disaster prevention and protection against climate-related hazards, removal of and protection against harmful substances such as asbestos and radon, fire and seismic safety', it does not further address the presence of hazardous substances such as PFAS in construction products and does not establish a link with the actions under the Chemicals strategy. As it may remain the only strategy addressing sustainability in the construction sector, the missing link with the Chemicals Strategy constitutes a policy gap.</p>
Type of act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal • Others
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribute to the 55% emission reduction target by 2030 set by the 2030 Climate Target Plan through energy efficiency gains in the construction sector – i.e. reduce buildings' greenhouse gas emissions by 60%, their final energy consumption by 14% and energy consumption for heating and cooling by 18%. • Provide an economic stimulus to the construction sector and create green jobs in the construction sector

¹ Pickstone, S. 'Commission quietly shelves strategy on sustainable built environment', [ENDS Europe](#), 5 August 2021.

² Legislative train schedule – A European Green Deal: [Strategy for a sustainable built environment](#).

	Specific Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least double the annual energy renovation rate of residential and non-residential buildings by 2030, i.e. 35 million building units renovated by 2030, and maintain the increased rate and depth of renovation post-2030 to reach climate neutrality by 2050 Foster comprehensive and integrated renovation interventions Address energy poverty and worst performing buildings Decarbonising heating and cooling Create 160 000 green jobs in the construction sector Creating a sustainable built environment integrating circularity principles, high health and environmental standards – including the protection against harmful substances 		
			Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development	N/A		
	Policy-realignment	N/A		
	Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation	N/A		
	Raising awareness (consumers)	N/A		
	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	N/A		
	Stakeholder cooperation	N/A		
	Financing	N/A		
	Other	N/A		
Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		N/A		
Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		N/A		
Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		N/A		
Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback		N/A		
Challenges		N/A		
Proposed timeline		The Communication was adopted in 2020. It does not contain a timeline for revision.		

Links	https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/renovation-wave_en#the-new-european-bauhaus
Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document	CEAP
Links to other ZeroPM-WPs	N/A
Notes	N/A

Appendix J: Soil Strategy 2030

<p>Name(s) of the initiative/policy</p>	<p>EU Soil Strategy for 2030. Reaping the benefits of healthy soils for people, food, nature and climate Soil Strategy COM(2021) 699 final (complemented by SWD(2021) 323 final)</p>
<p>Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM</p>	<p>The EU Soil Strategy was adopted in November 2021. It replaces the Thematic Strategy for Soil Protection, from 2006 and sets out a framework and concrete measures for protecting, restoring, and sustainably using soils and identifies actions to mobilise the necessary societal engagement and financial resources, shared knowledge, sustainable practices and monitoring to reach the formulated objectives. Healthy soils are seen as a key solution to contribute to tackling the following four major societal challenges:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Achieving climate neutrality and becoming resilient to climate change, 2. Developing a clean and circular (bio)economy, 3. Reversing biodiversity loss for human, animal, and plant health, and 4. Halting desertification and reversing land degradation. <p>The actions identified by the Soil Strategy fall under the following broad objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making sustainable soil management the new normal • Preventing desertification • Preventing soil pollution • Restoring degraded soils and remediating contaminated sites <p>In addition, actions are defined to create an enabling environment for the implementation of the measures; these include actions to set up new, (digital) tools and processes to support the assessment, monitoring and effective management of soil, promote and finance research, innovation, and sustainable soil management practices as well as facilitate and encourage soil literacy and societal engagement for healthy soils.</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM: The Soil Strategy identifies a list of actions related to soil pollution. The Strategy takes an approach that combines prevention and remediation, with a focus on prevention – the Strategy recognizes that ‘contamination should be prevented at source as a priority’ but also has clear ambitions with regards to the remediation of contaminated sites. It places some emphasis on the identification and prioritisation of soil pollutants of concerns and improving the consideration of soil quality and soil biodiversity in EU risk assessments for chemicals, food and feed additives, pesticides, fertilisers. The Soil Strategy establishes links with the Chemicals Strategy – the ‘one substance, one assessment’ initiative and a number of actions listed under the Chemicals Strategy, such as the REACH restriction on PFAS.</p>
<p>Type of act</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal • Others
	<p>General objective(s) The Soil Strategy defines an overarching goal for 2050: ‘By 2050, all EU soil ecosystems are in healthy condition and thus more resilient. By then, protection, sustainable use and restoration of soil has become the norm. As a key solution, healthy soils contribute to address our big challenges of</p>

Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		achieving climate neutrality and becoming resilient to climate change, developing a clean and circular (bio)economy, reversing biodiversity loss, safeguarding human health, halting desertification and reversing land degradation'		
	Specific Objectives	<p><u>By 2030</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combat desertification, restore degraded land and soil, including land affected by desertification, drought, and floods, and strive to achieve a land degradation-neutral world (Sustainable Development Goal 15.3) • Significant areas of degraded and carbon-rich ecosystems, including soils, are restored. • Achieve an EU net greenhouse gas removal of 310 million tonnes CO2 equivalent per year for the land use, land use change and forestry (LULUCF) sector • Reach good ecological and chemical status in surface waters and good chemical and quantitative status in groundwater by 2027. • Reduce nutrient losses by at least 50% (resulting in the reduction of use of fertilisers by at least 20%), the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% and the use of more hazardous pesticides by 50% by 2030. • Significant progress has been made in the remediation of contaminated sites. <p><u>By 2050</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reach no net land take. • Soil pollution should be reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to human health and natural ecosystems and respect the boundaries our planet can cope with, thus creating a toxic-free environment. • Achieve a climate-neutral Europe and, as the first step, aim to achieve land-based climate neutrality in the EU by 2035. • Achieve for EU a climate-resilient society, fully adapted to the unavoidable impacts of climate change by 2050. <p><u>Relevance to Zero PM</u> Links with the objectives of the Zero Pollution Action Plan to create a toxic free environment.</p>		
			Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
Actions/Measures for "prevent and reduce" & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development	Improve and harmonize the consideration of soil quality and soil biodiversity in EU risk assessments for chemicals, food and feed additives, pesticides, fertilizers, etc. It will do this under the 'one substance one assessment' initiative and in collaboration with the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the EEA, JRC and the Member States	X	WP6
		In cooperation with Member States and stakeholders, facilitate a dialogue and knowledge exchange on the risk assessment methodologies for soil contamination and identify best practices.	X	WP6
		Work towards integrating a pollution module in the future LUCAS in 2022 soil survey to better understand and map the issue of diffuse soil contamination in the EU, and produce a clean soil outlook as part of the integrated zero pollution monitoring and outlook framework	X	WP7
	Policy realignment	Evaluate the Sewage Sludge Directive by 2022	X	WP7
		Review the contaminant limits for EU fertilising products by July 2026 as part of the general review of that regulation	X	WP7
		By 2023 evaluate the Environmental Liability Directive, including with regard to the definition of land damage and the role of financial security	X	
		By 2022, revise the Industrial Emissions Directive	X	WP7

	Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation	Revise the Directive on the Sustainable Use of Pesticides by 2022	X	WP7
		Restrict intentionally used micro-plastics under the REACH Regulation and develop measures on the unintentional release of microplastics by 2022	X	WP2 WP5
		Restriction under REACH on all non-essential uses of the PFAS preventing their emission to the environment including soil	X	WP2 WP4 WP5
		Develop a policy framework on bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics by 2022	X	WP4 WP5
		By July 2024, adopt biodegradability criteria for certain polymers, such as coating agents and agricultural mulch films under the EU Fertilising Products Regulation	X	WP4 WP5
		Propose by 2023 a legislative framework for an EU sustainable food system, as indicated in the Farm to Fork Strategy.	X	
	Raising awareness (consumers / citizens)	N/A		
	Raising awareness (non consumers)	Prepare, in consultation with Member States and stakeholders, a set of sustainable soil management practices, including regenerative farming in line with agro-ecological principles, adapted to the wide variability of soil ecosystems and types, and identify unsustainable soil management practices		
		In the context of the CAP and in close cooperation with the Member States, continue the dissemination of successful sustainable soil and nutrient management solutions, including through the national rural networks of the rural development program, farm advisory services and AKIS, and the European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI)		
		Encourage and support Member States to set-up farm sustainability tools for nutrients (FaST), as part of the farm advisory services under the new CAP. Such tools will provide to farmers recommendations about the use of fertilizers, compliant with existing legislation and based on available data and knowledge		
	Stakeholder cooperation	Create with the Member States a network of excellence of practitioners, and an inclusive network of SSM ambassadors, including on regenerative and organic agriculture, connecting stakeholders beyond academia and agricultural actors. For this they will build on the work of Living Labs and Lighthouses of the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe'		
		Promote SSM through voluntary commitments between actors in the food system under the EU Code of Conduct on Responsible Food Businesses and Marketing practices		
	Financing	Through Horizon Europe and in particular the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe', the Commission will provide funding to research solutions to address soil degradation and pilot innovative technologies for decontamination	X	WP7
		Continue providing substantial funding to i) research solutions to increase soil biodiversity; ii) address soil degradation; iii) pilot innovative technologies for decontamination.	X	WP7
		Publish a guide in 2022 with an overview of EU funding opportunities available for the protection, sustainable management and restoration of soils, once all priorities and focus areas for 2021-2027 have been clearly defined.	X	
	Other	N/A		

Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	By 2024, develop an EU priority list for contaminants of major and/or emerging concern that pose significant risks for European soil quality, and for which vigilance and priority action at European and national level is needed.	X	WP6 WP7
Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	As part of the impact assessment for a Soil Health Law, the Commission will consider options for proposing legally binding provisions to i) identify contaminated sites, ii) set up an inventory and register of those sites and iii) remediate the sites that pose a significant risk to human health and the environment by 2050	X	WP7
Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)			
Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback	<p>SDW 2021 323 contains the synopsis report of consultations carried out during the adoption process of the Soil Strategy.</p> <p><u>General remarks:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Classic divide between public authorities / NGOs and industry representatives (mainly agriculture) on the adoption of an EU regulatory framework on soil – public authorities recognise its value, industry not in favour. Soil pollution does not seem to be very much addressed in the contribution from stakeholders (although that could be because the synopsis report is not detailed). <p><u>Feedback on Roadmap:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil contamination was an important theme raised by governmental organisations and agencies Industry representatives (bioeconomy, circular economy, energy, water, buildings sectors) were in favour of ‘setting quality standards for soil amendments and fertilizers, and rules for the reuse of soils that have been contaminated by former industrial activities (such as the Germany model)’, and backed the adoption at EU level of homogenous criteria for soil decontamination. Stakeholders in agriculture and minerals sectors tended to ‘reject EU binding regulations’ (such as common EU soil standards) and ‘deny the trans-boundary effects of soil degradation’. <p><u>Open Public consultation:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The soil remediation sector was underrepresented in the respondents (agriculture and environment / nature protection were the main sectors represented). Large majority (around 70%) of respondents considered that diffuse contamination (e.g. due to overuse of pesticides, nutrient pollution from excess use of fertilizers, microplastics, air depositions of pollutants) should be better addressed at EU level; and around 50% considered that local contamination by industrial and waste management activities’ should be better addressed at EU level Question on criteria to ascertain soil health proposed by the experts in the context of the Horizon Europe Mission ‘A Soil Deal for Europe’: (1) Presence of pollutants, excess nutrients and salts in the soil, (2) soil organic carbon content, (3) soil structure including medium soil density and absence of soil sealing or soil erosion, (4) soil biodiversity, (5) soil nutrients and acidity (pH), (6) vegetation cover, (7) landscape heterogeneity, (8) forest cover. The majority of respondents (60%) considered the criteria appropriate, about 35% of them consider the list incomplete. Among the additional criteria proposed were chemical criteria (nutrient availability and deficiency, nutrient balance, cation exchange capacity, heavy metals such as lead, waste residues, radioactivity) <p><u>Position papers joined to OPC</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public authorities raised concerns related to soil pollution and contamination and considered the EU should ‘provide a harmonized soil pollution risk assessment approach’. NGOs underlined that prevention is better and more cost-effective than remediation The need to address soil pollution was also raised by industry stakeholders. 		
Challenges	<u>Prevention</u>		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of data: According to the Soil Strategy, ‘the necessary data on the hazard and environmental fate of and exposure to such chemicals and the resulting risk they pose for soil quality and organisms are often lacking’. <p>Remediation of contaminated soils:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contaminated sites require remediation with often complex and costly techniques (although in certain cases low-cost, bioremediation techniques have been shown to be effective), which may slow down remediation ambition Non-harmonised legal framework and practices across Member States: some MS have soil contamination and remediation legislation in place, some do not; some have a register of contaminated sites, some do not; reporting on progress in managing soil contamination is currently voluntary, irregular and based on a changing methodology, different national definitions, screening values and risk assessment methodologies. This should be addressed by the upcoming Soil Health Law, but the disparities between Member States will certainly be a challenge in the short term. A common approach is lacking in the EU regarding historical or orphan contaminated sites Significant lack of data and knowledge on soil contamination: According to the Soil Strategy, ‘only a very small fraction of all chemicals is screened in the standard soil analysis, and even fewer substances are regulated under national legislation with contaminant thresholds’. As a result, most chemicals remain undetected in the soil. In addition, the Soil Strategy indicates that ‘the fate, behaviour and (eco)toxicological effects of contaminants of emerging concern are not yet well understood, especially for lower orders of soil biota’.
Proposed timeline	Strategy adopted in November 2021. Planned review: not stated in Strategy.
Links	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/eu-soil-strategy-2030_en
Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document	REACH Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive Fertilising Products Regulation
Links to other ZeroPM-WPs	<p>WP2 /WP4 Links made with PFAS restriction under REACH</p> <p>WP5 Actions on certain polymers (microplastics, biodegradable plastics, biodegradability criteria under Fertilisers Regulation); links made with restrictions on groups of substances (microplastics, PFAS)</p> <p>WP6 Focus of the strategy on better integration soil quality and soil biodiversity in EU risk assessments for chemicals, food and feed additives, pesticides, fertilisers, under ‘one substance, one assessment’ initiative and harmonisation of methods.</p> <p>WP7 The Soil Strategy contains a number of measures related to soil remediation – in particular initiatives to map the issue of diffuse soil contamination in the EU and the development of an EU priority list for soil contaminants European may be of interest for WP 7.</p>
Notes	

Table for further analysis of actions/measures with relevance to ZeroPM:

Actions, Sub-actions and Relevance to ZeroPM		Subcategories:								Prioritize	Remediate
		Research & Development	Policy-realignment	Tightening and re-formation of relevant legislation	Raising awareness (consumers)	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Stakeholder co-operation	Financing	Other		
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	<p>Improve and harmonize the consideration of soil quality and soil biodiversity in EU risk assessments for chemicals, food and feed additives, pesticides, fertilizers, etc. It will do this under the ‘one substance one assessment’ initiative and in collaboration with the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the EEA, JRC and the Member States</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Link to WP6.</p>	X								X	
	<p>In cooperation with Member States and stakeholders, facilitate a dialogue and knowledge exchange on the risk assessment methodologies for soil contamination and identify best practices.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Limited relevance for ZeroPM. Potential link to WP6.</p>	X					X				
	<p>Work towards integrating a pollution module in the future LUCAS in 2022 soil survey to better understand and map the issue of diffuse soil contamination in the EU, and produce a clean soil outlook as part of the integrated zero pollution monitoring and outlook framework.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> could be interesting data for WP7.</p>	X									
	<p>Evaluate the Sewage Sludge Directive by 2022</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> linked to use of sludge in agriculture, and possible chemicals contamination that could prevent their use. Sludge can be contaminated with PMT/vPvM substances from wastewater.</p>		X								
	<p>By 2023 evaluate the Environmental Liability Directive, including with regard to the definition of land damage and the role of financial security</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Limited relevance for ZeroPM. Link to decontamination of polluted sites.</p>		X								
	<p>By 2022, revise the Industrial Emissions Directive</p>			X							

	<p>Revision ongoing. COM Proposal for a Directive adopted in April 2022.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> The proposal intends to clarify the rules that apply to the indirect release of polluting substances into water through urban wastewater treatment plants, including PFAS, microplastics and pharmaceuticals. The review of the BREF should take into account the identification of substances of concern under EU water legislation (ground and surface water watchlists, and other substances posing a significant risk to or via the aquatic environment).</p>									
	<p>Revise the Directive on the Sustainable Use of Pesticides by 2022</p> <p><u>Relevance for ZeroPM:</u> the revision of the SUPD should contribute to the 50% reduction target for pesticide use. The revision should aim to reduce the use and risk of pesticides containing more hazardous active substances; increase the uptake of less hazardous and non-chemical alternatives for pest control.</p>			X						
	<p>Restriction under REACH on all non-essential uses of the PFAS preventing their emission to the environment including soil</p> <p>Restriction dossier expected in January 2023.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> application of group approach to regulating PFAS; reduction of PFAS use in consumer products.</p>			X						
	<p>By 2024, develop an EU priority list for contaminants of major and/or emerging concern that pose significant risks for European soil quality, and for which vigilance and priority action at European and national level is needed.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> possible integration of PMT/vPvM substances in the priority list.</p>							X		X
	<p>As part of the impact assessment for a Soil Health Law, the Commission will consider options for proposing legally binding provisions to i) identify contaminated sites, ii) set up an inventory and register of those sites and iii) remediate the sites that pose a significant risk to human health and the environment by 2050</p> <p><u>Relevance for ZeroPM:</u> Possible link with WP7.</p>							X		X
	<p>Through Horizon Europe and in particular the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe', the Commission will provide funding to research solutions to address soil degradation and pilot innovative technologies for decontamination</p>									X

	<u>Relevance for ZeroPM</u> : Possible link with WP7.											
	Continue providing substantial funding to i) research solutions to increase soil biodiversity; ii) address soil degradation; iii) pilot innovative technologies for decontamination .											
	<u>Relevance for ZeroPM</u> : Possible link with WP7.											

Appendix K: Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy

Name(s) of the initiative/policy		COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS on a new approach for a sustainable blue economy in the EU Transforming the EU's Blue Economy for a Sustainable Future COM(2021) 240 final		
Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM		<p>The communication lays the foundations of transforming from blur growth to a sustainable blue economy. A link is made to the EU Green Deal and the transformation of the economy as well as the recovery plan for Europe. The communication integrates ocean policy into Europes new economic policy in order to achieve the transformation set out in the Green Deal. The communication is divided up in to three main sections related to transforming blue economy value chains, supporting the development of a sustainable blue economy and creating condition for sustainable governance.</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM The communication highlights the importance of clean oceans – free of chemicals. The communication links to the EU action plan on zero pollution The circular economy and waste prevention is in focus though microplastics and other forms of chemical pollution are discussed. Chemical pesticides are highlighted as one of the main sources of pollution. There is a small link to ZeroPM through this and chemical pesticides are specifically mentioned. These substances are not covered by REACH (though many are likely PM substances).</p>		
Type of act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal • Others 		
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)	The objectives are related to the three sections of the document: transforming blue economy value chains, supporting the development of a sustainable blue economy and creating conditions for sustainable governance. Transforming blue economy value chains includes objectives related to climate neutrality and zero pollution, circular economy and preventing waste, biodiversity and investing in nature, coastal resilience and responsible food systems. The sustainable blue economy will be developed by focusing on ocean knowledge, research and innovation, investment and blue skills and jobs. A sustainable governance will be developed by focusing on maritime spatial planning, citizen engagement and ocean literacy, sea basins, regional cooperation and support for coastal regions, maritime security and promoting a sustainable blue economy abroad.		
	Specific Objectives	<p>Circular economy and preventing waste</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take action to halve plastic litter at sea, nutrient loss into the sea and the use and risk from chemical pesticides 		
			Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development	The candidate mission “Healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters” will aim to reduce the disturbance of marine ecosystems, regenerate marine and freshwater ecosystems, tackle biodiversity loss and pollution and promote blue economy solutions to become climate neutral		
		The new European partnership for a climate-neutral, sustainable and productive blue economy, due to start in 2023, will take the shape of a public initiative co-funded by the EU, national governments and national research funding agencies		

		The new InvestEU programme will be highly relevant for maritime transport, ports and offshore renewable energies, as well as for biodiversity conservation and restoration, sustainable aquaculture and ocean observation.		
	Policy-realignment	Start a review of the Maritime Strategy Framework Directive in 2021 and, based on the outcome, possibly revise the Directive by 2023		
	Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation	The Commission is considering revising the ship source pollution directive		
	Raising awareness (consumers)	N/A		
	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	N/A		
	Stakeholder cooperation	N/A		
	Financing	N/A		
	Other	N/A		
	Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	None unless a specific PMT/vPvM substance of interest is put in to focus (though unlikely)		
	Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	None unless a specific PMT/vPvM substance of interest is put in to focus (though unlikely)		
	Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	None unless a specific PMT/vPvM substance of interest is put in to focus (though unlikely)		
	Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback	None		
	Challenges	None mentioned		
	Proposed timeline	Communication from 2021		
	Links	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52021DC0240&from=EN		
	Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document	Single us plastic directive (semi relevant) EU circular economy action plan Farm to fork strategy		
	Links to other ZeroPM-WPs	WP2: WP4: WP5: Tenuous at best. WP6: WP7: WP8:		
	Notes			

Appendix L: Sustainable Textile Strategy

Name(s) of the initiative/policy		EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles Sustainable Textile Strategy COM(2022) 141 final (complemented by an annex)
Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM		<p>The Sustainable Textile Strategy was adopted in March 2022. It takes a global approach to transforming the textile value chain from production to consumption and recycling of textile waste towards increased sustainability and circularity. It also aims to ensure that the textile industry recovers from the COVID-19 crisis. It places a strong focus on sustainable product design, the integration of circularity principles (reuse, repair, recycle) in the textile value chain, and Extended Producer Responsibility rules for textiles, as well as other economic incentives to make products more sustainable. The Sustainable Textile Strategy explicitly links to the Chemicals Strategy through the commitment to ‘support industry to substitute as much as possible and otherwise minimise the substances of concern in textile products placed on the EU market’. It is also strongly linked to other Green Deal strategies such as the CEAP through the clear focus on integrating circularity principles and increasing preparation for reuse and recycling, and the Industrial Strategy, as textile is one of the industrial ecosystems selected in the Industrial Strategy.</p> <p>Relevance for ZeroPM</p> <p>The Sustainable Textile Strategy specifically addresses the presence of substances of concern in textile and plans for the adoption of ecodesign requirements linked to chemicals (without specifying which substances require action). It places strong focus on prevention and in particular on the introduction of safety, sustainability and circularity principles in product design. It links up to other initiatives promoting the safe and sustainable by design approach (CEAP, Chemicals Strategy). It also makes use of various market tools to foster transition such as labelling, information to consumer, GPP etc.</p>
Type of act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal • Others
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)	The Sustainable Textile Strategy defines an overarching goal for 2030 : ‘By 2030 textile products placed on the EU market are long-lived and recyclable, to a great extent made of recycled fibres, free of hazardous substances and produced in respect of social rights and the environment. Consumers benefit longer from high quality affordable textiles, fast fashion is out of fashion, and economically profitable re-use and repair services are widely available. In a competitive, resilient and innovative textiles sector, producers take responsibility for their products along the value chain, including when they become waste. The circular textiles ecosystem is thriving, driven by sufficient capacities for innovative fibre-to-fibre recycling, while the incineration and landfilling of textiles is reduced to the minimum’
	Specific Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving product design in terms of durability, reusability, reparability, recyclability, recycled fibre content, and reduce the presence of hazardous substances • Stopping the destruction of unsold or returned textiles • Reducing microplastics pollution • Improving consumer information and ensuring accuracy of green claims • Apply further extended producer responsibility and boost reuse and recycling of textile waste • Creating the enabling conditions for a sustainable textiles value chain – promoting alternative business and consumption models, supporting research, innovation and investments, developing skills

• Supporting a sustainable textiles value chains globally – including due diligence and addressing exports of textile waste			Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development	Horizon Europe calls to support R&D in textiles (2021-2027)	x	
	Policy-realignment	Review of the Best Available Techniques Reference Document for the Textiles Industry (2022)	x	WP2 WP4
		Launch of work on the setting of preparing for re-use and recycling targets for textiles (2022)	x	
		Adoption of common industrial technology roadmap on circularity (2022)	x	WP2 WP4
		Work on skills for the textiles ecosystem within the European Skills Agenda and the renewed European Alliance for Apprenticeships (as of 2022)		
	Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation	Mandatory performance requirements for the environmental sustainability of textile products under the new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (by 2024)	x	WP2 WP4
		Digital Product Passport for textiles with information requirements on environmental sustainability under the new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (by 2024)	x	
		Mandatory requirements concerning green public procurement and Member State incentives under the new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (by 2024)	x	WP4
		Disclosure of the number of discarded products by large enterprises and their subsequent treatment, and measures on banning the destruction of unsold textiles under the new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (by 2024)		
		Empowering consumers in the green transition and ensuring the reliability of green claims (by 2022)	x	
		Review of the Textile Labelling Regulation and considering the introduction of a digital label (by 2023)	x	
		Revision of the EU Ecolabel criteria for textiles and footwear (by 2024)	x	WP4
		Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules for apparel and footwear (2024)		
		Initiative to address the unintentional release of microplastics from textile products (2022)	x	WP4 WP7
		Extended Producer Responsibility requirements for textiles with eco-modulation of fees and measures to promote the waste hierarchy for textile waste (2023)	x	WP4
	Criteria for circular manufacturing of apparel under the Taxonomy Regulation (2022)	x		
	Raising awareness (consumers)			
Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Guidance on supporting uptake and partnerships for the circular economy between social enterprises and other actors, including in the textile sector (2022)			
	Guidance on circular economy business models featuring the textile sector (2024)			

		Launch of #ReFashionNow (as of 2022)		
	Stakeholder cooperation	Launch of the Transition Pathway for the Textiles Ecosystem (2022)	x	WP4
		Strengthening of market surveillance through cooperation between enforcement authorities and launch of EU Toolbox against counterfeiting (as of 2022)		
	Financing	New European Bauhaus to support sustainable textiles (as of 2022)		
	Other	Enforcing the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive in the textile sector (as of 2023)		
Enforcing the restrictions on exports of textile waste outside the OECD and developing criteria for distinguishing waste from second-hand textile products (as of 2023)				
Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback				
Challenges	The Strategy highlights a few challenges for the textile value chain that may have an impact on the success of the Strategy: the complexity and diversity of the textile value chain with many actors and subsidiaries, usually outside the EU; a linear business model, which 'often does not put quality, durability and recyclability as priorities for the design and manufacturing of apparel'; consumer habits linked to overconsumption; the economic situation of the sector, recovering from the pandemic period, characterised by 'drops in demand, disruptions of value chains and price hikes'.			
Proposed timeline	The Strategy was adopted in 2022. Its objectives should be achieved by 2030 and actions proposed in the action plan should be started by 2024. The Strategy does not set a timeline for revision.			
Links	https://ec.europa.eu/environment/strategy/textiles-strategy_en https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12822-EU-strategy-for-sustainable-textiles_en			
Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document	REACH Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Ecodesign Directive and Regulations Proposal for an Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation Industrial Emissions Directive / BAT & BREF EU Industrial Strategy CEAP Waste Framework Directive and other EU waste legislation Ecolabel Regulation Green Public Procurement			
Links to other ZeroPM-WPs	WP2: the adoption of environmental sustainability requirements for textile products under Ecodesign and the review of the BAT may be of interest (i.e. safe and sustainable by design approach). WP4: the adoption of environmental sustainability requirements for textile products under Ecodesign and the review of the BAT may be of interest (i.e. safe and sustainable by design approach). The Strategy makes use of various market tools to foster transition such as labelling, information to consumer, GPP, and sets up partnerships with industry for transition to a more sustainable value chain (unclear for now whether these will address chemicals).			

Notes	WP7: the Strategy links up to the initiative to address unintentional release of microplastics in the environment and aims to address it through the binding design requirements to be introduced under the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation.
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Table for further analysis of actions/measures with relevance to ZeroPM:

Actions, Sub-actions and Relevance to ZeroPM		Subcategories:							Prioritize	Remediate
		Research & Development	Policy-realignment	Tightening and re-formation of relevant legislation	Raising awareness (consumers)	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Stakeholder co-operation	Financing		
Actions/Measures for "prevent and reduce" & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Mandatory performance requirements for the environmental sustainability of textile products under the new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (by 2024) <u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> These requirements are defined in the Strategy as 'binding product-specific ecodesign requirements to increase textiles' performance in terms of durability, reusability, reparability, fibre-to-fibre recyclability and mandatory recycled fibre content, to minimise and track the presence of substances of concern and to reduce the adverse impacts on climate and the environment'. The Strategy further specifies that the development of these criteria will 'support industry to substitute as much as possible and otherwise minimise the substances of concern in textile products placed on the EU market, as announced in the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability'			X						
	Digital Product Passport for textiles with information requirements on environmental sustainability under the new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (by 2024) <u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> will include mandatory information requirements on circularity and other key environmental aspects – the Strategy does not specify which key environmental aspects will be covered, so the actual relevance of the measure is unclear. But it may cover information related to chemicals content. In such case, this would be indirectly a market transition tool as better information to consumers may shift consumption towards more sustainable products.			X	X					

	<p>Mandatory requirements concerning green public procurement and Member State incentives under the new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (by 2024)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> The Strategy does not specify the nature and content of the revision so the relevance of the measure is unclear. But it may include criteria related to the restrictions of hazardous chemicals. In such case, this would be indirectly a market transition tool, as it may shift public purchase towards more sustainable products.</p>			X						
	<p>Empowering consumers in the green transition and ensuring the reliability of green claims (by 2022)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> the Empowering Consumers for the Green Transition includes the amendment of the Unfair Commercial Practices Directive and stricter provisions for green claims and use of sustainability labels. In addition, the Green Claims Initiative intends to define minimum criteria for all types of environmental claims. This may include criteria related to safety and chemicals content. In such case, this would be indirectly a market transition tool as better information to consumers may shift consumption towards more sustainable products.</p>			X	X					
	<p>Review of the Textile Labelling Regulation and considering the introduction of a digital label (by 2023)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> will include mandatory disclosure of environmental information. The Strategy only refers to sustainability and circularity parameters' without specifying what will be covered, so the actual relevance of the measure is unclear. But it may cover information related to chemicals content. In such case, this would be indirectly a market transition tool as better information to consumers may shift consumption towards more sustainable products.</p>			X	X					
	<p>Revision of the EU Ecolabel criteria for textiles and footwear (by 2024)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> the EU Ecolabel criteria for Textile Products already contains criteria for the restrictions of hazardous chemicals. The revision may entail stricter criteria. According to the Strategy the Commission also intends to 'support its uptake among producers'. This would be indirectly a market transition tool as better information to consumers may shift consumption towards more sustainable products. This is also a way for producers to show off the quality of their products.</p>			X	X					
	<p>Initiative to address the unintentional release of microplastics from textile products (2022)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> the binding design requirements to be introduced under the</p>			X						

	<p>Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation will address the unintentional release of microplastics. In parallel (outside of this strategy), there will be a Commission initiative to address the unintentional release of microplastics in the environment. The Commission also intends to take other measures (in addition to product design) related to ‘manufacturing processes, pre-washing at industrial manufacturing plants, labelling and the promotion of innovative materials’ or ‘end-of-life textile waste treatment, and regulations for improved wastewater and sewage sludge treatment’.</p>									
	<p>Review of the Best Available Techniques Reference Document for the Textiles Industry (2022)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> the BREF for the Textile industry addresses processes such as fibre preparation, pretreatment (operations such as washing, bleaching, mercerisation), dyeing of fibres or textiles, printing and finishing. The Strategy links the revision of the BREF to the zero-pollution ambition, suggesting that the revision may target chemicals use and emissions.</p>		x							
	<p>Extended Producer Responsibility requirements for textiles with eco-modulation of fees and measures to promote the waste hierarchy for textile waste (2023)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> EPR aims to support waste prevention, preparation for reuse and recycling and promote the application of circularity principles in product design. The Strategy makes a link between chemicals use in products and recycling as hazardous substances may hamper the recycling of textile waste. Recycling may also be a source of pollution so EPR requirements are relevant.</p>			x						
	<p>Launch of work on the setting of preparing for re-use and recycling targets for textiles (2022)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> The Strategy makes a link between chemicals use in products and recycling as hazardous substances may hamper the recycling of textile waste. Chemicals use may be an important determinant in achieving the targets.</p>		x							
	<p>Launch of the Transition Pathway for the Textiles Ecosystem (2022)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> linked to the Industrial Strategy – transition pathways for relevant industrial ecosystems (collaborative tools / co-creation process with stakeholders for the transformation of the industrial ecosystems). Should lead to specific voluntary pledges such as commitments on circularity and circular business</p>					x				

	<p>models. To be determined whether this will also include specific actions on chemicals use.</p>									
	<p>Launch of #ReFashionNow (as of 2022)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Communication campaign, in the framework of the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, to mobilise designers, producers, retailers, advertisers and citizens in re-defining fashion. Also implemented through other initiatives, the European Bauhaus, the Sustainable Consumption Pledge or the European Year of Youth. Unclear now whether this might include some focus on safety and chemicals content.</p>				x	x	X			
	<p>Horizon Europe calls to support R&D in textiles</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> specific calls under Horizon Europe will be launched to scale up textile recycling capacities of the EU industry, increase fibre-to-fibre recycling and the uptake of recycled fibre content. There may be Horizon projects exploring relations between chemicals in products and recycling.</p>									
	<p>Adoption of common industrial technology roadmap on circularity</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> The Roadmap aims at streamlining industrial research and innovation, including on textile recycling. The content of the Roadmap is not further described in the Strategy. It may address relations between chemicals in products and recycling.</p>	x	x							
	<p>Criteria for circular manufacturing of apparel under the Taxonomy Regulation</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> The Strategy defines this action as the ‘adoption of technical screening criteria determining what constitutes a substantial contribution to circular economy in the manufacture of apparel under the Regulation on Taxonomy for Sustainable Investments, along with criteria regarding pollution from finishing of textiles’. The definition may include criteria related to chemical content as it has an impact on circularity.</p>			x			x			

Appendix M: Strategy for Plastics in a circular Economy

Name(s) of the initiative/policy		A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy COM(2018) 28 final (complemented by SWD(2018) 16 final)
Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM		<p>The European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy describes an EU-initiative that complements the original Circular Economy Action Plan from 2015 with an extended focus on plastics (including microplastics). In that regard, the document refers to circularity – with a focus on recyclability – in terms of design, production, use and discard of plastics, but also to plastic-induced environmental pollution and negative effects on health as well as measures to avoid them. In this context, the document tries to establish a strategic vision that covers the entire value chain.</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM:</p> <p>While the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy does offer quite some relevance linked to ZeroPMs goals, it is important to note, that a lot of its content is picked up by newer documents like the Circular Economy Action Plan and put into the European Green Deal framework. Aside from this, as the name suggests, the strategy covers plastics, which can be of interest in terms of persistent and mobile-substances under the right circumstances (e.g. if persistent and mobile additives are added to plastics). With that said, most of the actions will cover persistent and mobile substances only indirectly if at all. These – for the most part – aim at (plastic) waste streams, food contact materials and (chemical) contamination of recyclable materials.</p>
Type of act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication ✓ • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal • Others
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)	<p>The main objective of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy is to advance towards the presented “<i>Vision for Europe’s New Plastics Economy</i>” that rethinks and remodels the entire plastic value chain for more sustainability, circularity, climate-neutrality, new jobs, growth and innovation while curbing plastic (and micro-plastic) pollution and its adverse effects on health and the environment.</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM:</p> <p>The objectives of the action plan that are especially of relevance are those in terms of decontamination endeavors regarding plastic waste that is intended for recycling. The “<i>Vision for Europe</i>” aims at phasing out those substances that hamper recycling processes by cooperation of the plastics- and chemical-industry, but also by addressing the interface between chemical, product and waste legislation to improve traceability of (hazardous) substances to deal with the issue of legacy substances in recycled streams. In this context, the problems that are generated by using different additives (some of which can contain persistent and mobile substances) are also meant to be tackled.</p>
	Specific Objectives	<p>The “<i>Vision for Europe’s new plastics economy</i>” states some specific targets, the Commission is keen on achieving in the future. In addition, four specific objectives can be directly derived from the subitems of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy. These include the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improving the economics and quality of plastic recycling by bettering product design, boosting recycled content and enhancing the separate collection of plastic waste. This includes to shape incentives for producers to address design issues in regards to recycling- and reuse-needs, raise the demand for recycled plastic content by diminishing market insecurities and lowering barriers by actions like developing quality standards for sorted plastic waste, pledging campaigns or other forms of promotion. In addition, this objective contains the endeavor of

		<p>financing research projects (e.g. Horizon 2020) to identify contaminants and to figure out ways to decontaminate plastic waste that is intended for recycling. This – depending on the kind of contamination – might be of relevance for ZeroPM as well.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Curbing plastic waste and littering by reducing plastic waste generation in general (especially of single-use plastics and overpackaging) and decouple plastic waste generation from growth. In addition, decreasing leakages into the environment (e.g. sea-based sources of marine litter), making sure waste is handled adequately, assessing the effectiveness of compostable and biodegradable plastics and establishing and providing clear and correct information for consumers, so that they can make informed choices about plastics, are further specific goals. This objective also intends to tackle the problem of microplastics (in terms of better understanding the impacts, origins and routes of microplastic as well as preventing it from entering the seas, our drinking water, air and food) and plans to increase monitoring activities as well as complement the beforementioned by retrieval of plastics already floating in the oceans along with developing new technologies for remediation. In this context the document aims for all European cities to be much cleaner in the future. 3. Driving innovation and investment (private and public) toward circular solutions by creating, enabling and promoting a functioning investment and innovation framework for plastics. This includes the development of alternative business models, new technologies (e.g. fully biodegradable materials in natural environments or digital watermarking-options) and concepts like the extended producer responsibility (EPR). In addition, financing research about tracing and removing hazardous substances from recycled plastics is planned for this objective and might be of interest for ZeroPM. 4. Harnessing global action by assuming a leading global position and engaging with bilateral and multilateral initiatives on plastic and focusing on key regions while advancing the 2030 SDGs. This includes international trade and international projects and conventions that support the establishment of sound waste prevention and management systems. <p>Specific targets constituted in the document under the “Vision for Europe’s new plastics economy”:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By 2025 (and as a result of the EU pledging campaign) ten million ton of recycled plastics shall find their way into new products on the EU market • By 2030, all plastics packaging placed on the EU market is either reusable or can be recycled in a cost-effective manner • By 2030, more than half of plastics waste generated in Europe is recycled. Separate collection of plastics waste reaches very high levels. Recycling of plastics packaging waste achieves levels comparable with those of other packaging materials • By 2030, sorting and recycling capacity has increased fourfold since 2015, leading to the creation of 200.000 new jobs, spread all across Europe • Phasing out exports of poorly sorted plastic wastes • Recycled plastics become an increasingly valuable feedstock for industries in the EU and abroad • Substances that hamper recycling processes will be phased out. Because of: Cooperation between plastics and chemical industry • Establish a market for recycled and innovative plastics with clear growth perspectives. Increase demand for recycled plastics in EU fourfold. More revenues streams and more jobs accordingly • Reduce Europe’s dependence on fossil fuels and lower CO²-emissions according to the Paris Agreement • Develop more sustainable materials/alternatives feedstocks for plastic production/use • Europe confirms leadership in sorting and recycling equipment and technologies. Rising exports in lockstep with global demand for more sustainable ways of processing end-of-life-plastics
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			Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
Actions/Measures for "prevent and reduce" & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development	Q1 2018 onwards: Follow-up to COM (2018) 32 "Communication on the implementation of the circular economy package: options to address the interface between chemical, product and waste legislation": improve the traceability of chemicals and address the issue of legacy substances in recycled streams	X	WP5
		Ongoing: As regards food-contact materials: swift finalization of pending authorization procedures for plastics recycling processes, better characterization of contaminants and introduction of monitoring system	X	WP5/6/7
		2018: Development of quality standards for sorted plastics waste and recycled plastics in cooperation with the European Standardisation Committee		
		Ongoing: Analytical work, including the launch of a public consultation, to determine the scope of a legislative initiative on single-use plastics		
		2018 onwards: Development of measures to limit plastic loss from aquaculture (e.g. possible Best Available Techniques Reference Document)		
		Q1 2018 onwards: Conduct a lifecycle assessment to identify conditions where their [compostable and biodegradable plastics] use is beneficial, and criteria for such application		
		2018 onwards: Improved monitoring and mapping of marine litter, including microplastics, on the basis of EU harmonized methods		
		2018 onwards: Pursue work on life-cycle impacts of alternative feedstocks for plastics production	X	WP2
	Policy-realignment	Q1 2018 onwards: Preparatory work for future revision of the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive: Commission to initiate work on new harmonized rules to ensure that by 2030 all plastics packaging placed on the EU market can be reused or recycled in a cost-effective manner.	X	
		Q1 2018 onwards: Assessment of regulatory or economic incentives for the uptake of recycled content, in particular in the context of the: – Revision of the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive – Evaluation/review of the Construction Products Regulation – Evaluation/review of End-of-life Vehicles Directive		
		Q1 2018: Adoption of a legislative proposal on port reception facilities for the delivery of waste from ships		
		Ongoing: Evaluation of the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive: assessing effectiveness as regards microplastics capture and removal		
		Q2 2018: Development of a Strategic Research Innovation Agenda on plastics to guide future funding decisions		
		2018 onwards: Examining options for specific action to reduce plastic pollution in the Mediterranean, in support of the implementation of the Barcelona Convention		
	Tightening and reformation of relevant legislation	Ongoing: New eco-design measures: consider requirements to support the recyclability of plastics		
		Ongoing: Ensure better implementation of existing obligations on separate collection, including through ongoing review of waste legislation		
		2018: Development of measures to reduce loss or abandonment at sea of fishing gear (e.g. including recycling targets, EPR schemes, recycling funds or deposit schemes)		

		Ongoing: Start the process to restrict the use of oxo-plastics via REACH (note: ECHA withdrew its intention to restrict oxo-degradable plastic under REACH in May of 2019)		
		Ongoing: Start the process to restrict the intentional addition of microplastics to products via REACH (note: a possible adoption of this initiative by the European Commission is expected in 2022)		
		Ongoing: Examination of policy options for reducing unintentional release of microplastics from tyres, textiles and paint (e.g. including minimum requirements for tyre design (tyre abrasion and durability if appropriate) and/or information requirement (including labelling if appropriate), methods to assess microplastic losses from textiles and tyres, combined with information (including possibly labelling)/minimum requirements, targeted research and development funding).		
		Q1 2018 onwards: Development of measures to reduce plastic pellet spillage (e.g. certification scheme along the plastic supply chain and/or Best Available Techniques reference document under the Industrial Emissions Directive).		
		2018 onwards: Support to Member States on the implementation of their programs of measures on marine litter under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, including the link with their waste/litter management plans under the Waste Framework Directive		
		2019: Commission guidance on the eco-modulation of EPR fees		
	Raising awareness (consumers)	2019: Issue new guidelines on separate collection and sorting of waste		
		Q1 2018 onwards: Start work to develop harmonized rules on defining and labelling compostable and biodegradable plastics		
	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Q1-Q3 2018: Launching an EU-wide pledging campaign targeting industry and public authorities		
		2018 onwards: Ecolabel and Green Public Procurement: Further incentivize the use of recycled plastics, including by developing adequate verification means		
		In mid-2018: Recommendations by the recently launched 'Circular Economy Finance Support Platform'		
	Stakeholder cooperation	By mid-2019: Examine the feasibility of a private-led investment fund to finance investments in innovative solutions and new technologies aimed at reducing the environmental impacts of primary plastic production (note: primary plastic production is a process that takes place before the actual compounding process. The compounding process is the part of the value chain that entails the addition of chemical additives and therefore potential persistent and mobile substances)		
		2018 onwards: Project to reduce plastic waste and marine litter in East and South-East Asia to support sustainable consumption and production, the promotion of the waste hierarchy and extended producer responsibility, and improve recovery of fishing gear		
		2018 onwards: Cooperation on plastic waste prevention in major world river basins		
		2018 onward: Renewed engagement on plastics and marine litter in fora such as the UN, G7, G20, the MARPOL convention and regional sea conventions, including the development of practical tools and specific action on fishing and aquaculture.		
		2018 onward: Support to action under the Basel Convention, particularly for the implementation of the toolkit on environmentally sound waste management		
		2018 onward: Promote a circular plastics economy in non-EU countries through policy dialogues on trade, industry and environment, as well as economic diplomacy		
		2018 onward: Support the development of international industry standards on sorted plastic waste and recycled plastics		
	2018 onward: Ensure that exported plastic waste is dealt with appropriately in line with the EU Waste Shipment Regulation			
	2018 onward: Support the development of a certification scheme for recycling plants in the EU and in third countries			

	Financing	Ongoing: Direct financial support for infrastructure and innovation through the European Fund for Strategic Investment and other EU funding instruments (e.g. structural funds and smart specialization strategies, Horizon 2020)	X	
		2018 onward: Use bilateral, regional and thematic funding in EU development, neighborhood and enlargement policies to support the plastics strategy by preventing and appropriately managing waste and supporting the circular economy; through programs and instruments including 'Switch to Green' and the External Investment Plan		
	Other	N/A		
Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		N/A		
Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		N/A		
Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		N/A		
Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback		<p>N/A – There was no official period to give feedback organized by the Commission. There was however, under Annex III, a voluntary pledging campaign (including a subsequent assessment) toward the uptake of recycled plastics and other objectives of the strategy paper.</p> <p>Link to voluntary pledges under the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy: https://ec.europa.eu/growth/news/european-strategy-plastics-voluntary-pledges-2019-03-04_en (accessed 22.06.2022)</p> <p>Assessment report of the voluntary pledges under Annex III of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy: https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/34267 (accessed 22.06.2022)</p>		
Challenges		<p>A challenge of a globally increasing demand for plastics and a corresponding danger of inadequate waste stream treatments: While production and use of plastics drastically increased and is expected to further increase in the future, the EU did not tap into the potential of recycling and or reusing plastic waste yet. The rates of plastic landfilling and incineration are still high. Especially incineration leads to a rise of CO²-emissions. At the same time, a lot of waste streams are shipped into third countries for treatment, which often do not share the same environmental standards as the EU does. All of this leads to value losses by wasted materials that could otherwise be salvaged and used in the secondary market.</p> <p>A challenge of leakages of plastics into the environment: Leakages on land and sea cause economic (tourism, fishing, shipping) as well as environmental damage (forming of plastic litter, degradation into microplastics, long distance travel of plastics by e.g. marine currents that generate problems not only for the EU).</p> <p>A challenge of microplastics: Microplastics accumulate in the sea, are able to enter food chains and can be found in the air, in drinking water and foods. Yet, there is a lack of research on resulting health-impacts. Microplastics that are emitted into the environment directly and not by degradation of larger plastic pieces make preventing and or tracking them additionally challenging.</p> <p>A challenge of lacking interest and therefore low investments in plastic recycling: Low demand and accordingly low prospects of profitability decrease necessary investments. This includes among others a lack of common standards regarding sorted plastic waste, which leads to diversity in production (different polymers, different additives for plastic articles), which ends up making recycling more difficult and correspondingly less attractive for investors.</p>		

	<p>This is related to ZeroPM, since uncertainties of chemical composition and potential contamination by (persistent) substances of concern, regarding plastic waste that is intended for recycling, does further discourage demand while thematically intermingling with ZeroPMs goals.</p> <p>A challenge of biodegradable plastics: Unclearities in regards to informing about the (biodegradable) properties of plastics in purchased products by consumers could lead to more plastic leakage and littering and create problems in terms of mechanical recycling. These issues have to be solved to effectively profit from biodegradable plastics.</p> <p>A global challenge: According to the document, problems and opportunities regarding the plastic-problem are a task of international concern and action, since plastic-waste-streams are rarely coupled to national borders. An increasing global awareness is therefore necessary.</p> <p>A challenge of cooperation: To achieve the proposed objectives of the document, all key players of the value chain need to cooperate – from plastic producers, to recyclers, to retailers, consumers and civil society as well as science, governments and authorities. Especially a lack of knowledge and unclear information are a hurdle at different stages. This applies to manufacturers and consumers all the same.</p>
<p>Proposed timeline</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adoption of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy by the European Commission: January 16th 2018 • Planned review: not stated in the strategy document.
<p>Links</p>	<p>Overview by the European Commission: https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/research-area/environment/circular-economy/plastics-circular-economy_en (accessed 22.06.2022)</p> <p>A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy; COM(2018) 28 final: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2018:28:FIN (accessed 22.06.2022)</p> <p>Commission Staff Working Document accompanying the document “A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy”; SWD(2018) 16 final: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52018SC0016 (accessed 22.06.2022)</p>
<p>Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document</p>	<p>Strategy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - COM (2018) 32 final (Communication on the implementation of the circular economy package: options to address the interface between chemical, product and waste legislation. Note: This came before the Green Deal and might be outdated and therefore of low relevance due to the existence of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and the Zero Pollution Action Plan) <p>Legislative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Directive 94/62/EC (Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive) - Directive 98/83/EC (Drinking Water Directive) - Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 (on shipments of waste) - Directive 2008/56/EC (Marine Strategy Framework Directive) - Directive 2008/98/EC (on waste and repealing certain Directives) - Directive 2009/125/EC (Ecodesign Directive) - Directive (EU) 2019/883 (on port reception facilities for the delivery of waste from ships, repealing Directive 2000/59/EC and amending Directive 2009/16/EC and Directive 2010/65/EU) - Regulation (EU) 2021/695 (Horizon Europe) <p>Convention:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2030 SDGs

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Barcelona Convention - Basel Convention (on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal) - Bucharest Convention - HELCOM Convention (Baltic) - International Convention for the Prevention of Marine Pollution from Ships (MARPOL) - OSPAR Convention (North East Atlantic) - Our Ocean Conference - UN Global Partnership on Marine Litter - United Nations Environment Assembly
Links to other ZeroPM-WPs	<p>WP2 (Alternative Assessment): Actions that link the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy to WP2 might be found in the undertaking to improve the traceability of chemicals and the addressing of legacy substances in recycled streams as well as in the use of life-cycle assessments of alternative feedstocks for plastics production.</p> <p>WP5 & WP6 (Substance grouping & Risk Assessment): Actions that aim to better characterize contaminants of food-contact materials and the planned monitoring system might be of interest for WP5 and WP6.</p>
Notes	<p>This document from 2018 is not part of the European Green Deal and therefore not derived from the “New Circular Economy Action Plan” from 2020. It does complement the original “Circular Economy Action Plan” from 2015 though.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A total of 39 actions to be found in annex I of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy. • Annex II lists voluntary measures, that are recommended to national authorities and the industry. • Annex III contains a pledging campaign for voluntary action of stakeholders.

Table for further analysis of actions/measures with relevance to ZeroPM:

Actions, Sub-actions and Relevance to ZeroPM		Subcategories:							Prioritize	Remediate	
		Research & Development	Policy-realignment	Tightening and re-formation of relevant legislation	Raising awareness (consumers)	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Stakeholder co-operation	Financing			Other
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	<p>Q1 2018 onwards: Follow-up to COM (2018) 32 "<i>Communication on the implementation of the circular economy package: options to address the interface between chemical, product and waste legislation</i>": improve the traceability of chemicals and address the issue of legacy substances in recycled streams</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Legacy substances describe persistent substances. As such, improving or developing methods to trace the abovementioned substances and addressing recycled streams should be of interest for ZeroPM. The action also states, that it aims to make it easier to process or remove those substances during recycling.</p>	X									X
	<p>Ongoing: As regards food-contact materials: swift finalization of pending authorization procedures for plastics recycling processes, better characterization of contaminants and introduction of monitoring system</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> The better characterization of contaminants as well as introducing monitoring systems are of relevance regarding persistent and mobile substances. In addition, this action focuses on food-contact materials, which often are a subject of ZeroPMs agenda.</p>	X							X		
	<p>2019: Issue new guidelines on separate collection and sorting of waste</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> According to the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy, the quality of the separate collection and sorting is essential for avoiding contamination of waste streams intended for recycling with substances of concern. Because of this, persistent and mobile substances might be addressed as well.</p>		X		X						
	<p>Ongoing: Ensure better implementation of existing obligations on separate collection, including through ongoing review of waste legislation</p>		X	X							

	<p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>According to the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy, the quality of the separate collection and sorting is essential for avoiding contamination of waste streams intended for recycling with substances of concern. Because of this, persistent and mobile substances might be addressed as well.</p>									
	<p>Q1 2018: Adoption of a legislative proposal on port reception facilities for the delivery of waste from ships</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This action deals with measures that shall ensure that waste, that is generated on ships or gathered at sea, is treated in an adequate way on land. This might include waste that is contaminated by persistent and mobile substances. The directive that sprang forth from this action is Directive (EU) 2019/883, which refers to MARPOL (International Convention for the Prevention of Marine Pollution from Ships) in terms of “noxious” and “harmful” substances.</p>		X							
	<p>2018 onwards: Improved monitoring and mapping of marine litter, including microplastics, on the basis of EU harmonized methods</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>Industrial emissions are a subset of marine litter. Therefore, marine litter constitutes a source for persistent and mobile substances, which again leads to relevance regarding mapping and monitoring efforts.</p>	X								
	<p>2018 onwards: Support to Member States on the implementation of their programs of measures on marine litter under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, including the link with their waste/litter management plans under the Waste Framework Directive</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>Industrial emissions are a subset of marine litter. Therefore, marine litter constitutes a source for persistent and mobile substances.</p>			X		x				
	<p>2019: Commission guidance on the eco-modulation of EPR fees</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This action might be of relevance, if the stated EPR (extended producers’ responsibility) fees will be applied in terms of concerning substances too. If</p>			X						

	<p>producers are incentivized to develop more sustainable (plastic) products by otherwise having a fee to pay, this could very well result in a decrease of emissions of persistent and mobile substances, depending on what is included in the actual guidelines.</p>									
	<p>2018 onwards: Pursue work on life-cycle impacts of alternative feedstocks for plastics production</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This could be of relevance especially for WP2. If alternatives for unsustainable plastics (and in terms of biodegradability) are sought after, then this would be a chance to bring in alternatives free from persistent and mobile substances. (Note: Additives of the compounding process will play a big role in terms of relevance. For comparison see Nessi, et.al. 2021 "Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of alternative feedstocks for plastics production").</p>	X								
	<p>Ongoing: Direct financial support for infrastructure and innovation through the European Fund for Strategic Investment and other EU funding instruments (e.g. structural funds and smart specialization strategies, Horizon 2020)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>Since innovation programs like Horizon 2020 are funding ZeroPM itself, this action is automatically relevant for the reduction and prevention of persistent and mobile substances in the long run.</p>						X			
	<p>2018 onward: Support to action under the Basel Convention, particularly for the implementation of the toolkit on environmentally sound waste management</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>The Basel Conventions and its Environmentally Sound Management (ESM) toolkit do mention electrical waste as well as substances, "which are not identified and/or are new and whose effects on man and/or the environment are not known" in annex I "Categories of waste to be controlled". However, annex III, which lists hazardous characteristics does not explicitly include persistence or mobility. This action might be of relevance if persistent and mobile substances are included.</p>					X				
	<p>Q1 2018 onwards: Preparatory work for future revision of the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive: Commission to initiate work on new harmonized rules to ensure that by 2030 all plastics packaging placed on the EU market can be</p>		X							

Appendix N: Zero Pollution Action Plan

Name(s) of the initiative/policy		EU Action Plan: “Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil” Zero Pollution Action Plan COM(2021) 400 final (complemented by SWD(2021) 140 final and SWD(2021) 141 final)
Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM		<p>The Zero Pollution Action Plan describes an EU-initiative under the European Green Deal that envisions a pollution-free world by 2050. It proposes at its core the need to restore and sustain natural ecosystems, by preventing pollution before it happens, monitoring as well as reporting and – if necessary, ultimately – remediating it, to achieve a toxic-free, healthy environment for Europeans. This includes a) air pollution by noise, particles and other emissions, b) soil pollution by nutrient losses and the use of chemicals, c) the loss of biodiversity, d) plastic litter and micro-plastic-emissions as well as e) waste-generation and waste-management.</p> <p>To achieve these goals by 2050, the action plan works as an overarching strategy-paper that alludes many other European initiatives and therefore takes all relevant ongoing and planned EU-efforts and legislatives and integrates them into a comprehensive strategy. Since implementation will take some time and therefore the implementation process will be cumulative the strategy paper sets intermediate goals that are to be achieved by 2030.</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM: The Zero Pollution Action Plan is of high relevance to ZeroPM. It engages with many policy-areas like water or soil, as well as with chemicals and pollution and therefore directly or indirectly with persistent and mobile substances as well. A lot of the proposed actions, goals and specific targets align with ZeroPMs agenda.</p>
Type of act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication • Delegated act • Implementing act • Legislative proposal • Others
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)	<p>First, the general objective of the Zero Pollution Action Plan can be found in the “Zero Pollution Ambition” for 2050. It states: “<i>Air, water and soil pollution is reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems and that respect the boundaries our planet can cope with, thus creating a toxic-free environment</i>”.</p> <p>Second: “<i>The main objective of this action plan is to provide a compass for including pollution prevention in all relevant EU policies, maximising synergies in an effective and proportionate way, stepping up implementation and identifying possible gaps or trade-offs</i>”.</p> <p>Finally, a third goal can be identified in form of the “Zero pollution hierarchy”: Reactive action of the EU, after the damage is done, shall not be the focal point of its engagement. Rather the reverse – aligning with the ideals of ZeroPM – shall be strived for: the prevention of environmental damage – if possible – before it even occurs. After that, pollution should be minimised where full prevention is not achievable. Only then, remediation shall be of essence. Integrated in this hierarchy and therefore in upcoming EU-environmental-policies shall be the precautionary principle, the polluter-pays-principle, the principle that preventive action should be taken, as well as the principle that environmental damage should be, as a priority, be rectified at source.</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM:</p>

		<p>A precondition for a truly “toxic-free environment” is the prevention and eventual elimination of persistent and mobile substances. In this regard and in the matter of introducing the topic to all other relevant EU policies, the general objective of the action plan mirrors ZeroPMs main-goal to some extent. This is expressed furthermore by the fact, that not only ZeroPM, but also the Zero Pollution Action Plan both lean heavily on the hierarchy to fight pollution which was first presented by the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) in 2020.</p>
	<p>Specific Objectives</p>	<p>Seven specific Objectives can be directly derived from the subitems of the Zero Pollution Action Plan. These include the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improvement of health and well-being by the implementation of the Zero-Pollution-Ambition in different environmental media (air, water, soil, waste). This includes noise-pollution and pollution by chemicals and focuses mostly on various aspects of human health and consequences of ongoing pollution for the same. 2. Living within our planetary boundaries by keeping a pollution footprint from overstepping levels that the planet and therefore humankind can no longer cope with. This objective of the Zero Pollution Action Plan emphasizes the protection of environmental media in regards to ecosystems and the environment as the foundation of life itself. 3. Moving towards zero pollution from production and consumption by moving to a strategy of “green growth” that decouples economic growth from an increase in pollution. A transformation of production and consumption patterns towards zero pollution by circular economic practices, clean and sustainable designs, the promotion of low-emissions, new (digital) technologies and the phasing out of alarming chemicals shall be strived for. 4. Ensure stricter implementation and enforcement of regulations, including support of civil societies role as a “compliance watchdog” of sorts. 5. Boost change across society for zero pollution by integrating people in a variety of ways into the zero-pollution-strategy (like complement public funding by “green” and sustainable investments of the private sector, involvement of cities and regions by EU-cooperation in zero-pollution-practices and by promoting research, innovations and digital solutions to better educate, train, inform and support people, especially in regards to “green skills” and the labor market). 6. Promote worldwide change for zero pollution and do not settle on the European Space only, since often pollution is a problem unhindered by national borders. Also reduce EUs external pollution footprint in the process. (Note: The Zero Pollution Action Plan still highlights cooperation – among others – with Russia. It was presented before the Ukrainian-Russian-war in 2022.) 7. Track progress, anticipate trends and mainstream zero pollution by efforts of monitoring different types of pollution, assessing the impact of said pollution on health, environment, economy and society as well by long-term-data-collection that can be used for “early warning”-systems and future recommendations. <p>Also, there are six specific targets set in the Zero pollution Action Plan in annex 2 that are – as a milestone – to be achieved by 2030:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>By 2030 the EU should reduce by more than 55% the health impacts (premature deaths) of air pollution</i> 2. <i>By 2030 the EU should reduce by 30% the share of people chronically disturbed by transport noise</i> 3. <i>By 2030 the EU should reduce by 25% the EU ecosystems where air pollution threatens biodiversity</i> 4. <i>By 2030 the EU should reduce by 50% nutrient losses, the use and risk of chemical pesticides and the use of the more hazardous ones, and the sale of antimicrobials for farmed animals and in aquaculture</i> 5. <i>By 2030 the EU should reduce by 50% plastic litter at sea and by 30% micro-plastics released into the environment</i> 6. <i>By 2030 the EU should reduce significantly total waste generation and by 50% residual municipal waste.</i>

		Complementing these targets, a set of key actions, that are planned to be implemented in 2021-2024 , are specified in the action plan (listed below). In 2025 stock will be taken by the European Commission in regards to the degree of implementation and a review and identification of further needs for subsequent actions and targets will be held.		
			Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Research & Development	As from 2022: Reducing health inequalities through zero pollution. Regularly feed pollution monitoring and outlook data into the Cancer Inequalities Registry and the Atlas of Demography’s. (Flagship1)	X	WP6
		As from 2023: Build capacity and improve knowledge on less polluting practices with national advisory services for farmers	X	
		As from 2024: Create Destination Earth to develop a very high precision digital model of the Earth with Copernicus data as key building block to monitor the state of air, freshwaters, seas and soil		
		2022 & 2024: Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook Reports	X	WP6
		2023/2024: Develop a ‘European Environment and Health Atlas’	X	WP6
	Policy-realignment	As from 2022: Supporting urban zero pollution action. As part of the future Year of Greener Cities, in synergy with the proposed Horizon Europe Mission for Climate Neutral and Smart Cities, the revision of the Urban Mobility Package, the Covenant of Mayors, and the New European Bauhaus initiative, identify key urban greening and innovation needs to prevent pollution, including indoors. By 2024, the Commission will reward the cities reporting the most progress over 2021-2023 in reducing air, water and soil pollution. (Flagship 2) #		
		2022: Revise the Ambient Air Quality Directives		
		2022: Implementation Report on the Environmental Noise Directive		
		2023: Assess pathways and policy options to improve indoor air quality, and propose legislative measure as relevant		
		2021-2023: Review and, if necessary, revise the Bathing Water Directive	X	WP5
		As from 2021: Review and, if necessary, revise the Energy Efficiency Directive, the Renewable Energy Directive and the eco-design and energy labelling requirements for heating appliances		
		2021-2023: Review and, if necessary, revise the Marine Strategy Framework Directive	X	
		2022: Revise the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive in synergy with the review of the Industrial Emissions Directive and the evaluation of the Sewage Sludge Directive	X	WP7
		2022: Revise the Environmental Quality Standards Directive and the Groundwater Directive	X	
		2021/2022: Revision of the Industrial Emissions Directive and the E-PRTR Regulation	X	WP4
		2024: Recommendations on the basis of a fitness check on the implementation of the polluter pays principle	X	WP4
		2022: Revision of the Mercury Regulation		
		2021: Revise the Environmental Crime Directive	X	
2023: Fitness check of the Environmental Liability Directive	X			
Tightening and reformation of	2021: Introduce more stringent emission limits for motor vehicles (Euro 7)			
	As from 2021: Reduce air and noise emissions from transport at source by updating, where relevant, EU or international regulatory frameworks			

	relevant legislation	As from 2022: Support the implementation of the new Drinking Water Directive and adopt relevant implementing and delegated acts	X	
		2022: Reduce underwater noise and marine litter through EU threshold values to be set under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive	X	
		2022-2023: Support the implementation of the Strategic Guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture - Environmental performance aspects	X	WP5/6
	Raising awareness (consumers)	N/A		
	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	2024: Promoting zero pollution across regions. In cooperation with the Committee of the Regions, present a Scoreboard of EU regions' green performance to measure, in particular, efforts to achieve pollution-relevant targets. (Flagship 3)	X	
		As from 2022: Facilitating zero pollution choices. Encourage public and private sector operators to make 'zero pollution pledges' to promote best available, 'near-zero waste' and least polluting options. (Flagship 4)	X	
		2023: Compile and make accessible in a digital format all main obligations on nutrient management stemming from EU law to limit the environmental footprint of farming activities		
		2023: Create a zero-pollution contribution to the European Green Deal Dataspace to improve data availability	X	WP4
		As from 2021: Improved training and educational support on environmental risks including pharmaceuticals through: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> tailored EU training modules for healthcare and other social care sector workers Guidelines for healthcare professionals on the prudent use of pharmaceuticals and support to include environmental aspects in training and professional development programs Training and educational support for climate, environment, and health conscious professionals and economic operators. 		
		As from 2022: Showcasing zero pollution solutions for buildings. Showcase from the renovation wave strategy and New European Bauhaus initiative how building projects and the use of Local Digital Twins can contribute to zero pollution objectives. (Flagship 6)		
	Stakeholder cooperation	As from 2021: Support international work on best available techniques (BAT), including new and emerging technologies, to reduce industrial emissions and on the revision of the Kyiv Protocol (PRTR) to improve public access to information on those emissions		
		As from 2022: Enforcing zero pollution together. Bring together environmental and other enforcement authorities to kick off the exchange of best practices and encourage Member States to devise cross-sectorial compliance actions towards zero tolerance for pollution at national level and transboundary level. (Flagship 5)	X	
		2021: Living Labs for green digital solutions and smart zero pollution. Launch Living Labs for green digital solutions and smart zero pollution to help develop local actions for green and digital transformation. (Flagship 7)		
		As from 2021: Advance international cooperation on black carbon policies to reduce climate change impacts and improve air quality		
		As from 2021/2022: Support global action on the export of end-of-life and used vehicles	X	

		As from 2021: Support initiatives to better monitor and manage international trade for waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) and waste batteries	X	WP5
		As from 2021/2022: Support a global initiative to end informal recycling of used lead acid batteries	X	
		As from 2021: Minimizing the EU's external pollution footprint. Promote global zero pollution in all relevant international fora and work with the EU Member States and stakeholders. (Flagship 8)	X	WP8
		As from 2021: Launch Zero Pollution Stakeholder Platform (including thematic hubs, e.g. on digital solutions, clean air tech, soil pollution)	X	WP2/4/8
	Financing	N/A		
	Other	2022/2023: Follow up of the evaluation of the Outdoor Noise Directive		
Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		2022-2024: Identify and remedy contaminated sites by: establishing an EU priority watch list for soil contaminants and introducing a zero-soil pollution module in the future LUCAS survey	X	WP5
Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		2022-2024: Identify and remedy contaminated sites by facilitating and promoting awareness of public and private funding for identification, investigation, assessment and remediation of contaminated soils and groundwater.	X	
		2022-2024: Identify and remedy contaminated sites by investigating best practices and providing guidance for a passport for the safe, sustainable and circular use of excavated soil		
Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)		As from 2021: Consolidating EU's Knowledge Centres for Zero Pollution. Consolidate the roles of the European Environment Agency (EEA) and the Joint Research Centre (JRC) as the EU's Knowledge Centres of Excellence for Zero Pollution. (Flagship 9)		
Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback		<p>Feedback was given in form of a 4 weeks long feedback period that ended on 29th October 2020. 111 replies were given. These are available under: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12588-Towards-zero-pollution-in-air-water-and-soil-EU-action-plan/feedback_en?p_id=8608948 (accessed 21.06.2022)</p> <p>Also, there was a public consultation (Eurobarometer) to give feedback for a duration of 12 weeks that finished on 10th February 2021. 699 replies of feedback were given in total. The resulting data is free to be downloaded in form of an excel-sheet. Data and download can be found here: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12588-EU-Action-Plan-Towards-a-Zero-Pollution-Ambition-for-air-water-and-soil/public-consultation_en (accessed 21.06.2022)</p> <p>The public consultation also brought forth an Ares(2021)3143582 summary report that is available here: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=PL_COM:Ares(2021)3153819&from=EN (accessed 21.06.2022)</p> <p>A section of the Zero Pollution Action Plan itself states the following insights in response to the summary report:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respondents seem to view that relevant societal actors are not doing enough and that EU and national governments need to take more action • There is a demand to step up international action • There is a demand for better implementation of polluted-related legislation • There is a demand for promotion of formal education and therefore for influencing behavioral change 		
Challenges		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An economic challenge: The need to decouple pollution from growth brings a multitude of friction points with it. Industrial emissions, for example, annually account according to the Zero Pollution Action Plan for close to €100 billion of damage. In this regard, the striving for short-term instead of long-term economic profits by – among other things – still viewing pollution for the most part as an external instead of an internal cost and therefore only addressing it by regulation, is a problem. To solve this by applying the polluter-pays-principle and assigning a 		

	<p>price for pollution will be as much as a challenge as the demand of transforming production and consumption modes while simultaneously sustaining European prosperity and creating and consolidating a non-toxic material cycle.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A challenge of insufficient implementation: Quite some legislations and regulations like the Ambient Air Quality Directive or the freshwater legislation have been – according to the Zero Pollution Action Plan – only partially effective or even outright insufficient. This is caused by a factette of factors like a lack of investments, a limited inclusion of protection objectives in other policy-areas, the need to better address chemical pollution or simply because of a slow and or negligent process of implementation in general. These gaps in implementation cost society according to the Zero Pollution Action Plan around €55 billion per year alone in regards to environmental law. • International challenges: The Zero Pollution Action Plan makes it quite clear, that pollution does not stop at borders. Instead, pollution enters and leaves the EU through oceans, rivers, winds and imported as well as exported goods. Considering this, the external pollution footprint of the EU is something to look out for. Accompanying this, there is a need to gather an international willingness to adopt, act, harmonize and implement new standards in form of multilateral and international law to advance a “<i>global zero pollution agenda</i>”. This includes areas of growing concern in developing countries like streams of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE), waste batteries, but also inadequate management of end-of-life vehicles (ELVs). • Digital challenge: The development and provision of digital technologies and tools contains meaningful and innovative potential to further the goals of the Zero Pollution Action Plan. At the same time certain risks arise according to the Zero Pollution Action Plan, that need to be mitigated while still reaping the benefits. Related to that is the need to prevent a lack of data to hinder the transition.
<p>Proposed timeline</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First presentation of the Zero Pollution Action Plan (roadmap): October 1st 2020 (announced already in the European Green Deal in December 2019) • Adoption of the Zero Pollution Action Plan by the European Commission: May 12th 2021 • Planned review of the Zero Pollution Action Plan and its degree of implementation by the European Commission by 2025.
<p>Links</p>	<p>Overview by the European Commission: https://ec.europa.eu/environment/strategy/zero-pollution-action-plan_de (accessed 21.06.2022)</p> <p>Zero Pollution Action Plan; COM(2021) 400 final: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0400&qid=1623311742827 (accessed 21.06.2022)</p> <p>Complementary staff working document (SWD) of the Zero Pollution Action Plan on digital solutions; SWD(2021) 140 final: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52021SC0140 (accessed 21.06.2022)</p> <p>Complementary staff working document (SWD) of the Zero Pollution Action Plan on a monitoring and outlook framework; SWD(2021) 141 final: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52021SC0141 (accessed 21.06.2022)</p>
<p>Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document</p>	<p>Strategy documents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COM(2019) 640 final (The European Green Deal) • COM(2020) 98 final (Circular Economy Action Plan) • COM(2020) 380 final (EU Biodiversity Strategy) • COM(2020) 381 final (Farm to Fork Strategy)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COM(2020) 456 final (NextGenerationEU) • COM(2020) 662 final (Renovation Wave) • COM(2020) 667 final (Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability) • COM(2021) 44 final (Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan) • COM(2021) 669 (EU Soil Strategy) <p>Legislative/regulative documents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Directive 86/278/EEC (Sewage Sludge Directive) • Directive 91/271/EEC (Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive) • Directive 98/83/EC (Drinking Water Directive) • Directive (EU) 2016/2284 (National Emission Reduction Commitments (NEC) Directive) • Directive 2000/60/EC (Water Framework Directive) • Directive 2003/4/EC (Directive on public access to environmental information) • Directive 2004/35/CE (Environmental Liability Directive) • Directive 2006/7/EC (Bathing Water Directive) • Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006 (on shipments of waste) • Directive 2007/2/EC (INSPIRE Directive) • Directive 2008/50/EC (Ambient Air Quality Directive) • Directive 2008/56/EC (Marine Strategy Framework Directive) • Directive 2008/99/EC (Environmental Crime Directive) • Directive 2009/128/EC (Sustainable Use of Pesticides) • Directive 2010/75/EU (Industrial Emissions Directive) • Directive 2011/65/EU (on the restriction of certain hazardous substances in electrical and electronical equipment) • Directive 2012/18/EU (Seveso III Directive) • Regulation (EU) 2021/695 (Horizon Europe) <p>Conventions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Barcelona Convention • Basel Convention • Convention on Biological Diversity • Kyiv Protocol on Pollutant Release and Transfer Registers (PRTR) • Minamata Convention • Rotterdam Convention • Stockholm Convention • UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) • UNECE Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes <p>Other:</p>
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<p>Links to other ZeroPM-WPs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green Claims initiative <p>Since the Zero Pollution Action Plan takes the form of a strategic document with goals that align strongly with the ZeroPM-project, the links to other WPs are numerous and can be found throughout its text. Because of this – WP1 aside – all WPs of ZeroPM are linked in some way or another.</p> <p>WP2 (Alternative Assessment): The launch of the Zero Pollution Stakeholder Platform planned for December 2021 might be of interest to WP2, since its goal is to bring together stakeholders and experts to mainstream zero pollution to different policy-areas. By inserting ZeroPM-expert-knowledge, in form of full life cycle considerations and the concerns of persistent and mobile substances, as well of potential alternatives, this platform might prove to be an opportunity to advance ZeroPMs goals and draw attention to persistent and mobile substances. The call for applications is closed at the time though.</p> <p>WP4 (Market Transition): On a similar note, WP4 might find interest in the Zero Pollution Stakeholder Platform as another link to stakeholders and therefore the economy, as well. Aside from that, the revision of the Industrial Emissions Directive (IED) and the E-PRTR Regulation might support the market transition that WP4 is trying to stimulate. Also, the initiation of a Green Deal Dataspace to improve data availability and to help stakeholders, citizens and other players by providing information about pollution in simpler ways should align with WP4s idea of supporting companies and other stakeholders to assist a market-transition by tools like the Marketplace.</p> <p>WP5 (Substance Grouping): The review and possible revision of the Bathing Water Directive as well as the monitoring-endeavors of international initiatives regarding waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) along with waste batteries might be of interest for WP5 in terms of prioritization and or grouping of persistent and mobile substances. The same applies to the identification of contaminated sites in form of an EU priority watch list for soil.</p> <p>WP6 (Risk Assessment): The Zero Pollution Action Plan takes a look at human health in form of different actions. Pollution monitoring and outlook data feeding a Cancer Inequalities Registry as well as the development of an “<i>European Environment and Health Atlas</i>” might be valuable additional data sources for WP6 if substances of interest will be included. The other way around there might be pathways to feed ZeroPM-findings into said initiatives in the future.</p> <p>WP7 (Technical Solutions): The revision of the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive combined with the review of the Industrial Emissions Directive and the Sewage Sludge Directive might be of interest for the work of WP7 and their efforts of remediating water-bodies.</p> <p>WP8 (Dissemination and Communication): Since the EU is planning to promote global zero pollution in all relevant international fora and work with stakeholders and member states alike, there could be possible entryways for WP8 to further disseminate project-findings. Again: The Zero Pollution Stakeholder Platform might come in useful in this context too.</p>
<p>Notes</p>	<p>Annex 1 describes a list of 39 actions in total. These contain flagship-actions (9), actions (33) and a corresponding timetable.</p> <p>The actual document of the Zero Pollution Action Plan contains more and also more nuanced actions than the ones described in annex 1. Nevertheless, all actions included in this template originate from said annex, since it is conceivable, that these are the actions the European Commission is most focused on</p>

	<p>achieving in time. On top of that, some of the further actions that are not listed here were already announced in other documents as well (e.g. the reduction of pollution by pesticides in air, water and soil by 50% until 2020 was announced in “Farm to Fork” and the “Biodiversity Strategy”).</p> <p>Annex 2 describes a list of concrete set out targets that are to be achieved by 2030.</p>
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Table for further analysis of actions/measures with relevance to ZeroPM:

Actions, Sub-actions and Relevance to ZeroPM		Subcategories:							Prioritize	Remediate
		Research & Development	Policy-realignment	Tightening and re-formation of relevant legislation	Raising awareness (consumers)	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Stakeholder co-operation	Financing		
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	<p>As from 2022: Reducing health inequalities through zero pollution. Regularly feed pollution monitoring and outlook data into the Cancer Inequalities Registry and the Atlas of Demography’s. (Flagship1)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> Human health affected by environmental pollution caused by persistent and mobile substances is of relevance for ZeroPM. The same is true for raising citizen-awareness of potential detrimental effects by said substances.</p>	X			X					
	<p>2021-2023: Review and, if necessary, revise the Bathing Water Directive</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> The review and or revision will discuss the need to include new parameters into the directive. This might be a gateway for ZeroPM to attract awareness to persistent and mobile substances in a legal way related to bathing water.</p>		X						X	
	<p>As from 2022: Support the implementation of the new Drinking Water Directive and adopt relevant implementing and delegated acts</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u> “Higher human health protection thanks to more stringent water quality standards, tackling pollutants of concern, such as endocrine disruptors and microplastics...”. Persistent and mobile substances might be addressed among other pollutants of concern as well.</p>		X							

	<p>2024: Promoting zero pollution across regions. In cooperation with the Committee of the Regions, present a Scoreboard of EU regions' green performance to measure, in particular, efforts to achieve pollution-relevant targets.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>An action of relative low relevance. It states to “...measure [...] efforts of EU regions to achieve the pollution-relevant targets set under this action plan and other strategies”. With this, this action – depending on its interpretation – could include pollution by persistent and mobile substances as well.</p>		X							
	<p>2021-2023: Review and, if necessary, revise the Marine Strategy Framework Directive</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>“Taking into account the state of implementation of EU laws addressing key pollution sources [...] and contaminants”. Persistent and mobile substances might be addressed among other pollutants of concern as well.</p>		X							
	<p>2022: Reduce underwater noise and marine litter through EU threshold values to be set under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>Relevance is given because marine litter includes industrial emissions, which can contain persistent and mobile substances.</p>			X						
	<p>2022: Revise the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive in synergy with the review of the Industrial Emissions Directive and the evaluation of the Sewage Sludge Directive</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>“It will also address emerging pollutants such as microplastics and micropollutants, including pharmaceuticals”. Persistent and mobile substances might be addressed among other emerging pollutants of concern as well.</p>		X							
	<p>2022-2024: Identify and remedy contaminated sites by investigating best practices and providing guidance for a passport for the safe, sustainable and circular use of excavated soil</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p>	X					X			X

	<p>Identification and remediation of contaminated sites (soils/groundwater) might include pollution by persistent and mobile substances as well. Further information about the exact implementation of this action is needed.</p>									
	<p>2022-2024: Identify and remedy contaminated sites by facilitating and promoting awareness of public and private funding for identification, investigation, assessment and remediation of contaminated soils and groundwater.</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>Identification and remediation of contaminated sites (soils/groundwater) might include pollution by persistent and mobile substances as well. Further information about the exact implementation of this action is needed.</p>				X	X	X	X		X
	<p>2022: Revise the Environmental Quality Standards Directive and the Groundwater Directive</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>Both directives tackle chemical pollution in water.</p>		X							
	<p>2022-2023: Support the implementation of the Strategic Guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture - Environmental performance aspects</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p><i>“Updating the lists of problematic substances for surface water and groundwater will protect nature and human health from the most relevant substances based on the most up-to-date scientific insights”.</i> Tackling persistent and mobile substances might fall under the category of <i>“up-to-date scientific insights”</i> regarding problematic substances, so this is of relevance for ZeroPM.</p>			X				X		
	<p>2021/2022: Revision of the Industrial Emissions Directive and the E-PRTR Regulation</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p><i>“The Industrial Emissions Directive (IED) is the main instrument regulating air, water and soil pollutant emission from over 52 000 of the largest EU industrial installations”.</i></p> <p>Also, E-PRTR (European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register, adopted 2006 in form of the E-PRTR Regulation) is a register that provides environmental data from</p>		X							

	<p>industrial facilities that contains data of 91 key-pollutants including pesticides and dioxins.</p>									
	<p>As from 2022: Facilitating zero pollution choices. Encourage public and private sector operators to make 'zero pollution pledges' to promote best available, 'near-zero-waste' and least polluting options. (Flagship 4)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>The aim is to provide more options and better information on clean options. The pledge is focused on actions against climate change first and only after that on other topics like chemicals. E.g. the identification of the carbon footprint and following reduction targets for it by pledge-takers is the only mandatory part of the pledge. Optional is the environmental footprint (which contains impacts on air, water, soil, resources and toxicity) as well as the aspect of circularity.</p>				X	X				
	<p>2021: Revise the Environmental Crime Directive</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This contains content like "<i>serious breaches of EU chemicals legislation</i>" and "<i>pollution caused by certain dangerous substances discharged into the aquatic environment of the community</i>". These are problems ZeroPM is working with.</p>		X							
	<p>2023: Fitness check of the Environmental Liability Directive</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>The Environmental Liability Directive includes pollution by (dangerous) substances. "<i>This Directive shall only apply to environmental damage or to an imminent threat of such damage caused by pollution of a diffuse character, where it is possible to establish a causal link between the damage and the activities of individual operators</i>".</p>		X							
	<p>As from 2022: Enforcing zero pollution together. Bring together environmental and other enforcement authorities to kick off the exchange of best practices and encourage Member States to devise cross-sectorial compliance actions towards zero tolerance for pollution at national level and transboundary level. (Flagship 5)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This might be a way to also close gaps within the (legal) implementation framework that effects persistent and mobile substances.</p>			X			X			

	<p>As from 2023: Build capacity and improve knowledge on less polluting practices with national advisory services for farmers</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This includes the attempt to reduce ammonia and nitrate emissions. If persistent and mobile substances will also be targeted, this will be of relevance.</p>				X					
	<p>2023: Create a zero-pollution contribution to the European Green Deal Dataspace to improve data availability</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>Relevance depends on the kind of data that will be shared. If no data about persistent and or mobile substances will be shared this might be a potential data-gap.</p>			X	X					
	<p>As from 2021: Support initiatives to better monitor and manage international trade for waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) and waste batteries</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This might be of relevance depending on what kind of substances can be found within WEEE/waste batteries. If persistent and mobile substances are included ZeroPM should have an interest to engage with respective international initiatives and to give out recommendations.</p>	X	X			X		X		
	<p>As from 2021/2022: Support global action on the export of end-of-life and used vehicles</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This might be of relevance depending on what kind of substances can be found within ELVs (end-of-life-vehicles) and used vehicles. If persistent and mobile substances are included ZeroPM will have an interest.</p>					X				
	<p>As from 2021/2022: Support a global initiative to end informal recycling of used lead acid batteries</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This might be of relevance depending on what kind of substances can be found within lead acid batteries. If persistent and mobile substances are included ZeroPM should have an interest.</p>					X				

	<p>As from 2021: Minimizing the EU’s external pollution footprint. Promote global zero pollution in all relevant international fora and work with the EU Member States and stakeholders. (Flagship 8)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>Dissemination of the issue of persistent and mobile substances on a global level is of relevance for the project.</p>						X			
	<p>2022 & 2024: Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook Reports</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p><i>“Results of relevant innovative research, such as on human biomonitoring, exposure, soil health or pollinators will need to be better taken on board to provide long-term data collection...”</i></p> <p><i>“The Zero Pollution Outlook will analyze synergies and trade-offs between different EU policies, help translate ‘early warnings’ into recommendations on pollutants of increasing concern based on the latest research findings”.</i> This should include findings on persistent and mobile substances and if not, this would be a gap to be closed.</p>	X								
	<p>2023/2024: Develop a ‘European Environment and Health Atlas’</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>This is planned to complement the Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook and thus could be of interest for ZeroPM.</p>	X								
	<p>As from 2021: Launch the Zero Pollution Stakeholder Platform (including thematic hubs, e.g. on digital solutions, clean air tech, soil pollution)</p> <p><u>Relevance to ZeroPM:</u></p> <p>By bringing together different stakeholders and experts there will be a chance for the projects agenda to be heard.</p>				X	X	X			
Relevant actions/measure of the Zero Pollution Action Plan: 25 out of 39										

Appendix O: Towards a monitoring and outlook framework for the zero pollution ambition

Name(s) of the initiative/policy		Towards a Monitoring and Outlook Framework for the Zero Pollution Ambition SWD(2021) 141 final
Brief description & relevance to ZeroPM		<p><i>“The implementation of the zero pollution monitoring and outlook framework will require a clear and effective governance of all partners at EU level involved in the preparation of the outputs, as well as all partners in the member states, who are data owners and users at the same time. Such a governance will build work of other existing governance systems and establish close coordination, as necessary, to create synergies.”</i></p> <p>This working document describes, how monitoring of all kind of pollutants (e.g. Air Quality, Industrial Emissions (E_PPTR), Bathing Water, Monitoring of SDGs, ...) under different thematic strategies (Circular Economy Action Plan, EU Biodiversity Strategy, Farm to Fork, Bioeconomy Strategy, Chemical Strategy for Sustainability) would be combined into a framework to gather data on the current status on pollutants and to monitor changes in pollutant abundance. Based on that monitoring information, an outlook shall be derived to judge the effectiveness of the Zero Pollution Ambition.</p> <p>Relevance to ZeroPM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring indicators for chemicals needs to be defined. Monitoring of chemicals is sustained in this SWD.
Type of act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication Delegated act Implementing act Legislative proposal Others
Objectives/targets & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	General objective(s)	<p>The Zero Pollution Action Plan for air, water and soil offers the opportunity for the development and regular application of an integrated monitoring and outlook framework, complementing the monitoring framework for greenhouse gases set up to monitor the EU’s climate reduction and carbon neutrality targets and the monitoring frameworks which aim to track the targets set out in the Biodiversity Strategy and the Farm to Fork Strategy. Together with the Monitoring Framework for the Circular Economy and the Indicator Framework on Chemicals [note: reference is made to the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability COM(2020) 667], these elements can build the core pillars for a newly developed environmental monitoring framework foreseen under the 8th Environment Action Program (8th EAP).</p> <p>The overall purpose and objectives of the Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook Framework are set out in the Zero Pollution Action Plan. This monitoring framework is implementing the “zero pollution”-part of the overarching monitoring set out in Article 4 of that Proposal.</p> <p><i>“...the monitoring and outlook framework will cover the entire scope of the zero pollution ambition including the monitoring systems developed under the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, the pollution dimension of the upcoming EU Soil Strategy and the upcoming Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan”.</i></p> <p><i>“The monitoring framework will provide an assessment for the achievement of the targets as well as a regular snapshot of the state of environment as regards the key challenges caused by the pollution”.</i></p>

		<p>Relevance to ZeroPM: The relevance of the Monitoring and Outlook Framework for ZeroPM can be assessed as high. Focus lies not on chemicals on their own, but instead on chemicals as an issue to be monitored and on projection (outlook). Also this framework can be seen as a complement for other frameworks, like e.g. those mentioned in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability.</p>	Relevant To ZeroPM:	Relation to other WPs:
	Specific Objectives	<p>Five specific Objectives can be directly derived from the Monitoring and Outlook Framework. These include the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A knowledge system driving the zero pollution ambition towards 2050 and a means for communication, allowing for accountability and engagement of citizens • A contribution to defining wellbeing (the wellbeing framework is rather broad (see e.g. OECD), in the context of this document it focuses on the health dimension which is an integral part of the wellbeing framework.) and planetary boundaries linked to pollution including the ambition to have (at some point) an integrated assessment of the total pollution load (exposure) on human health and (impact) on species and ecosystems • A tool to measure the progress of the zero pollution ambition including the illustration of some successful or challenging policy and implementation progress and effectiveness illustrated through a few telling examples as well as identifying synergies and strengthening coherence with related policy areas • A driver for change towards a more streamlined, simplified, modern, digital monitoring and reporting as well as the uptake of new digital and earth observation technologies resulting in real-near time data flows presented in an accessible way, while reducing administrative burden • Create an overarching, integrated monitoring that satisfies the Better Regulation Guidelines (in particular Section V) 		
Actions/Measures for “prevent and reduce” & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	N/A			
Actions/measures for prioritization & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	<p>“...the Zero Pollution Action Plan and other European Green Deal initiatives have identified a number of targets for 2030 and many additional targets and objectives exist in EU law [...]. The monitoring of these targets is one main purposes of the monitoring framework. These targets are associated to indicators for impacts or pressures. The available indicators linked to the established targets [with relevance for ZeroPM]” have been listed below (From Annex 2 of the Monitoring and Outlook Framework)</p> <p>Part B: KEY HEADLINE INDICATORS ON IMPACTS / HARM</p> <p>(2) Health impact from water pollution: Proportion of population using drinking water which does not meet requirements of the Directive; Comment: Data available annually only from 2023 onwards (new Directive), in 2022, data from current Directive if critical. Explore analysis of specific pollutants (e.g. PFAS, pesticides, nitrates)</p> <p>(4) Health impacts from industrial chemicals: To be identified (see Part C); No indicator available at the moment. Linking to socioeconomic status</p> <p>(9) Environment impact from industrial chemicals: To be identified (see Part C); No annual indicator available at the moment.</p>	X		

	<p>PART C: KEY HEADLINE INDICATORS FOR EMISSIONS AND OTHER POLLUTION PRESSURES ON THE ENVIRONMENT (FOR TREND ANALYSIS)</p> <p>(4) Hazardous chemicals: Aggregated total production and consumption of hazardous chemicals (hazardous for human health and environment): Data from Eurostat (sdg_12_10); Derived from PRODCOM. To be further developed in line with objectives of the Chemicals Strategy. (Note: Linking to socio-economic status will be made, where possible.)</p> <p>(6) Pesticides: Use and risk of chemical pesticides (Risk Indicator (HRI1)); Data from ESTAT (aei_hri); Comment: Indicator link to pesticides reduction target in the Farm to Fork Strategy.</p> <p>(7) Pesticides: Use of the more hazardous pesticides; Data from ESTAT; Comment: Indicator link to pesticides reduction target in the Farm to Fork Strategy and the CAP Communication.</p> <p>(8) Industry: Industrial pollution intensity; data from EEA (see CSI055 indicator)/ ESTAT; Comment: Based on E-PRTR or air emissions account as included in SDG 9.</p> <p>Part E: INDICATORS TO BE DEVELOPED A number of indicators are planned to be developed for various pollution subjects (e.g. “Chemicals” or “Water pollution”)</p>		
<p>Actions/measures for remediation & relevance to ZeroPM (if)</p>	<p>N/A</p>		
<p>Other actions/measures & relevance to ZeroPM (if)</p>	<p>N/A</p>		
<p>Summarized Stakeholder-Feedback</p>	<p>Open public consultation for the preparation of the Zero Pollution Action Plan included an expert section on the pollution monitoring framework Ecorys (2021): “Consultations on the EU Action Plan towards a zero pollution ambition for air, water and soil”; Synopsis Report (see ‘Have your say’ portal’). There is stated:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (50% or more) completely or somewhat agree with the statements relating to the needed improvements of the various aspects to pollution policies. • 58% of the respondents completely agree that linkages of health data with pollution data need to improved • 33%) consider the existing monitoring frameworks for pollution at the EU and national level to be sufficient 		
<p>Challenges</p>	<p>“The work on the zero pollution monitoring and outlook framework is closely coordinated with the 8th EAP work and the aim is to achieve a fully coherent and integrated outcome, e.g. in terms of approach and indicators”.</p> <p>Of relevance for ZeroPM are challenges originating from the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability.</p> <p><i>“The Strategy announces that a framework of indicators will be developed, as part of a wider zero pollution monitoring and outlook framework, in the context of the 8th Environment Action Programme, to monitor the drivers and impacts of chemical pollution and to measure the effectiveness of chemicals legislation. The Commission will also establish Key Performance Indicators to measure the industrial transition towards the production of safe and sustainable chemicals. In addition, the Strategy – as part of the ‘one substance, one assessment’ approach – sets out a number of important actions in relation to chemical monitoring data, in particular:</i></p>		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>making all chemical monitoring data available via the Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring to ensure their findability, accessibility and interoperability</i> • <i>making a legislative proposal to removing legislative obstacles for the re-use of data and better streamlining the flow of chemical data between EU and national authorities</i> • <i>extending the principle of open data and the relevant transparency principles from the EU food safety sector to other pieces of legislation dealing with chemicals</i> • <i>rationalising the use of expertise and resources by proposing the reattribution of technical and scientific work on chemicals performed under the relevant pieces of legislation to European agencies, including work of the relevant scientific committees</i> • <i>enabling EU and national authorities to commission testing and monitoring of substances as part of the regulatory framework when further information is considered necessary"</i> <p>Challenging too, will be the establishment of a zero pollution monitoring concept with several layers of indicators and dimensions in face of the large numbers of "<i>pollutants, sources and endpoints</i>".</p>
<p>Proposed timeline</p>	<p>2022: First 'Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook' report is planned to include following subjects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>"Zero Pollution Monitoring: 'Pollution affecting Health and Biodiversity' (working title) presenting the results of the indicators and assessment listed in [the] SWD.</i> • <i>Zero Pollution Outlook including: Clean Air Outlook; Clean Water and Marine Outlook; Clean Soil Outlook</i> • <i>Zero Pollution Foresight (i.e. the outcome of the FORENV project). A number of stand-alone 'thematic' or 'technical' reports can and should be published around the same time by the knowledge partners directly. The list can evolve during the consultation process but some examples are already given here, in particular:</i> • <i>Zero pollution monitoring by Copernicus</i> • <i>Key results of pollution-related research linked to health and ecosystems based on the reports including pollutants of emerging concern (e.g. ultrafine particles or light pollution) from EU-funded R&I projects;</i> • <i>Key results from the assessment of the final National Energy and Climate Plans (as published in 2020) including on issues such as biodiversity and air quality".</i> <p><i>"In addition to these reports, a Zero Pollution online portal will present selected indicators which can be regularly updated by the European Environment Agency".</i></p> <p>2023: <i>"Follow-up on gaps identified to improve 2024 assessment and update indicators, if possible".</i></p> <p>2024: Ready FOR USE</p>

	<p><i>“Once the indicator set for the monitoring framework has been agreed, the question of aggregating or simplifying the available indicators, at least for communication purposes, may arise. It is attractive to consider the development of a ‘zero pollution index’ or ‘composite indicator’ as is the case for many other policy areas” (DESI).</i></p>
Links	<p>Staff working document (SWD) of the Zero Pollution Action Plan on a monitoring and outlook framework; SWD(2021) 141 final: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52021SC0141 (accessed 21.06.2022)</p> <p>Zero Pollution Action Plan; COM(2021) 400 final: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0400&qid=1623311742827 (accessed 21.06.2022)</p> <p>Complementary staff working document (SWD) of the Zero Pollution Action Plan on digital solutions; SWD(2021) 140 final: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52021SC0140 (accessed 21.06.2022)</p>
Relevant policy/legislation mentioned in the document	<p>Legislation/Regulation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Directive 2000/60/EC (Water Framework Directive) • Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 (REACH) • Directive 2008/56/EC (Marine Strategy Framework Directive) <p>Conventions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) <p>Other:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EEA’s report on ‘The European Environment: State and Outlook’ (SOER) • Fitness Check of environmental monitoring and reporting SWD(2017) 230
Links to other ZeroPM-WPs	N/A
Notes	PFAS are mentioned (e.g. as exemplary pollutant).

Table for further analysis of actions/measures with relevance to ZeroPM:

Actions, Sub-actions and Relevance to ZeroPM		Subcategories:							Prioritize	Remediate	
		Research & Development	Policy-realignment	Tightening and re-formation of relevant legislation	Raising awareness (consumers)	Raising awareness (non-consumers)	Stakeholder co-operation	Financing			Other
Actions/Measures for "prevent and reduce" & relevance to ZeroPM (if)	Set up indicator for chemical pollution	X	X							X	

Appendix P: Regulatory Watch Gantt Chart

OVERVIEW OF REGULATORY INITIATIVES	2022			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
	Revision of REACH Regulation to help achieve a toxic-free environment	CLOSED	CLOSED	
Revision of Cosmetics Regulation	CLOSED	OPEN (UNTIL 21 JUNE 2022)		Upcoming Q4 2022
Revision of the Toy Safety Directive	CLOSED	CLOSED		Upcoming Q4 2022
Revision of Detergents Regulation	CLOSED	CLOSED		Upcoming Q4 2022
Review of the RoHS Directive	CLOSED	CLOSED		Upcoming Q4 2022
Regulation to reduce the impact of microplastic pollution on the environment	CLOSED	CLOSED		Upcoming Q4 2022
Integrated Nutrient Management Action Plan	CLOSED	OPEN (UNTIL 26 AUGUST 2022)		Upcoming Q4 2022
Revision of the Mercury Regulation	CLOSED	CLOSED		Upcoming Q4 2022
Revision of the End-of-life vehicles Directive	CLOSED	CLOSED		Upcoming Q4 2022
One substance, one assessment initiative - streamlining scientific assessments	CLOSED	CLOSED		Upcoming Q4 2022
Repository of health based limit values	CLOSED	N/A		Upcoming Q4 2022
Revision of Annex I POPs Regulation (new PFHxS entry)	N/A	N/A		Upcoming Q4 2022

OVERVIEW OF REGULATORY INITIATIVES

H2020 project Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances
EU Grant Agreement No. 101036756